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Instruction to Author

The followings are the general instructions regarding the structure/format of an article.

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- The following general instructions are to be followed by author(s) in contributing a paper.
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- Unless otherwise specified for different sections, as is stated below, all parts of the manuscript, in general (abstract, text, tables, figure captions, notes and references), must be single-spaced.
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- There should be a title at the top of every table preceded by a number, in Arabic, if more than one table is used. A single sequence of numbers must be used even when tables differ in kind.
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2.3 Acknowledgements

Acknowledgements, if any, should be at the end of the article (before the references).

2.4 Appendices

There should be a title at the top of every appendix preceded by a number, in Roman, if more than one appendix is used. A single sequence of numbers must be used even when appendices differ in kind.

2.5 References

Citations in the text and reference list should follow the procedure prescribed by the Style Manual of American Psychological Association (APA), Sixth Edition.

Editorial

We are pleased to introduce Volume 29, Issue 1 at a critical juncture for academic publishing in India. With the recent announcement to do away with the UGC CARE List, there are important developments taking place towards the assessment and certification of scholarly journals. The UGC now calls for institutions and researchers to adopt a decentralised mechanism with clear, non-binding criteria for journal evaluation that puts the emphasis on editorial quality, robust peer review, and scholarly integrity. This is a welcome shift away from decades of excessive centralisation, delays, and marginalization of numerous Indian language and regional journals under the old system.

This new environment offers a real challenge for regional journals such as ours to receive greater recognition and affirm the worth and heritage built over years of committed scholarship. We have always been a model of high editorial standards and peer review ethics, and our origins in the region have allowed us to retain and enhance local scholarship, culture, and research diversity. By the removal of limiting barriers, our publications are now in a better position to reach not only the academic community in our immediate surroundings but also the wider national and global platform.

The papers in this issue are a testament to our unwavering commitment: they scrutinize cognitive bias in information behavior, bibliometric profile among India's top scientists, geospatial research, and the changing reach of Geographical Indications—among other vital themes. By keeping publishing ethical and promoting inclusivity—particularly with our introduction of DOIs and timely publishing schedule—we make each paper discoverable, citable, and effective.

During this time of change, our journal is a beacon for trustworthy, high-quality research, open to submissions by various scholars looking for substantial engagement and exposure. With the system changing, we reiterate our commitment to promoting higher scholarly standards, honoring regional heritage, and actively participating in the expansion of knowledge in India and beyond.

Thank you for your continued support.

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Cognitive Biases in Information Behavior: From Seeking to Decision-Making

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Abstract: *We live in a complex world that is saturated with information. At every step, at every moment and in every interaction, we make a large number of conscious and unconscious decisions. In the digital age, information is abundantly available, yet individuals often struggle to make objective and well-informed decisions due to cognitive biases. Cognitive biases are mental shortcuts that simplify decision-making but also introduce systematic errors. This article explores the influence of cognitive biases on information behavior, particularly how they shape the processes of information search and selection. Cognitive biases, such as confirmation bias, anchoring, framing effects, and the availability heuristic, impact how users initiate, navigate, and conclude their search for information. These biases often lead individuals to select information that aligns with pre-existing beliefs, overlook alternative perspectives, or rely on easily accessible but potentially misleading data. Ultimately, understanding how cognitive biases shape information behavior is crucial for enhancing decision-making processes, improving information retrieval systems, and promoting a more informed and discerning public in an increasingly information-saturated world.*

Keywords: Anchoring bias, Availability heuristic, Bandwagon Effect, Confirmation Bias, Exposure Effect, Framing Effect, Information Retrieval, Order Effect, Priming Effect, Search Behavior.

1 Introduction

With the widespread availability of digital tools and the internet, information seeking has evolved dramatically. As of April 2025, there are 5.64 billion internet users globally—68.7% of the world's population—who spend an average of 6 hours and 38 minutes online daily. While online activities

range from communication to media consumption, information seeking remains the top motivation, with 62.8% of adults citing it as a primary reason for going online (Digital Around the World, 2025). Platforms like Google process an estimated 8.5 billion searches per day, with 6.3 million queries per minute and over 1 billion voice searches monthly (Dixon, 2025; Jain, 2025). Most of these searches are informational—52.65%, according to Datos—followed by navigational (32.15%), commercial (14.51%), and transactional (just 0.69%) intents (Fishkin, 2024). Search behavior shows adaptability: users often start with short queries of a few words and refine them when the results don't meet their expectations—more frequently on mobile devices than on desktop (Tober, 2022). These evolving patterns highlight the increasing complexity and importance of digital information navigation in everyday life.

In the digital age, understanding how individuals seek and process information is key to comprehending modern information behavior. Information behavior encompasses the various ways people interact with information, particularly through deliberate acts of information seeking, which are shaped by both personal and contextual factors (Chatterjee, 2017). According to Wilson (2000), information seeking is goal-driven and influenced by the seeker's background, the nature of their need, and the resources available. The process of seeking information concludes when individuals feel sufficiently informed to proceed to subsequent decision-making.

The average person makes thousands of decisions every day, most of them unconsciously and guided by mental shortcuts known as heuristics. These shortcuts, while useful, often give rise to cognitive biases that can result in judgments and choices that stray from logic or factual accuracy (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974; Gilovich, Griffin, & Kahneman, 2002; Eldridge, 2023). Cognitive biases are robust and universal psychological patterns that affect judgment and decision-making (Wilke & Mata, 2012; Korteling, Paradies & Sassen-van Meer, 2023). Rooted in predictable cognitive styles, they influence how individuals process and organize information, sometimes resulting in rational outcomes, sometimes leading to poor or suboptimal choices (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973). Individual differences, combined with the mind's limited processing capacity—especially under stress or time pressure—further shape how information is used and decisions are made (Phillips-Wren, Power & Mora, 2019)

Cognitive biases have a profound impact on decision-making across various domains, particularly in health, politics, finance, management, and consumer behavior. In healthcare, bias can lead professionals to overestimate the likelihood of certain conditions based on recent cases, potentially resulting in misdiagnosis (Blumenthal-Barby and Krieger, 2015). In politics, bias often drives individuals to seek information that supports their existing beliefs, impairing objectivity and reinforcing political polarization (Peer & Gamliel, 2013). In finance, cognitive biases can lead to poor investment decisions, as seen in tendencies toward overconfidence or risk aversion (Kumar & Goyal, 2015). Similarly, management decisions are susceptible to biases, which can lead to flawed strategic planning and ineffective leadership (Barnes Jr, 1984). In consumer behavior, emotional attachment, social influence, and marketing tactics often trigger biases that result in irrational purchasing choices. These largely unconscious biases can significantly undermine rational decision-making, often leading to suboptimal outcomes.

Understanding cognitive biases is crucial for improving both information processing and decision-making. As personalization becomes more prevalent in algorithm-driven systems, such as search engines and generative AI tools, understanding the impact of cognitive biases on user behavior is also essential for designing better information systems and decision-support tools that can help counteract

the negative influences of bias. Moreover, awareness of one's own cognitive biases can empower individuals to reflect on and improve their decision-making strategies in both personal and professional contexts.

2 Cognitive Biases

Cognitive biases are unconscious, systematic errors in thinking that affect how individuals perceive, interpret, and act upon information in their environments (Kahneman & Tversky, 1982). Cognitive biases are systematic cognitive dispositions or inclinations in human thinking and reasoning that often do not comply with the tenets of logic, probability reasoning, and plausibility. These intuitive and subconscious tendencies are at the basis of human judgment, decision making, and the resulting behavior. (Korteling, Gerritsma and Toet, 2021)

While cognitive biases are often framed as flaws, they are generally the byproducts of heuristics—mental shortcuts that the brain uses to navigate a complex world efficiently. These shortcuts evolved to help humans make rapid decisions in situations of uncertainty or overload, offering clear evolutionary advantages. The brain is constantly processing a vast stream of information, and heuristics help filter, simplify, and prioritize this input, allowing individuals to respond quickly when necessary (Eldridge, 2023). Heuristics often operate unconsciously, meaning people are typically unaware of the biases that arise from them. According to Kahneman's two-system model of cognition, System 1 governs fast, intuitive thinking and is responsible for many of the snap judgments that lead to cognitive biases. In contrast, System 2 represents slower, analytical reasoning that can override these intuitive judgments with conscious effort (Azzopardi, 2021). However, because engaging System 2 requires time and energy, most daily decisions remain within the domain of the more error-prone System 1.

Since the foundational work of Tversky and Kahneman (1974), researchers have identified over 180 types of cognitive biases. These can be broadly categorized into four major groups based on common mental challenges. First, biases stemming from information overload occur because the brain must rapidly filter massive quantities of data, often ignoring useful information in the process. Second, biases related to the lack of inherent meaning in information arise when the brain attempts to fill in gaps and make sense of fragmented input, sometimes creating false narratives or imagined details. Third, action-oriented biases occur due to the need to act quickly and decisively, which can lead to snap judgments that are unfair or counterproductive. Lastly, memory-based biases reflect the limitations of our recall processes, which often reinforce errors and distortions in future thinking (Benson & Manoogian, 2016). These categories demonstrate the various ways in which cognitive shortcuts, though helpful in navigating complexity, can systematically distort human judgment and decision-making.

3 The Role of Cognitive Biases in Search Behavior

Cognitive biases play a significant role in shaping an individual's information-seeking behavior throughout the entire search process, influencing both the approach to query formulation and the subsequent interpretation of search results. The process of information seeking typically unfolds in four stages: querying, examining result lists, judging result items, and assessing search satisfaction (Azzopardi, 2021). Cognitive biases are evident in each of these stages, from pre-search influences, such as existing beliefs or expectations that guide the types of queries users initiate, to the ongoing

evaluation of results during and after the search. For instance, during the pre-search phase, users' cognitive biases—such as confirmation bias—may lead them to formulate queries that align with their pre-existing attitudes or beliefs. This bias can steer individuals toward certain information sources while dismissing others, thus shaping their entire search experience.

Similarly, during the search process, biases like selective exposure can influence how users interact with search results. Selective exposure refers to the tendency to seek out information that supports one's current viewpoints, both consciously and unconsciously, which can lead users to prioritize links that align with their ideological stance (Robertson, Lazer & Wilson, 2018). As a result, even in algorithmically-driven environments designed to present a range of perspectives, users are likely to engage more with identity-congruent content. The rise of large language models and AI-powered chatbots presents a new challenge, as slight variations in user prompts can yield vastly different results due to their stochastic nature (Röttger et al., 2024). This further emphasizes the complexity of information seeking, as users' intent—the underlying reason for conducting a search—directly affects the types of queries they submit. Consequently, the way users phrase their search queries is influenced by their personal attitudes and information needs, which can further reinforce cognitive biases. The complexity of information seeking is emphasized by how users' intent, attitudes, and information needs shape their search queries, often reinforcing cognitive biases.

3.1 Common Cognitive Biases in Information Seeking

There are numerous types of biases, including several subcategories; however, the following table depicts the most common forms of cognitive bias that influence our search behaviour.

Table 1. Cognitive Biases Influencing Different Stages of Search Behaviour

	Querying	Examining	Judging	Satisfaction
Information overload	Confirmation Bias	Confirmation, Availability, Framing Effects	Confirmation, Anchoring, Availability, Framing Effects	
Lack of meaning	Bandwagon Effect	Bandwagon Effect	Bandwagon Effect, Exposure Effect	
Need to act quickly		Ambiguity Effect	Ambiguity Effect	Less is more
recall/ memory	Priming Effect	Order Effects	Priming Effect, Order Effects	Priming Effect, Peak End Rule

- **Confirmation Bias**

Confirmation bias, commonly defined in psychological literature as the tendency to seek or interpret evidence in ways that favor pre-existing beliefs, expectations, or hypotheses (Nickerson, 1998), remains a significant factor in online information behavior. Evidence suggests that users often prefer search queries that align with their existing attitudes (Ekström, Madison, Olsson & Tsapos, 2024), and there is increasing support for the notion that individuals engage more with attitude-consistent content—a pattern referred to as selective exposure or confirmation bias. For example, experiments by

Knobloch-Westerwick et al. (2015) using simulated search results demonstrated that users not only prefer but also spend more time with content aligned with their views, reinforcing the presence of selective exposure.

- **Anchoring Bias**

Anchoring bias is a cognitive tendency to rely excessively on the first piece of information encountered, which then serves as a reference point for interpreting subsequent information (The Decision Lab, n.d.). This bias leads individuals to assess later data relative to the initial "anchor," rather than evaluating it objectively. In the context of online search, anchoring occurs when the first result on a search engine results page (SERP) shapes users' perceptions of the information that follows (Tversky & Kahneman, 1974). For instance, if the top result frames a medical condition as severe, users may continue to view it as such despite later results downplaying its severity. This effect persists even when users are unaware of the influence, often diminishing the level of critical thinking applied to subsequent information (Novin & Meyers, 2017).

- **Availability Heuristic**

The availability heuristic is the tendency to rely on information that is easily available or retrievable from memory rather than seeking out and objectively evaluating all relevant information (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973). This heuristic is influenced by factors such as salience, vividness, negativity, and the primacy-recency effect, which enhance recall and lead individuals to judge the frequency or likelihood of events based on how easily examples come to mind (Tversky & Kahneman, 1973; Dale, 2015). It operates on the assumption that readily recalled information is more important than less accessible alternatives. In the digital age, this effect is amplified by the constant availability of information online, leading individuals to misattribute externally accessible information to their own knowledge—a phenomenon known as the Google Effect—which can reduce the motivation to internalize or rehearse information (The Decision Lab, n.d.).

- **Framing Effects**

The framing effect refers to the cognitive bias in which individuals' decisions are influenced by how information is presented, particularly whether it is framed in a positive or negative light (Framing Effect (Psychology), n.d.). This effect highlights that identical information can lead to different responses depending on contextual cues, such as wording, imagery, emotional tone, or reference points (Framing effect, n.d.). In the context of search engine results pages (SERPs), one form of framing is the document genre (e.g., blog, news report, journal article), which shapes users' interpretations of a source's credibility and purpose (Novin & Meyers, 2017). These framing elements reduce cognitive effort by embedding additional meaning, subtly guiding decision-making through both the content itself and the contextual cues that surround it.

- **Bandwagon Effect**

The bandwagon effect occurs when individuals place disproportionate emphasis on external information while making decisions under conditions of uncertainty (Harris, 2019). This effect, also referred to as herd behavior, subtly shapes user search behavior, particularly through the rapid integration of suggested queries. Users tend to adopt these suggestions more readily when confronted with difficult search tasks or when they do not have much knowledge about the search query, using them as an idea-generation strategy to construct higher-quality queries. Notably, while usage

information may not directly influence selection, the increased reliance on query suggestions underscores the nuanced role of social influence in guiding search behavior without explicitly altering users' selection preferences (Kelly, Cushing, Dostert, Niu, and Gyllstrom, 2010).

- **Exposure Effect**

Exposure effects, closely related to the Bandwagon Effect, occur when repeated exposure to a particular stimulus leads individuals to develop increasingly positive attitudes toward it. (Lau & Coiera, 2007) The frequency and duration of engagement with information reflecting a specific stance or viewpoint can reinforce favorable impressions of that perspective over time. Consequently, when a search engine results page predominantly presents information supporting a single viewpoint, it may influence users to adopt that stance regardless of its accuracy, potentially resulting in biased judgments or flawed decision-making. (Azzopardi, 2021)

- **Ambiguity Effect**

The Ambiguity Effect refers to the tendency for individuals to avoid options with uncertain outcomes, even when those options may offer favorable results. In the context of information search, this bias often manifests as a preference for result items from familiar, trusted sources perceived as reliable, while users are less likely to engage with content from unfamiliar or ambiguous sources. This behavior reflects a cognitive inclination to minimize perceived risk and uncertainty during decision-making processes (Kazai, Craswell, Yilmaz, & Tahaghoghi, 2012).

- **Less is more Effects**

In various everyday contexts, research has shown that presenting individuals with too many options can lead to decision paralysis, reduced decision quality, and lower satisfaction—a phenomenon known as the paradox of choice. If this effect extends to search engine use, it suggests that increasing recall by returning a larger set of results may inadvertently reduce user satisfaction, as users may feel overwhelmed by the volume of choices and struggle to identify the most relevant or appropriate information. (Oulasvirta, Hukkinen, & Schwartz, 2009)

- **Priming Effect**

Priming effects occur when exposure to a stimulus subconsciously influences an individual's response to subsequent stimuli. In the context of information search, these stimuli often take the form of words or images encountered during a search session. For example, the images or search results presented in response to a query can activate certain mental associations, shaping how users perceive and interpret subsequent information. This cognitive activation may, in some cases, lead to unintended and problematic consequences—such as reinforcing offensive, inappropriate, or socially harmful associations—which can then be internalized or further propagated through continued interaction with biased or suggestive content. (Azzopardi, 2021)

- **Order Effect**

Order effects in web search demonstrate that user behavior is strongly influenced by the position of results on a search engine results page. Wu, Jiang, and Zhang (2012) show that clicks follow the serial position effect, with users favoring higher-placed results regardless of their actual relevance. Pan et al. (2007) attribute this to position bias, arguing that users adopt a “fast and frugal heuristic” by trusting top-ranked items, as search engines typically rank the most relevant results first. This trust, they suggest, is learned through repeated interactions and is not irrational. However, Joachims et al. (2005)

identify trust bias and quality bias, where users click more on higher-ranked links even if less relevant, and base decisions partly on position rather than content.

- **Peak End Rule**

The Peak-End Rule bias significantly influences user satisfaction during the search process. As users exert more effort to complete a search task, their satisfaction decreases (Al-Maskari & Sanderson, 2010). Similarly, Kokubu et al. (2005) found that satisfaction diminishes as users examine more results down the rank to find relevant information. Liu and Han (2020) further revealed that user satisfaction is strongly linked to relative gains, losses, and key reference points, with peak and end moments having the greatest impact. The Peak-End Rule suggests that users' evaluations of their search experience are shaped extremely by intense moments (peaks) and the final moments (end), rather than by the overall experience.

4 Strategies for Mitigating Cognitive Biases in Information Behavior

Cognitive biases, deeply ingrained in human thinking, influence how we process, interpret, and act upon information, shaping our decisions and behaviors in ways that are often subtle yet significant. These biases, which have evolved over millennia, are both structural and functional, stemming from neural mechanisms and evolutionary pressures that have historically served adaptive purposes (Korteling & Duistermaat, 2018). However, given their systemic and persistent nature, biases feel natural and self-evident, making them difficult to mitigate through simple educational or training interventions (Korteling, Gerritsma, & Toet, 2021). This inherent limitation calls into question the effectiveness of traditional bias-mitigation strategies, particularly when aimed at long-term or broad decision-making improvements.

Rather than attempting to eliminate these biases, it may be more productive to acknowledge their evolutionary role and adapt strategies that leverage them effectively. While cognitive biases can be detrimental in certain contexts, they are not inherently harmful; rather, they are tools that, when understood and managed correctly, can be beneficial in specific situations (Benson & Manoogian, 2016). Thus, a more realistic approach may involve recognizing that biases are intrinsic to human cognition, and an informed, strategic use of them can lead to more efficient and adaptive decision-making in various contexts. Several approaches can be adopted to counteract the negative influence of cognitive biases in information behavior. These include:

- i. **Awareness:** Developing an awareness of cognitive biases and their influence on decision-making, and using this knowledge to make more informed and objective choices.
- ii. **Critical Information Practices:** using diverse information sources, nurturing critical thinking, and developing a habit of evaluating information with skepticism to counter bias in information selection and interpretation.
- iii. **Search Engine Design Improvements:** Designing search engine results pages that are more neutral and balanced, minimizing the risk of reinforcing biases through skewed or unrepresentative search results.

5 Conclusion

Cognitive bias exerts a profound influence on information behavior, shaping how individuals search for, evaluate, and use information in decision-making. Biases such as confirmation bias, anchoring

bias, availability heuristic, framing bias, and the ambiguity effect often lead individuals to selectively attend to familiar or belief-confirming information while avoiding sources perceived as uncertain or unfamiliar—even when such sources may be valuable. These tendencies are further intensified in digital environments through algorithmic personalization, which curates content based on past user behavior, reinforcing pre-existing beliefs and preferences. Concepts such as the filter bubble and echo chamber underscore how users are increasingly exposed to homogeneous viewpoints, limiting cognitive diversity and entrenching biased perspectives.

Additionally, other biases compound these effects. The exposure effect and Bandwagon Effect cause users to develop more favorable attitudes toward frequently encountered or widely endorsed content, regardless of its accuracy. The less-is-more effect points that too many options can overwhelm users, reducing decision quality and satisfaction—particularly relevant in search environments with high recall. Priming and order effects further influence how users perceive and evaluate information based on its initial framing or its position within a list of results, rather than its intrinsic merit. Finally, the peak-end rule indicates that users often judge the overall quality of an information experience based on its most intense moment and how it ends, rather than on an overall assessment.

Collectively, these cognitive biases highlight the complexity of digital information behavior and may often undermine the accuracy and objectivity of decisions. Recognizing their influence in information behavior is vital for enhancing information behaviour and improving decision quality. Doing so requires a multifaceted approach—creating user awareness, promoting critical information practices, and designing more transparent and diverse information systems that actively counteract personalization and echo chamber effects. Such measures can aid in supporting more balanced and informed decision-making in both personal and societal contexts.

References:

- Alamir Novin and Eric Meyers. 2017. Making Sense of Conflicting Science Information: Exploring bias in the search engine result page. In Proceedings of the 2017 conference on conference human information interaction and retrieval. 175–184. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3020165.3020185>
- Al-Maskari, A., & Sanderson, M. (2010). A review of factors influencing user satisfaction in information retrieval. *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*, 61(5), 859-868.
- Azzopardi, L. (2021, March). Cognitive biases in search: a review and reflection of cognitive biases in Information Retrieval. In *Proceedings of the 2021 conference on human information interaction and retrieval* (pp. 27-37).
- Barnes Jr, J. H. (1984). Cognitive biases and their impact on strategic planning. *Strategic Management Journal*, 5(2), 129-137.
- Benson, B., & Manoogian, J. (2016). Cognitive bias cheat sheet: Because thinking is hard. *Better Humans*, 1.
- Berthet, V. (2022). The impact of cognitive biases on professionals' decision-making: A review of four occupational areas. *Frontiers in psychology*, 12, 802439.

- Blumenthal-Barby, J. S., & Krieger, H. (2015). Cognitive biases and heuristics in medical decision making: a critical review using a systematic search strategy. *Medical decision making*, 35(4), 539-557.
- Chatterjee, A. (2017). Chapter C - Information Users in Elements of Information Organization and Dissemination. Chandos Publishing. pp 47-71, ISBN 9780081020258, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102025-8.00003-X>.
- Dale, S. (2015). Heuristics and biases: The science of decision-making. *Business Information Review*, 32(2), 93-99.
- Deborah Frisch and Jonathan Baron. 1988. Ambiguity and rationality. *Journal of Behavioral Decision Making* 1, 3 (1988), 149–157. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bdm.3960010303>
- Digital around the world (2025, April). <https://datareportal.com/global-digital-overview>.
- Dixon, S. J. (2025, January 23). *Media usage in an online minute 2024*. <https://www.statista.com/statistics/195140/new-user-generated-content-uploaded-by-users-per-minute/>
- Ekström, A. G., Madison, G., Olsson, E. J., & Tsapos, M. (2024). The search query filter bubble: Effect of user ideology on political leaning of search results through query selection. *Information, Communication & Society*, 27(5), 878–894. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2023.2230242>
- Eldridge, S. (2023, March 10). *Cognitive bias | Description & Examples*. Encyclopedia Britannica. <https://www.britannica.com/science/cognitive-bias>
- Fishkin, R. (2024, December 4). *New Research: We analyzed 332 million queries over 21 months to uncover never-before-published data on how people use Google*. <https://sparktoro.com/blog/new-research-we-analyzed-332-million-queries-over-21-months-to-uncover-never-before-published-data-on-how-people-use-google/>
- Framing effect (psychology). (n.d.). EBSCO Information Services. <https://www.ebsco.com/research-starters/social-sciences-and-humanities/framing-effect-psychology>
- Framing effect. (n.d.). Newristics. <https://newristics.com/heuristics-biases/framing-effect>
- Gilovich, T., Griffin, D., & Kahneman, D. (Eds.). (2002). *Heuristics and biases: The psychology of intuitive judgment*. Cambridge university press.
- Harris, C. G. (2019, June). Detecting cognitive bias in a relevance assessment task using an eye tracker. In *Proceedings of the 11th ACM Symposium on Eye Tracking Research & Applications* (pp. 1-5).
- Jain, G. (2025, January 28). *Jaw-Dropping Google Search Statistics and Facts (2025)*. MageComp Blog. <https://magecomp.com/blog/google-search-statistics-and-facts/>
- Joachims, T., Granka, L., Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., & Gay, G. (2017, August). Accurately interpreting clickthrough data as implicit feedback. In *Acm Sigir Forum* (Vol. 51, No. 1, pp. 4-11). New York, NY, USA: ACM.
- Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow*. Allen Lane and Penguin Books, New York.

- Kahneman, D., & Tversky, A. (1982). On the study of statistical intuitions. *Cognition*, 11(2), 123-141.
- Kazai, G., Craswell, N., Yilmaz, E., & Tahaghoghi, S. M. (2012, October). An analysis of systematic judging errors in information retrieval. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management* (pp. 105-114).
- Kelly, D., Cushing, A., Dostert, M., Niu, X., & Gyllstrom, K. (2010, April). Effects of popularity and quality on the usage of query suggestions during information search. In *Proceedings of the SIGCHI conference on human factors in computing systems* (pp. 45-54).
- Knobloch-Westerwick, S., Mothes, C., Johnson, B. K., Westerwick, A., & Donsbach, W. (2015). Political online information searching in Germany and the United States: Confirmation bias, source credibility, and attitude impacts. *Journal of Communication*, 65(3), 489–511. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12154>
- Kokubu, T., Sakai, T., Saito, Y., Tsutsui, H., Manabe, T., Koyama, M., & Fujii, H. (2005, December). The Relationship between Answer Ranking and User Satisfaction in a Question Answering System. In *NTCIR*.
- Korteling, J. E., Gerritsma, J., and Toet, A. (2021). Retention and transfer of cognitive bias mitigation interventions: a systematic literature study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 629354. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2021.629354
- Korteling, J. E., Paradies, G. L., & Sassen-van Meer, J. P. (2023). Cognitive bias and how to improve sustainable decision making. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1129835.
- Korteling, J.E., and Duistermaat, M. (2018). Psychological Deception. Report TNO R11532. Soesterberg: TNO Defence, Safety and Security.
- Kumar, S., & Goyal, N. (2015). Behavioural biases in investment decision making—a systematic literature review. *Qualitative Research in financial markets*, 7(1), 88-108.
- Lau, A. Y., & Coiera, E. W. (2007). Do people experience cognitive biases while searching for information?. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 14(5), 599-608.
- Liu, J., & Han, F. (2020, July). Investigating reference dependence effects on user search interaction and satisfaction: A behavioral economics perspective. In *Proceedings of the 43rd international ACM SIGIR conference on research and development in information retrieval* (pp. 1141-1150).
- Oulasvirta, A., Hukkinen, J. P., & Schwartz, B. (2009, July). When more is less: the paradox of choice in search engine use. In *Proceedings of the 32nd international ACM SIGIR conference on Research and development in information retrieval* (pp. 516-523).
- Pan, B., Hembrooke, H., Joachims, T., Lorigo, L., Gay, G., & Granka, L. (2007). In Google we trust: Users' decisions on rank, position, and relevance. *Journal of computer-mediated communication*, 12(3), 801-823.
- Peer, E., & Gamliel, E. (2013). Heuristics and biases in judicial decisions. *Ct. Rev.*, 49, 114.
- Phillips-Wren, G., Power, D. J., & Mora, M. (2019). Cognitive bias, decision styles, and risk attitudes in decision making and DSS. *Journal of Decision Systems*, 28(2), 63-66.
- Raymond S. Nickerson. 1998. Confirmation bias: A ubiquitous phenomenon in many guises. *Review of General Psychology* 2, 2 (1998), 175–220. <https://doi.org/10.1037/1089-2680.2.2.175>

- Robertson, R. E., Lazer, D., & Wilson, C. (2018). Auditing the personalization and composition of politically-related search engine results pages. *Proceedings of the 2018 World Wide Web Conference*, 955–965. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3178876.3186143>
- Röttger, P., Hofmann, V., Pyatkin, V., Hinck, M., Kirk, H. R., Schütze, H., & Hovy, D. (2024). Political compass or spinning arrow? Towards more meaningful evaluations for values and opinions in large language models (arXiv:2402.16786). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2402.16786>
- Shad, R., Olukemi, A., & Potter, K. (2024). The Impact of Cognitive Biases on Consumer Decision-Making. *Journal of Consumer Behaviour*.
- The Decision Lab. (n.d.). Why do we compare everything to the first piece of information we received?. <https://thedecisionlab.com/biases/anchoring-bias>
- The Decision Lab. (n.d.). Why do we forget information that we just looked up?. <https://thedecisionlab.com/biases/google-effect>
- The Think with Google Editorial Team. (2024, november). *How well do you know Google Search?*. <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/marketing-strategies/search/google-search-innovations/>
- Tober, M. (2022, October 25). *Zero-Clicks study*. Semrush Blog. <https://www.semrush.com/blog/zero-clicks-study/>
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1973). Availability: A heuristic for judging frequency and probability. *Cognitive psychology*, 5(2), 207-232.
- Tversky, A., & Kahneman, D. (1974). Judgment under Uncertainty: Heuristics and Biases: Biases in judgments reveal some heuristics of thinking under uncertainty. *science*, 185(4157), 1124-1131.
- Wilke, A., & Mata, R. (2012). Cognitive bias. *Encyclopedia of Human Behavior (Second Edition)*. Academic Press. pp. 531-535, ISBN 9780080961804, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-375000-6.00094-X>.
- Wilson, T. D. (2000). Human information behavior. *Informing science*, 3, 49.
- Wu, M., Jiang, S., & Zhang, Y. (2012, October). Serial position effects of clicking behavior on result pages returned by search engines. In *Proceedings of the 21st ACM international conference on Information and knowledge management* (pp. 2411-2414).

Impact of Research Publications of Bhatnagar Awardees in Biological Sciences (2011-20): An Evaluation through Traditional Vis-À-Vis Alternative Metrics

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Abstract: *This study evaluates the research publications of Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar (SSB) awardees in biological sciences through a multidimensional analysis of publication metrics. Using bibliometric data from Scopus, Mendeley, and Altmetrics platforms, 1,054 publications across 18 laureates spanning 2011–2020 have been analysed to assess productivity (article counts), academic influence (citations, readership), and societal engagement (Altmetric Attention Scores). This study reveals that publication productivity does not consistently correlate with long-term impact, Mendeley readership strongly aligns with citation counts, and altmetric attention shows significant variability independent of traditional metrics, highlighting the complex nature of research evaluation in biological sciences.*

Keywords: Bhatnagar awardees, Research Impact Assessment, Bibliometrics, Altmetrics, Citation Analysis, Mendeley Readership, Scientific Productivity, Biological Sciences.

1 Introduction

Biological science, a cornerstone of the natural sciences, is the systematic study of living organisms and their interactions with the environment, encompassing diverse sub-disciplines such as molecular biology, genetics, ecology, and physiology. (Alberts et al., 2022) Research in biological science unravels the complexities of life, from the molecular mechanisms driving cellular processes to the intricate dynamics of ecosystems, thereby advancing medical, agricultural, and environmental innovations. (National Research Council, 2009) The impact of biological research on society has been profound, catalysing breakthroughs such as vaccines, genetic engineering, and biodiversity conservation while also addressing global challenges. (Collins & Varmus, 2015) Evaluating research output in this field helps assess its impact and influence on future researchers and society, leading to

tangible real-world contributions. (Bornmann et al., 2012)

To comprehensively evaluate the research output of a given subject area, it is essential to prioritize scholarly articles and publications that have demonstrated significant influence within the field. This influence can be measured through high citation counts, publication in high-impact journals, or the inclusion of works by distinguished authors whose contributions have been widely recognized (Bornmann et al., 2012). Established researchers often achieve prominence through groundbreaking discoveries, sustained academic impact, or prestigious accolades such as Nobel Prizes, Lasker Awards, or other discipline-specific honours, which further validate the credibility of their work (Bjørk, 2020). By focusing on such high-impact publications—those occupying the upper tiers of academic influence researchers can ensure a robust and representative analysis of the field's intellectual progress (Hicks et al., 2015). A systematic examination of top-tier research outputs not only enhances the rigor of academic evaluation but also helps identify key trends, knowledge gaps, and future directions within the discipline (National Research Council, 2009).

For this study, the research output of Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar (SSB) Prize awardees in Biological Sciences has been selected for evaluation, as their contributions represent the pinnacle of scientific excellence in India. Instituted in 1958 by the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), the SSB Prize is India's most prestigious scientific honour, named after Dr. Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar, the founder director of CSIR. The prize is conferred annually for exceptional research and outstanding contributions to science and technology, spanning seven disciplines, including Biological Sciences.

In the domain of Biological Sciences, Bhatnagar laureates have made transformative discoveries, significantly shaping both national and global research landscapes. By analysing the works of these distinguished scientists, this study not only tracks the development of advanced biological research in India but also underscores the role of elite recognition systems in identifying and validating groundbreaking contributions to science.

This study employs a dual methodological approach, integrating traditional bibliometric metrics and altmetric measures to comprehensively evaluate the research publications of Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. Traditional metrics quantify academic influence, revealing patterns in scholarly impact through citation analysis and journal prestige. Complementing these, altmetrics track non-traditional indicators such as online attention, policy citations, and patent references providing insights into the broader societal engagement and real-world dissemination of their work.

2 Objectives of the Study

This study aims to conduct a comprehensive evaluation of the research output of Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. The specific objectives are:

- i. To examine year-wise publication trends, citation patterns, and social visibility metrics to identify temporal variations in research productivity and impact in biological sciences.
- ii. To assess the research impact of each awardee by employing both traditional indicators and alternative metrics (altmetrics) that capture broader societal engagement in biological sciences.
- iii. To perform a detailed analysis of altmetric components to evaluate their societal influence.
- iv. To investigate whether the impact factor of journals correlates with the publication frequency of the awardees, thereby exploring the influence of journal prestige on research output.

3 Scope

This study evaluates the scholarly impact of Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences, focusing exclusively on researchers awarded between 2011-2020. The analysis is restricted to 1,054 Scopus-indexed articles published by the 18 selected awardees during this decade. To maintain analytical focus on high-impact research, only the 100 most-cited articles per awardee (where applicable) were included in the evaluation.

4 Methodology

This study employs a dual-metric analytical approach, combining traditional bibliometric indicators and alternative metrics (altmetrics) to comprehensively evaluate the research impact of research publications by Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. The analysis focuses on journal articles and review papers published by these distinguished researchers, awarded between 2011 and 2020, with all data systematically retrieved from the Scopus database in January 2025.

The research methodology followed a rigorous multi-stage process. First, Scopus author profiles of each awardee were identified, from which all articles and review articles published in a journal through 2024 were extracted using Scopus's advanced filtering system. To ensure analytical focus on high-impact research, a maximum of 100 most-cited articles were selected for each prolific author (those with >100 publications), yielding a final dataset of 1,054 articles published by the 18 awardees. For each article, traditional citation metrics from Scopus alongside altmetric indicators including Mendeley reader counts, Altmetric Attention Scores (AAS), and detailed social media mentions across multiple platforms were retrieved using the Altmetric bookmarklet tool and the altmetric.org details page, which provides granular data on social media mentions and their contribution to the overall AAS.

To assess the relationship between journal prestige and publication frequency, the top 10 journals with the highest number of publications in the dataset were identified. Their Impact Factors (IF) were sourced from official journal websites and analysed to determine whether IF correlates with the volume of publications by awardees.

Throughout the study, all references and citations adhere to the American Psychological Association (APA) 6th edition style guidelines to maintain academic rigor and consistency in documentation.

5 Data Analysis

Scopus citations measure academic influence by tracking how often research is cited in scholarly literature. Mendeley readership reflects early researcher engagement and often precedes future citations. The Altmetric Attention Score (AAS) assesses broader societal impact by monitoring mentions in news, social media, policy documents, and patents, extending beyond traditional academic recognition.

Figure 1: Temporal Analysis of Research Productivity and Impact Metrics in Biological Sciences

Figure 1 presents aggregated data on the total Scopus citations, Mendeley readers, and AAS per article for each year range. Due to significant inconsistencies in the raw values, the figure displays averaged values relative to the total number of articles published in the respective year ranges. It reveals clear trends in publication output and research influence across five-year intervals. The 2015-2019 period marks the highest productivity with 272 publications, while the most recent phase (2020-2024) follows with 194 articles. Earlier periods demonstrate a steady decrease in output. In terms of Scopus citations, the 2005-2009 interval has the strongest impact, averaging 136.82 citations, trailed by 2000-2004 with 86.57. Conversely, the latest period (2020-2024) records the lowest average citations at 18.97. A similar pattern emerges in Mendeley readership, where 2005-2009 leads with 122.64 average readers, and 2015-2019 follows with 88.46, while recent works attract fewer readers. Notably, Altmetric attention scores peak in the 2020-2024 period, averaging 16.54, before dropping significantly in earlier years and disappearing entirely for works from 1994 and before.

Table 1: Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Alternative Metrics in Assessing Research Impact among Bhatnagar Awardees in Biological Sciences

Sl. No.	Author name (awarded in year)	Total Number of articles	Total Scopus citations	Total Mendeley readers	Total AAS
1	Dr. Subhadeep Chatterjee (2020)	34	1610	2191	131
2	Dr. Vatsala Thirumalai (2020)	26	972	1585	255

Sl. No.	Author name (awarded in year)	Total Number of articles	Total Scopus citations	Total Mendeley readers	Total AAS
3	Dr. Soumen Basak (2019)	40	1778	2349	179
4	Dr. Kayarat Saikrishnan (2019)	19	422	666	56
5	Dr. Ganesh Nagaraju (2018)	33	1381	1894	96
6	Dr. Thomas Pucadyil (2018)	57	3390	3722	391
7	Dr. Deepak Thankappan Nair (2017)	50	1881	1863	404
8	Dr. Sanjeev Das (2017)	27	1050	1090	53
9	Dr. Rishikesh Narayanan (2016)	57	1528	2547	233
10	Dr. Suvendra Nath Bhattacharyya (2016)	41	9778	8761	450
11	Dr. Balasubramanian Gopal (2015)	88	1319	2213	206
12	Dr. Rajeev Kumar Varshney (2015)	100	29362	29587	3726
13	Dr. Roop Mallik (2014)	57	2816	3014	322
14	Dr. Sathees Chukkurumbal Raghavan (2013)	100	5787	6155	313
15	Dr. Shantanu Chowdhury (2012)	61	2795	3738	213
16	Dr. Suman Kumar Dhar (2012)	71	2772	2738	193
17	Dr. Amit Prakash Sharma (2011)	93	3086	4558	1271
18	Dr. Rajan Sankaranarayanan (2011)	100	3024	3383	332
Total		1054	74751	82054	8824

Table 1 presents the publication records and impact measures (Scopus citations, Mendeley readership, and Altmetric Attention Scores) for 18 Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences. Collectively, these awardees have published 1,054 articles accumulating 74,751 citations and 82,054 Mendeley readers, with a combined Altmetric Attention Score of 8,824. The data reveals considerable variation in publication output, ranging from 19 to 100 articles per researcher. Dr. Rajeev Kumar Varshney emerges as the top performer across all metrics, leading in total publications (100 articles), Scopus citations (29,362), Mendeley readership (29,587), and AAS (3,726). Following closely, Dr. Suvendra Nath Bhattacharyya demonstrates strong academic impact with the second-highest citations (9,778) and readership (8,761), though with comparatively lower AAS (450) despite having fewer

publications (41 articles). Notably, Dr. Sathees Chukkurumbal Raghavan shares the highest publication count (100 articles) but shows moderate citation (5,787) and readership numbers (6,155), along with relatively low AAS (313). An interesting pattern appears when comparing Dr. Amit Prakash Sharma (93 publications, 3,086 citations, 4,558 readers, 1,271 AAS) and Dr. Thomas Pucadyil (57 publications, 3,390 citations, 3,722 readers, 391 AAS), where similar citation counts accompany markedly different AAS values. The AAS metric displays particularly wide variability, ranging from as low as 53 to as high as 3,726.

Table 2: Altmetric Components and their Societal Influence in Biological Sciences Research

Components	Total number of attentions in biological sciences	Percentage
Twitter/X	6848	79.44
Patent	477	5.53
Wikipedia	372	4.32
News	343	3.98
Facebook	301	3.49
Blog	94	1.09
Policy document	57	0.66
Research highlight platform	48	0.56
Google+ users	37	0.43
YouTube	16	0.19
Peer reviews	13	0.15
Reddit	12	0.14
Q&A forums	2	0.02

The Altmetric Attention Score (AAS) is calculated by tracking mentions across various online platforms, where each component contributes differently based on predefined weightings assigned by Altmetric. For every mention in a platform, a predetermined score is assigned according to Altmetrics weighting system, and the sum of all these individual platform scores constitutes the final AAS. Table 2 presents the distribution of total number mentions across 13 tracked platforms for 1,054 publications by 18 Bhatnagar Awardees in biological sciences. Twitter emerges as the overwhelmingly dominant platform, accounting for 6,848 mentions (79.44% of total attention). Other significant components include patent citations (477 mentions, 5.53%), Wikipedia (372 mentions, 4.32%), and news outlets (343 mentions, 3.98%). In contrast, several platforms show minimal engagement, with YouTube (16 mentions, 0.19%), peer reviews (13 mentions, 0.15%), Reddit (12 mentions, 0.14%), and Q&A forums (2 mentions, 0.02%) representing the least active components.

The impact factor (IF) has long served as a key metric of journal prestige, influencing academic reputation and career advancement. This study analyses the publication distribution of top biological sciences researchers across journals, exploring the relationship between journal impact factor and publication frequency to understand current trends in elite research dissemination.

Table 3: Analysis of Journal Publication Patterns and Impact Factor Influence in Biological Sciences Research

Sl. No.	Top 10 journals by publication frequency	Total number of articles	Impact Factor in 2023
1	Journal Of Biological Chemistry	46	4
2	Nucleic Acids Research	46	16.7
3	Scientific Reports	29	3.8
4	Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America	25	9.4
5	Acta Crystallographica Section D Biological Crystallography	22	2.6
6	Biochemistry	21	2.9
7	Journal Of Molecular Biology	21	4.7
8	Plos One	21	2.9
9	FEBS Journal	17	5.5
10	Acta Crystallographica Section F Structural Biology and Crystallization Communication	15	1.1

The top 10 journals where the highest number of articles by Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences were published are listed in Table 3. The Journal of Biological Chemistry and Nucleic Acids Research were found to have the highest number of publications, with 46 articles each, despite their significantly different Impact Factors (4 and 16.7, respectively). Scientific Reports and Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America (PNAS) were observed to have the second-highest number of publications, with 29 and 25 articles, respectively, though their Impact Factors (3.8 and 9.4) differed considerably. The next four journals Acta Crystallographica Section D Biological Crystallography, Biochemistry, Journal of Molecular Biology, and Plos One were noted to have a similar number of publications (ranging from 22 to 21 articles), with relatively close Impact Factors (2.6, 2.9, 4.7, and 2.9, respectively). The lowest number of publications among the top 10 journals were recorded in FEBS Journal (17 articles, Impact Factor 5.5) and Acta Crystallographica Section F Structural Biology and Crystallization Communications (15 articles, Impact Factor 1.1).

6 Findings

- I. The data in Figure 1 shows that in recent years, the number of publications has been higher compared to earlier years among the Bhatnagar Awardees in Biological Sciences. This suggests that research output has increased over time within this group. When examining citation and

readership patterns, Scopus and Mendeley show similar trends—articles with higher average readership on Mendeley also tend to have higher average citations. This indicates that readership could be a useful predictor of future citations, as articles that attract more readers are likely to accumulate more citations over time.

However, there is a notable difference when looking at Altmetric Attention Score (AAS). Unlike citations and Mendeley readership, which grow steadily over time, the AAS drops sharply for older articles. At the same time, newer articles tend to have higher AAS values. This reinforces the idea that AAS is more relevant as a short-term impact metric, reflecting changes in how research is shared and recognized. The trend suggests that modern research dissemination practices may prioritize quick visibility and online engagement over the slower, citation-based measures of long-term impact.

- II. The table 1 shows that the publication quantity (ranging from 19 to 100 articles per researcher) does not consistently correlate with academic impact, as some authors with moderate publication numbers achieved higher citation counts than those with more publications.

Mendeley readership (82,054 total) consistently parallels Scopus citation patterns (74,751 total) across all researchers, regardless of their publication volume. This close alignment suggests these metrics provide complementary measures of scholarly impact. Notably, Mendeley readership exceeds total citations by approximately 9.8%, indicating broader early-stage engagement than formal citation counts capture.

The Altmetric Attention Scores (total 8,824) demonstrate markedly different behaviour, being significantly lower than both citation and readership metrics. These scores fluctuate independently of traditional impact measures, with values ranging widely from 53 to 3,726 regardless of publication numbers or citation counts. This pattern shows unlike citation-based metrics, AAS solely indicates how widely research is shared and discussed in public forums and social media which are tracked by altmetrics.

- III. The data reveal a striking dominance of Twitter in research dissemination, comprising 79.44% (6,848 mentions) of all altmetric attention. While Facebook (3.49%), Wikipedia (4.32%), and news outlets (3.98%) show moderate engagement.

The overwhelming focus on social media engagement (especially Twitter) in altmetric scores suggests these metrics capture public visibility more effectively than academic recognition. This pattern likely occurs because: traditional academic platforms like peer reviews and research highlights are either less visible to the public or less actively discussed online; researchers may still prefer conventional academic channels over social media for sharing their work; and/or these scholarly platforms simply receive less public attention compared to mainstream social media. While Altmetric can technically track all these platforms, the low engagement in traditional academic platforms peer reviews (0.15%), research highlights (0.56%), and Q&A forums (0.02%) collectively account for less than 1% of total mentions, indicates either limited public interest in these formats or researchers' continued reliance on traditional dissemination methods. This reveals an important limitation of AAS it measures what is popular in online public discourse rather than comprehensive academic impact.

- IV. Based on the data presented in Table 3, it is observed that the selection of journals for publishing articles by Bhatnagar awardees in Biological Sciences is not solely determined by the Impact

Factor (IF) of the journals. Instead, other factors—such as the scope of the journal, target audience, or relevance to the discipline—appear to be prioritized by researchers when choosing publication venues.

7 Conclusion

This study comprehensively evaluates the research impact of Bhatnagar awardees in biological sciences, integrating traditional bibliometrics (citations, Mendeley readership) and altmetrics (AAS, social media, patents, policy citations) to reveal key patterns in scientific influence. The findings demonstrate that while citations reflect long-term academic impact, AAS captures short-term visibility, and Mendeley readership strongly correlates with scholarly recognition. Notably, peak publication output in recent years contrasts with the sustained influence of earlier research, highlighting that productivity alone does not guarantee long-term impact. Social media, particularly Twitter, dominates research dissemination, whereas patent and policy citations underscore significant societal and industrial engagement. The study also reveals that journal selection is influenced by disciplinary relevance and accessibility rather than impact factor alone. These insights advocate for a balanced, multidimensional framework for research assessment—one that values academic, societal, and economic impact. Future research should explore longitudinal altmetric trends and industry engagement to refine impact evaluation in biological sciences.

References:

- Alberts, B. et al. (2015). *Molecular Biology of the Cell* (7th ed.). New York, W. W. Norton & Company.
- Altmetric. (2024, December 3). The donut and Altmetric Attention Score - Altmetric. Retrieved from <https://www.altmetric.com/about-us/our-data/donut-and-altmetric-attention-score/>
- Bjørk, R. (2020). The journals in physics that publish Nobel Prize research. *Scientometrics*, 122(2), 817-823. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11192-019-03312-8>
- Bornmann, L., de Moya-Anegón, F., & Leydesdorff, L. (2012). The new excellence indicator in the World Report of the SCImago Institutions Rankings 2011. *Journal of Informetrics*, 6(2), 333–335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2011.11.006>
- Collins, F. S., & Varmus, H. (2015). A new initiative on precision medicine. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 372(9), 793–795. <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMp1500523>
- Council of Scientific & Industrial Research. (n.d.). Regulations governing the award of the Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for Science and Technology. Retrieved from https://csirhrdg.res.in/SiteContent/ManagedContent/ContentFiles/20220109211426327Proforma_pdf_2022.pdf
- Hicks, D. et al. (2015). Bibliometrics: The Leiden Manifesto for research metrics. *Nature*, 520(7548), 429–431. <https://doi.org/10.1038/520429a>
- National Research Council. (2009). *A new biology for the 21st century*. Washington, National Academies Press.

Press Information Bureau (PIB). (2021). JNCASR Scientist wins Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for ground-breaking discoveries for treatment of Alzheimer's and lung cancer. Retrieved from <https://www.pib.gov.in/PressReleasePage.aspx?PRID=1760791>

Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for Science and Technology. Council of Scientific & Industrial Research. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.csir.res.in/en/award/shanti-swarup-bhatnagar-prize-science-and-technology>

Wikipedia contributors. (2025, April 13). Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize for Science and Technology. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shanti_Swarup_Bhatnagar_Prize_for_Science_and_Technology

Wikipedia contributors. (2025, June 6). List of Shanti Swarup Bhatnagar Prize recipients. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_Shanti_Swarup_Bhatnagar_Prize_recipients

Geospatial Scholarship in India: Bibliometric Trends and Impact of GIS and Remote Sensing Research (2000–2024)

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Abstract: This study conducts a bibliometric analysis of research output on Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) using data retrieved from the Scopus database. Bibliometric techniques, including co-citation analysis, scientific collaboration mapping, co-word analysis, and network visualization, were applied through Biblioshiny and VOSviewer. A total of 9,118 papers published between 2000 and 2024 were analyzed, revealing steady annual growth. India leads globally with 8,594 publications, 133,709 citations, and a total link strength of 694, followed by the United States with 160 publications and 6,270 citations. Institutionally, the Indian Institute of Technology ranks first (337 publications), followed by the Indian Institute of Remote Sensing (240 publications). The Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing leads among journals with 425 publications and 7,750 citations. Kumar A is the most prolific author (176 publications), while Singh S.K. has the highest scholarly impact with 4,158 citations from 108 documents, along with the top h-index (31) and g-index (63). The most frequent keywords include Remote Sensing, GIS, Geographic Information Systems, Satellite Imagery, and Land Use.

Keywords: GIS, RS, Geographic Information System, Remote Sensing, Satellite Image, Earth Observation, ISRO, IIRS, NRSC

1 Introduction

Human civilization has flourished on Earth, a planet rich in biodiversity, evolving physically, intellectually, and technologically over billions of years through curiosity and research. Since India's independence, research across science, technology, medicine, space science, and socio-economic development has accelerated, with Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS)

emerging as transformative fields. GIS is a computer-based system for analyzing, visualizing, and managing geographically referenced data from sources like satellite imagery and GPS. NASA defines GIS as integrating and analyzing geospatial datasets to study Earth's changes, while Burrough (1986) described it as "a powerful set of tools" for spatial data collection, storage, transformation, and display. GIS applications span natural resource planning, environmental management, transportation, telecommunications, and business planning. Remote sensing (RS), which advanced rapidly after World War II, involves obtaining information about Earth's surface without direct contact, using electromagnetic wave properties via satellites or aircraft. George Joseph emphasized its role in resource management, land use, and environmental protection. Together, GIS and RS address challenges in resource management, urban planning, agriculture, disaster mitigation, climate adaptation, and infrastructure growth. In India, institutions like ISRO and IIRS have led their expansion. This study presents a bibliometric analysis of Indian GIS and RS research (2000–2024), highlighting publication trends, impact, and collaborations.

2 Literature Review:

2.1 Geographic Information Systems (GIS)

The threat of the fair use domain contracting is brought about by the production and publication of copyrighted digital content over time. Encouraging legitimate and equitable uses of digital copyrighted works is crucial for users in OA movement. In this setting the main objectives of this study are as follows:

- To outline open access initiatives around the world;
- To state various Digital Rights Management (DRM) technologies;
- To know the areas of activities those violate the owners' interest;
- To find out the possibilities of libraries for supporting OA movements.

3 Review of Literature

Research into GIS has expanded across multiple disciplines, with bibliometric studies highlighting both thematic diversity and increasing scholarly impact. Alcaras et al. (2023) analyzed 5,204 GIS-related manuscripts in ecological research (1979–2021, Scopus), identifying China as the leader in publication volume and the USA in citations. Key terms—remote sensing, spatial analysis, land use—underscore GIS's central role in ecological monitoring. Oncu et al. (2022) examined 1,325 GIS publications from Turkey (1990–2020), revealing traditional focuses like land use and urban planning, alongside emerging themes such as climate change and multi-criteria decision-making. Duarte and Teodoro (2021) explored open-source GIS applications (2010–2020), noting a rise in mobile GIS and integration with IoT and big data. Bielecka (2020) investigated GIS-based land use change modeling, finding the field mature and interdisciplinary, with strong European, Chinese, and U.S. contributions. Earlier, Mohamad et al. (2013) tracked GIS publishing trends (2002–2011), mapping collaboration and authorship patterns. Integration of GIS with **Building Information Modelling (BIM)**, termed GeoBIM, has been studied by Garramone et al. (2020) and Wang et al. (2019), focusing on interoperability, semantic modeling, and asset management. Tian et al. (2008) reported a tripling of global GIS publications between 1997 and 2006, while Xuemei et al. (2014) showcased the use of GIS in bibliometric visualization.

2.2 Remote Sensing (RS)

Remote sensing has evolved as a critical partner to GIS, particularly in environmental monitoring and earth observation. Singh and Arti (2022) examined 9,418 RS publications (2015–2022), highlighting India's growing contributions and identifying prolific authors. Vijayalakshmi and Ambuja (2010) provided an earlier scientometric review (2006–2010), emphasizing the method's utility for tracking RS trends. Applications range from ocean salinity (Zanon et al.) to inland water monitoring (Ogashawara, 2021) and mountainous environments (Jombo et al., 2023). Maddisetty and Babu (2020) analyzed the *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing* (2010–2019), confirming Lotka's law in authorship productivity and revealing strong India–China–Iran collaborations. In public health, Viana et al. (2017) reviewed RS-based disease monitoring, focusing on malaria and dengue. Tikader et al. (2024) examined RS-GIS integration for air pollution mapping in Chhattisgarh, India, while Ju et al. (2024) assessed 37,977 RS publications on mineral exploration. Singh et al. (2023) explored soil moisture estimation using RS and machine learning, noting advances such as NASA–ISRO's NISAR mission.

3 Objectives:

- 3.1 To examine the growth and trends of GIS and RS research (2000–2024).
- 3.2 To analyze document types, top authors, and collaboration patterns.
- 3.3 To evaluate author performance using h-index and g-index metrics.
- 3.4 To identify leading institutions, core journals, and highly cited publications.
- 3.5 To explore international collaboration and emerging research topics.

4 Scope of the Study:

This study draws on the Scopus database to analyze publications on GIS and RS by Indian scientists from 2000 to 2024. Out of 9,118 research outputs, 5,282 were journal articles, followed by conference papers (2,521), book chapters (697), reviews (181), and other formats. The analysis employs bibliometric tools such as VOSviewer and Biblioshiny (RStudio), adhering to the APA 7th edition referencing style.

5 Methodology:

A targeted advanced search in Scopus used keywords including “Geographic Information Science”, “GIS”, “Earth Observation”, “Remote sensing”, and “Satellite image”. Results were restricted to 2000–2024 and to the country “India.” Data retrieval occurred on 16 May 2025. Analytical tools—MS Excel, Biblioshiny, and VOSviewer—were used for processing and visualization, while Zotero and Mendeley managed references.

6 Significance of the Study:

Research output not only advances knowledge but also generates economic and societal benefits. For a resource-constrained yet talent-rich country like India, strategic investment in high-impact areas such as GIS and RS is essential. Bibliometric studies help policymakers and funding agencies evaluate performance, identify research gaps, and prioritize funding for maximum developmental impact. By

mapping publication trends, collaboration networks, and thematic focus, this study offers valuable insights for researchers, institutions, and decision-makers.

7 Data Collection & Analysis

7.1 Year wise Publication Growth:

Figure 1: Bar Graph of Year wise Publication Growth

Between 2000 and 2024, GIS and RS publications rose from 54 to 1,207, with notable growth after 2015, peaking in 2023–2024 due to technology, impactful research, and rising awareness.

7.2 Top 25 Relevant Authors:

Figure 2: Bar Graph of Top 25 Relevant Authors

This overview lists the top 25 prolific GIS and RS authors (2000–2024). Kumar A leads with 176 publications, followed by Kumar S (148) and Singh SK (108). Others exceeding 50 include Singh S (82), Singh A (78), and Kumar P (70). Several, like Kumar D and Singh R, have 49 each, marking notable scholarly contributions.

7.3 Top 25 Authors' Local Impact:

Table 1: Author Impact Analysis Chart

Author	h_Index	g_Index	Total Citation	Total Publications
Singh, SK	31	63	4158	108
Kumar, A	31	55	3684	176
Chowdary, VM	20	34	3037	34
Jha, M K	17	24	2982	24
Nagendra, H	19	21	2891	21
Srivastava, PK	24	52	2781	70
Kumar, S	26	46	2441	148
Chandraseka,r N	16	25	2280	25
Pham, BT	16	21	2101	21
Magesh, NS	15	16	2069	16
Mukherjee, S	20	45	2056	50
Arora, MK	14	27	2035	27
Singh, P	23	44	2027	74
Kumar, R	18	39	1580	69
Bhandari, AK	17	18	1572	18
Singh, S	21	38	1559	82
Singh, GK	17	17	1554	17
Kumar, M	18	38	1531	66
Singh, RP	14	33	1456	33
Chowdhury, A	5	8	1426	8
Das, S	18	37	1412	50
Mal, BC	7	7	1339	7
Prakash, I	13	18	1336	18
Tienbui, D	6	6	1321	6
Ghosh, S	17	36	1320	56

7.3.1 Relevant Authors and Citation Metrics:

The most cited author is **Singh SK** with 4,158 citations from 108 publications. **Kumar A** (3,684 citations) and **Chowdary VM** (3,037 citations) follow, while **Tien Bui D** and **Mal BC** show higher citation impact per publication, with 1,321 citations from 6 papers and 1,339 from 7 papers, respectively. Other highly cited researchers include **Jha MK** (2,982), **Nagendra H** (2,891), and **Srivastava PK** (2,781). Authors with fewer than 2,000 citations include **Kumar R** (1,580) and **Bhandari AK** (1,572).

7.3.2 h-index:

The highest h-index is shared by **Kumar A** and **Singh SK** (31), followed by **Kumar S** (26) and **Srivastava PK** (24). Several others, including **Banerjee B** and **Chandrasekhar N**, hold an h-index of 16.

7.3.3 g-index

Singh SK leads with a g-index of 63, followed by **Kumar A** (55) and **Srivastava PK** (52). **Kumar P**, **Kumar V**, and **Roy PS** each record a g-index of 29.

7.4 Publication Distribution of Top 20 Journals of GIS and RS:

Table 2: Publication Distribution of Top 20 Journals of GIS and RS:

Source	Documents	Citations
Journal of the Indian society of remote sensing	425	7750
Current science	160	3117
International archives of the photogrammetric, remote sensing and spatial information sciences - isprs archives	156	936
Lecture notes in civil engineering	144	262
Geocarto international	134	8826
Geocarto international	131	3212
Journal of the geological society of India	123	2108
Advances in intelligent systems and computing	106	479
Environmental monitoring and assessment	98	2548
Proceedings of spie - the international society for optical engineering	96	280
Arabian journal of geosciences	95	3396
Environmental earth sciences	92	4349
Remote sensing	77	3190
Aip conference proceedings	69	63
International journal of applied engineering research	69	173
Natural hazards	68	2732
International journal of earth sciences and engineering	64	147
Remote sensing applications: society and environment	58	1329
Modeling earth systems and environment	57	2265
Lecture notes in electrical engineering	53	98

In India’s GIS and RS research, the top twenty journals (≥ 50 documents, ≥ 50 citations) demonstrate varying influence (Table 4.6). The *Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing* leads with 425 articles and 7,750 citations, followed by *Current Science* (160 articles, 3,117 citations). *Geocarto International* is most cited (8,826 citations from 134 papers). *Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, with 53 publications and 98 citations, still contributes meaningfully. These metrics guide researchers in selecting impactful journals to enhance research visibility.

7.5 Most Relevant Affiliation:

Figure 3: Bar Graph of Most Relevant Affiliation

GIS and RS research in India has expanded, with many institutions contributing. The top 20 producers include IIT (337 publications), Indian Institute of Remote Sensing (240), and Anna University (209). Others exceeding 100 publications include NIT (199), IIT Bombay (172), IIT Roorkee (165), and BHU (164). Some institutions show smaller yet valuable outputs.

7.6 Top 10 Affiliation’s Production Time year wise:

Figure 4: Line Graph of Top 10 Affiliation’s Production Time

The figure shows a sharp post-2010 rise in GIS and RS research in India, led by NIT and IIRS, driven by rapid technological advancements and their integration into research practices.

7.7 Top 20 Countries and their Publication Impact:

Table 3: Top 20 Countries and their Publication Impact

Country	Documents	Citations	Total link strength
India	8594	133709	694
United States	160	6270	160
Germany	61	2278	61
United Kingdom	56	1274	56
Japan	42	846	42
China	41	914	41
Ethiopia	40	765	40
Italy	34	1300	34
Saudi Arabia	32	423	32
Australia	27	585	27
Iraq	27	48	27
South Korea	26	688	26
Malaysia	25	628	25
Netherlands	25	459	24
Iran	20	312	20
France	19	408	19
Canada	18	270	18
Amp	16	36	16
Sri Lanka	13	201	13
Vietnam	13	154	13

Table shows the top 20 countries in GIS and RS research, based on outputs and citations, filtered by at least 2 countries/document, 5 documents, and 5 citations, from 105 countries, narrowed to 39, then 20.

Figure 5: Country Collaboration Map in the World

India leads GIS and RS research with 8,594 publications and 133,709 citations, followed by the US and Germany, while Sri Lanka and Vietnam rank lowest, showing varied global research contributions.

Figure 6: Line Graph of Top 20 Countries Production year wise

The figure illustrates India’s rapid growth in GIS and RS research, rising from under 500 publications in 2000 to over 1,500 by 2024. Unlike China, France, Germany, and Italy, India’s surge reflects technological advancements and increasing academic interest in these fields.

7.8 Most Relevant Frequent Keywords:

Table 4: Frequency Count Chart of Relevant Keyword

Terms	Frequency
Remote sensing	4638
GIS	1643
Geographic information systems	1623
Satellite imagery	1143
Land use	851
Satellites	684
Satellite images	654
Groundwater	635
Remote-sensing	627
Satellite data	588
Water quality	575
Deep learning	563
Image classification	554
Environmental monitoring	465
Image enhancement	444
Mapping	430

Terms	Frequency
Land cover	415
Landsat	385
Decision making	383
Image analysis	360
Image segmentation	356
Image processing	348
Remote sensing images	343
Water management	322

Keywords in GIS and Remote Sensing

Bibliometric research in GIS and Remote Sensing (RS) employs diverse keywords reflecting core concepts and themes. As shown in Figure the top 24 frequently used terms highlight their prevalence. *Remote Sensing* dominates with 4,638 occurrences, underscoring its central role. *India* ranks second (2,381), indicating strong thematic relevance, followed by *GIS* (1,643) and *Water Management* (322).

7.9 Co-Occurrence Network of Author Keywords:

Using VOSviewer (minimum occurrence: 5), 1,079 of 173,520 author keywords met the threshold, forming 14 clusters from a selection of 1,000 keywords. In this network, bubble size and distance indicate frequency and associative strength. *Remote Sensing* appears most (1,873; link strength: 4,501), followed by *GIS* (1,417; 3,270) and *Deep Learning* (345; 972). These findings reveal both the dominant research areas and the interconnectedness of concepts in bibliometric studies of GIS and RS, emphasizing their influence on scholarly evaluation and the mapping of research landscapes.

Figure 7: Co-Occurrence Network of Author Keywords

7.10 Top 20 Trend Topics:

Table 5: Term and their Frequency Chart w.r.t to Period

Term	Frequency	Year (Q1)	Year (Median)	Year (Q3)
Remote sensing	4638	2013	2019	2022
GIS	1643	2012	2017	2022
Geographic information systems	1623	2013	2018	2022
Satellite imagery	1143	2014	2019	2023
Land use	851	2015	2019	2022
Satellites	684	2015	2018	2022
Satellite images	654	2017	2021	2023
Remote-sensing	627	2022	2023	2024
Water quality	575	2016	2021	2023
Deep learning	562	2022	2023	2024
Image classification	554	2017	2021	2023
Environmental monitoring	465	2017	2022	2023
Image enhancement	444	2018	2022	2023
Landsat	385	2018	2022	2023
Image segmentation	356	2016	2020	2023
Image processing	348	2013	2017	2019
Classification (of information)	312	2017	2020	2023
Machine learning	305	2022	2023	2024
Article	286	2015	2020	2023
Watershed	239	2011	2016	2020

Table highlights top author keywords in GIS and RS research over 24 years, revealing emerging trends. “Remote sensing” dominated with 4,638 occurrences in 2013, 2019, and 2022, followed by “GIS” (1,643) and “Geographic Information System” (1,623). In 2023–2024, new trends included “satellite imagery,” “deep learning,” “water quality,” and “machine learning.”

7.11 Top 10 Global Cited Documents:

Table 6 Papers with Most Citations Globally

Paper	DOI	Total Citations	TC per Year
1.Rajendra P. Sishodia , Ram L. Ray and Sudhir K. Singh , (2020), Applications of Remote	10.3390/rs12193136	806	134.33

Paper	DOI	Total Citations	TC per Year
Sensing in Precision Agriculture: A Review			
2.B.P. Ganasri, H. Ramesh, (2016), Assessment of soil erosion by RUSLE model using remote sensing and GIS - A case study of Nethravathi Basin	10.1016/j.gsf.2015.10.007	688	68.80
3.J.S. Rawat a, Manish Kumar, (2015), Monitoring land use/cover change using remote sensing and GIS techniques: A case study of Hawalbagh block, district Almora, Uttarakhand, India	10.1016/j.ejrs.2015.02.002	641	58.27
4.Magesh N.S, (2012), Delineation of groundwater potential zones in Theni district, Tamil Nadu, using remote sensing, GIS and MIF techniques	10.1016/j.gsf.2011.10.007	594	42.43
5.Pham BT et al. , 2017, Hybrid integration of Multilayer Perceptron Neural Networks and machine learning ensembles for landslide susceptibility assessment at Himalayan area (India) using GIS	10.1016/j.catena.2016.09.007	536	59.56
6.Nagendra H et al. , (2013), Remote sensing for conservation monitoring: Assessing protected areas, habitat extent, habitat condition, species diversity, and threats	10.1016/j.ecolind.2012.09.014	510	39.23
7.Arulbalaji P , D. Padmalal & K. Sreelash, (2019), GIS and AHP Techniques Based Delineation of Groundwater Potential Zones: a case study from Southern Western Ghats, India	10.1038/s41598-019-38567-x	476	68.00
8.Gandhi GM et al. , (2015), Ndvi: Vegetation change detection using remote sensing	10.1016/j.procs.2015.07.415	473	43.00

Paper	DOI	Total Citations	TC per Year
and gis – A case study of Vellore District			
9.Pettorelli N, (2014), Satellite remote sensing for applied ecologists: opportunities and challenges	10.1111/1365-2664.12261	458	38.17
10.Bhandari AK, (2014), Cuckoo search algorithm and wind driven optimization based study of satellite image segmentation for multilevel thresholding using Kapur’s entropy	10.1016/j.eswa.2013.10.059	424	35.33

The bibliographic details of the ten most cited articles in bibliometrics mapping and citation analysis are presented in the table, reflecting their influential role in shaping current research and practices. Leading the list is *Applications of Remote Sensing in Precision Agriculture: A Review* by Rajendra P. Sishodia, Ram L. Ray, and Sudhir K. Singh (2020, DOI: 10.3390/rs12193136), with 806 citations - an annual average of 134.33—demonstrating its sustained scholarly impact. Second is *Assessment of Soil Erosion by RUSLE Model Using Remote Sensing and GIS - A Case Study of Nethravathi Basin* by B.P. Ganasri and H. Ramesh (2016, DOI: 10.1016/j.gsf.2015.10.007), earning 688 citations at 68.80 annually. Third, *Monitoring Land Use/Cover Change Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques: A Case Study of Hawalbagh Block, District Almora, Uttarakhand, India* by J.S. Rawat and Manish Kumar (2015, DOI: 10.1016/j.ejrs.2015.02.002) has 641 citations, averaging 58.27 per year.

10.12 Author Collaboration Network:

The author collaboration network in GIS and RS research identifies 548 active authors from 15,024, with the top 50 visualized in six clusters. The largest cluster includes Bose Arghadeep, Chowdary V.M., Das Biswajit, and others; the second features Avinash Kumar, Deepika B., Garg P.K., among others; and the third comprises Chakraborty Debasis, Dadhwal V.K., Das Rajib, and colleagues. Color-coded links represent collaborative ties, while unconnected authors indicate no recorded joint research in the GIS and RS domain.

Figure 8: Author Collaboration by Bibliographic Coupling

10.13 Institution Collaboration Network:

The institutional collaboration network in GIS and RS research (Figure) maps cooperative links among 72 institutions, filtered from 15,137 based on parameters: a maximum of five institutions per document, at least five documents per institution, and a minimum of five citations. While some institutions are interconnected, others operate independently, forming eleven clusters, with three being dominant.

The **first cluster** links institutions such as Manonmaniam Sundaranar University, NIT, University of Allahabad, University of North Bengal, Jamia Millia Islamia, University of Gour Banga, Anna University, University of Jammu, ICAR–National Bureau of Soil Survey, and others.

The **second cluster** involves IIT departments (Civil Engineering, Earth Sciences), TERI University, Birla Institute of Technology, ICAR–IARI, ISRO, NRSC, and Jawaharlal Nehru University.

The **third cluster** includes the Academy of Scientific and Innovative Research, Anna University, Aligarh Muslim University, Birla Institute of Technology, NRSC Hyderabad, and JNU's School of Environmental Sciences.

Figure 9: Institution Collaboration by Bibliographic coupling

10.14 Countries Collaboration Network:

Figure depicts the GIS and RS countries collaboration network, showing 61 nations (from 130) meeting set criteria. Three major clusters emerge: Cluster 1—Canada, Greece, India, Ireland, South Africa, Switzerland, Turkey, UK; Cluster 2—Austria, France, Netherlands, Singapore, Spain, Sweden; Cluster 3—Brazil, Croatia, Egypt, Italy, Morocco, Poland.

Figure 10: Countries Collaboration by Bibliographic coupling

8 Findings:

A bibliometric analysis of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Remote Sensing (RS) literature (2000–2024) using the Scopus database revealed significant growth patterns and research insights. A total of 9,118 documents were identified, with publications rising from 54 in 2000 to a peak of 1,207 in 2024—representing a 22-fold increase. Kumar A emerged as the most prolific author (176 publications), while Singh SK led in citations (4,158 from 108 publications). The Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing ranked as the most impactful journal, followed by Current Science. The Indian Institute of Technology topped institutional contributions with 337 publications, reflecting a broader trend of growth among Indian institutions. India dominated globally with 8,594 publications, far ahead of the United States (160) and other nations. "Remote sensing" was the most frequent keyword, indicating a strong thematic focus on AI integration in spatial research. The most cited article was Sishodia RP, 2020, Remote Sensing, with 806 citations.

9 Conclusion

This bibliometric study offers a comprehensive overview of the rapid growth, thematic focus, and scholarly influence of GIS and RS research in India between 2000 and 2024. The results confirm India's global leadership in publications, citations, and collaborative networks, with premier institutions such as the Indian Institute of Technology and the Indian Institute of Remote Sensing playing pivotal roles. Prolific scholars like Kumar A and Singh SK have shaped the discipline's academic trajectory, while established journals—especially the Journal of the Indian Society of Remote Sensing—serve as key dissemination channels. Dominant keywords such as Remote sensing, GIS, and Satellite imagery highlight the technologies' alignment with national priorities like natural resource management, environmental monitoring, and urban planning. Overall, the study underscores that India's GIS and RS research is not only expanding in volume but also achieving substantial impact, with strong potential for further advancements through institutional support, technological innovation, and international collaboration.

References:

- Alcaras, E., Amoroso, P. P., Figliomeni, F. G., & Parente, C. (2024). Geographic Information System (GIS) for ecology: a bibliometric network analysis. *Ecological Questions*, 35(1). <https://doi.org/10.12775/EQ.2024.006>
- ALTUNDAL ÖNCÜ, M., ATEŞ, E., FİDAN, S., & YILMAZ, M. (2022). 30 Years of Geographic Information Systems Studies in Turkey: A Bibliometric Analysis (1990-2020). *Türkiye Coğrafi Bilgi Sistemleri Dergisi*, 4(2), 79–86. <https://doi.org/10.56130/tucbis.1178247>
- Bielecka, E. (2020). Gis spatial analysis modeling for land use change. A bibliometric analysis of the intellectual base and trends. In *Geosciences (Switzerland)* (Vol. 10, Issue 11, pp. 1–21). MDPI AG. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences10110421>
- Cascón-Katchadourian, J., Quesada-Román, A., Martínez-Sánchez, M. Á., & Cobo, M. J. (2024). A Bibliometric Analysis of the Past 25 Years at International Journal of Geographical Information Science. *BiD*, 53. <https://doi.org/10.1344/bid2024.53.03>
- Duarte, L., & Teodoro, A. C. (2021). GIS Open-Source Plugins Development: A 10-Year Bibliometric Analysis on Scientific Literature. *Geomatics*, 1(2), 206–245. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geomatics1020013>
- Earth Science Data Systems, N. (2021, May 18). *Remote Sensing | NASA Earthdata* [Data Basics]. Earth Science Data Systems, NASA. <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/earth-observation-data-basics/remote-sensing>
- Earth Science Data Systems, N. (2024, October 10). *About GIS at NASA | NASA Earthdata* [Basic page]. Earth Science Data Systems, NASA. <https://www.earthdata.nasa.gov/learn/gis/about>
- Garramone, M., Moretti, N., Scaioni, M., Ellul, C., Re Cecconi, F., & Dejacco, M. C. (2020). BIM and GIS INTEGRATION for INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET MANAGEMENT: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS. *ISPRS Annals of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, 6(4/W1), 77–84. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-annals-VI-4-W1-2020-77-2020>
- Jombo, S., Abd Elbasit, M. A. M., Gumbo, A. D., & Nethengwe, N. S. (2023). Remote Sensing Application in Mountainous Environments: A Bibliographic Analysis. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(4). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20043538>
- Ju, L., Liu, Y., Liu, S., Xiang, Q., Hu, W., & Yu, P. (2024). Bibliometric analysis of global trends and characteristics of remote sensing for mineral exploration in the early 21st century. In *All Earth* (Vol. 36, Issue 1, pp. 1–17). Taylor and Francis Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1080/27669645.2024.2418730>
- Kundu, R. (2021). *Remote sensing and GIS*. Tapati Publishers.
- Maddisetty, B. (n.d.). *Scientometric Study of Publications of “Journal of Indian Society Scientometric Study of Publications of ‘Journal of Indian Society of Remote Sensing’ of Remote Sensing.”* <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac>
- Mohamad, A. N., Masrek, M. N., & Rasam, A. R. B. A. (2013, March). A bibliometric analysis on scientific production of Geographical Information System (GIS) in Web of Science. In *2013 International Conference of Information and Communication Technology (ICoICT)* (pp. 264–268). IEEE.

- Ogashawara, I. (2021). Bibliometric Analysis of Remote Sensing of Inland Waters Publications from 1985 to 2020. In *Geographies* (Vol. 1, Issue 3, pp. 346–361). Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI). <https://doi.org/10.3390/geographies1030019>
- Pramod, *, Singh, K., Arti, D., & Assistant, S. (n.d.). *Library Waves: A Biannual Peer Reviewed Journal of Library and Information Science Indian Research Output on Remote Sensing Literature Using Scopus Database: A Bibliometric Study (2015-2022)*. www.librarywaves.com
- Singh, A., Gaurav, K., Sonkar, G. K., & Lee, C. C. (2023). Strategies to Measure Soil Moisture Using Traditional Methods, Automated Sensors, Remote Sensing, and Machine Learning Techniques: Review, Bibliometric Analysis, Applications, Research Findings, and Future Directions. *IEEE Access*, 11, 13605–13635. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2023.3243635>
- Tian, Y., Wen, C., & Hong, S. (2008). Global scientific production on GIS research by bibliometric analysis from 1997 to 2006. *Journal of Informetrics*, 2(1), 65–74. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2007.10.001>
- Tikader, M., Mukhopadhyay, D., & Dabhadker, K. (2024). Remote Sensing and GIS in Air Pollution Mitigation: A Bibliometric Review of Chhattisgarh, India. *International Journal of Environment and Climate Change*, 14(4), 174–193. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ijecc/2024/v14i44106>
- Viana, J., Santos, J. V., Neiva, R. M., Souza, J., Duarte, L., Teodoro, A. C., & Freitas, A. (2017). Remote sensing in human health: A 10-year bibliometric analysis. *Remote Sensing*, 9(12). <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs9121225>
- Vijaylakshmi, S., & Ambuja, R. (n.d.). *International Journal of Library and Information Studies REMOTE SENSING LITERATURE IN SCOPUS DATABASE: A BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS*.
- Wang, H., Pan, Y., & Luo, X. (2019). Integration of BIM and GIS in sustainable built environment: A review and bibliometric analysis. In *Automation in Construction* (Vol. 103, pp. 41–52). Elsevier B.V. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.03.005>
- Xuemei, W., Mingguo, M., Xin, L., & Zhiqiang, Z. (2014). Applications and researches of geographic information system technologies in bibliometrics. *Earth Science Informatics*, 7(3), 147–152. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12145-013-0132-4>
- Zanon, F., Cesarano, C., Cotroneo, Y., Fusco, G., Budillon, G., & Aulicino, G. (2022). Remote sensing of sea surface salinity: A bibliometric analysis. *Advances in Oceanography and Limnology*, 13(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.4081/aiol.2022.10862>

Geographical Indications (GI) in India: A State-Wise Comparative Study

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Abstract: *The Geographical Indications (GI) are a form of intellectual property that recognize products as originating from a specific geographical location. India has registered a wide range of GI products, including agricultural goods, handicrafts, manufactured items, and natural products. However, the distribution of GI tags across Indian states has been uneven, with some states leading in registrations while others remain underrepresented. This study aims to conduct a comparative analysis of the state-wise distribution of GI tags in India. By categorizing and comparing GI registrations, the study highlights gaps, and suggests to encourage all stake holders. The findings aim to support to the related people and local communities in leveraging GI protection for inclusive economic growth and cultural preservation.*

Keywords: Geographical Indications (GI), GI Tags in India, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), Regional Identity, Traditional Knowledge, Cultural Heritage Protection

1 Introduction

India is a land of immense cultural, agricultural, and artisanal diversity, reflected vividly through its wide array of region-specific products. From the aromatic Basmati rice of the north to the intricate Kancheepuram silk sarees of the south, each region of India boasts unique goods that are deeply rooted in tradition, geography, and community identity. These goods are more than just goods; they are symbols of pride, history, and local identity. These products, often crafted using traditional knowledge and natural resources specific to their region, are legally protected under the framework of Geographical Indications (GI).

Over the years, hundreds of products from different states have been registered under GI, spanning categories such as agricultural products, handicrafts, manufactured goods, and natural products. However, the distribution of these GI tags is not uniform across Indian states. Some states have taken proactive steps to identify and register local products, while others lag behind due to lack of awareness, institutional support, or policy initiative.

This study aims to undertake a comparative analysis of the state-wise distribution of GI tags in India, exploring the reasons behind the disparity and the types of products registered. It also seeks to identify best practices adopted by leading states and recommend strategies to ensure more balanced and inclusive GI registration across the country.

2 Geographical Indications (GI)

The term "geographic indications of goods" describes a type of economic property that indicates a country or a region within it is the country or place of origin of a certain product. Such a name typically conveys a sense of quality and originality, primarily because it originated in that particular region, country, or geographic place. Articles 1(2) and 10 of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property acknowledge geographic indicators as a component of IPRs (About us, n.d.). The Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) Agreement, which was one of the agreements that concluded the Uruguay Round of GATT negotiations, also covers them in Articles 22 to 24 (Overview: the TRIPS Agreement, n.d.; InsightsIAS, October 23, 2023). In India, GI tags are governed by the Geographical Indications of Goods (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999, which came into effect in 2003 (Geographical Indications, n.d.).

2.1 Purpose of GI Tags:

- Preserve cultural heritage and biodiversity
- Prevent unauthorized use or imitation
- Promote rural and artisanal economies
- Protect the unique identity of traditional products

2.2 Categories of GI-Tagged Products in India:

- Agricultural Products – Basmati Rice, Alphonso Mango, Bhut Jolokia etc.
- Handicrafts – Pashmina Shawls, Madhubani Paintings, Channapatna Toys and so on.
- Manufactured Goods – Banarasi Sarees, Blue Pottery of Jaipur etc.
- Natural Goods – Kashmiri Saffron, Lakadong Turmeric and so on.

2.3 Benefits of GI Tags (<https://ariyalur.nic.in>):

- Boosts employment and rural development
- Encourages traditional knowledge preservation
- Ensures legal protection for producers
- Increases market value and access to global markets

3 Objectives

The main objectives of this study are as follows:

- To analyze the distribution of GI tags across different states in India.
- To categorize GI tags based on product types (Agricultural, Handicraft, Manufactured, and Natural Goods).
- To identify gaps and challenges in the equitable distribution of GI registrations across India.
- To recommend strategies for improving the state-wise distribution and effectiveness of GI registrations.

4 Methodology

The study has followed for capturing data through online survey which includes the websites, reports, journals, web pages, blogs etc. Numerical data are available in the portal of Office of the Controller General of Patents, Design & Trade Marks, Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Government of India. This website includes all GI status i.e. refused, registered, withdrawn, abandoned and pending applications in this regard. All the data have been collected upto the period of July 26, 2024. A total of 605 data have been collected which include GI applications registered upto this period Rudrajyoti, M. (n.d.). The study has considered the goods registered by the States/UTs individually or jointly. Goods details have been collected from the website of Geographical Indications Registry (<https://search.ipindia.gov.in/GIRPublic/>). This website includes all GI status i.e. refused, registered, withdrawn, abandoned and pending applications in this regard.

5 Review of Literature

The WTO (1994) defines GIs under Article 22.1 of TRIPS as: “*Indications which identify a good as originating in the territory of a Member... where a given quality, reputation or other characteristic of the good is essentially attributable to its geographical origin.*” Several scholars (Rangnekar, 2004; Giovannucci et al., 2009) stress that GIs encompass not only geographical origin but also embedded traditional knowledge, production methods, and cultural identity.

The effectiveness of GIs is largely dependent on the legal features of GIs and the various ideas of GIs with various areas of TRIPS provisions on GIs and compares these provisions with the comparable provisions of the Indian GI Act (Srivastava, 2003; Das, 2006). Legal scholars such as Gangjee (2007) explore the interface between trademark law and GIs, highlighting the legal pluralism in GI protection across countries. GIs have been promoted as tools for rural development and economic empowerment.

According to Barham (2003) and Belletti & Marescotti (2011), GI products often command a price premium, ensure product differentiation, and support sustainable local economies. Some studies (Sylvander, 2004; Bramley et al., 2009) argue that GIs enhance international trade by serving as signals of quality. However, the benefits are unevenly distributed due to market access barriers and differing legal regimes. GI protection is often seen as a way to preserve cultural heritage and collective identity (Bowen, 2010). It safeguards traditional practices and links them to specific landscapes and communities.

Numerous geographic indicators have been examined in relation to rural development and the bolstering of India's economy (Vats, 2016). Numerous studies on GIs have been discussed in the fields of food (Seal & Piramanayagam, 2018; Marie-Vivien, 2016; Chavan, 2022), Indian agriculture (Chaudhary, Yadav & Kumar, 2017), and horticulture (Kishore, 2019). The history and development of GIs in India (Maurya, 2022) and the different difficulties faced in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic (Mishra, 2022) are two further studies that are important for the efficacy of GIs. This study assesses GIs' current efficacy in India.

Developing countries have pushed for expanded GI protections to promote their indigenous products. Recent literature (Belletti et al., 2017) explores the role of GIs in promoting environmentally sustainable practices, particularly in agriculture. Global markets face issues of counterfeiting and misappropriation of GI tags. Enforcement mechanisms remain weak in many jurisdictions (WIPO, 2020).

6. Data Collections and Analysis

6.1 State wise distribution of GIs registration

A total of 588 goods (As per Sec 2 (f) of GI Act 1999) have been registered by different States and UTs separately in the Patent Office in India up to July 26, 2024. The following table shows the distribution of the goods registration by the States during this period.

Table 1: Statement showing state wise distribution of GI Tags

S.N.	States/UTs	Total	%
1	Andhra Pradesh	19	3.23
2	Arunachal Pradesh	19	3.23
3	Assam	31	5.27
4	Bihar	16	2.72
5	Chhattisgarh	7	1.19
6	Goa	10	1.70
7	Gujarat	27	4.59
8	Himachal Pradesh	10	1.70
9	Jammu & Kashmir	16	2.72
10	Jharkhand	1	0.17
11	Karnataka	44	7.48
12	Kerala	35	5.95
13	Ladakh (UT)	4	0.68
14	Madhya Pradesh	21	3.57
15	Maharashtra	49	8.33
16	Manipur	6	1.02
17	Meghalaya	6	1.02
18	Mizoram	7	1.19
19	Nagaland	4	0.68
20	Odisha	26	4.42
21	Pondicherry	2	0.34
22	Rajasthan	20	3.40
23	Sikkim	1	0.17
24	Tamil Nadu	59	10.03
25	Telangana	17	2.89
26	Tripura	4	0.68
27	Uttar Pradesh	74	12.59
28	Uttarakhand	26	4.42
29	West Bengal	27	4.59
Total		588	100.00

Chart 1: State wise distribution of GI registrations

Results: The above table and chart show that highest number of GI tags i.e. 74 (12.59% of total GI application by each State i.e. 588) are found in Uttar Pradesh and then Tamil Nadu shows 59 Tags (10.03%). Third and fourth positions hold Maharashtra (49 GI Tags i.e. 8.33%) and Karnataka (44 GI Tags i.e. 7.48%) respectively. A total number of 27 GI Tags (4.59%) are found in West Bengal.

6.2 Joint GI Tags holders

Although GI tags safeguard goods associated with a particular region, the same GI product is frequently produced by numerous small manufacturers or artisan groups in that area. To ensure that everyone in that area benefits, the GI is owned by a number of stakeholders rather than a single state or UT. Therefore, some goods have been registered of GI Tags by two or more states and/or Union

Territories (UTs). GI law of India encourages joint ownership to represent all legitimate producers fairly.

Table 2: Statement showing GI Tags registered by more than one state

S.N.	States/UTs	Agricultural	Handicraft	Total
1	Arunachal Pradesh and Assam	1	-	1
2	Kerala, Karnataka & Tamil Nadu	1	-	1
3	Maharashtra & Madhya Pradesh	1	-	1
4	Maharashtra, Gujarat, Dadara & Nagar Haveli, Daman Diu	-	1	1
5	Punjab, Haryana & Rajasthan	-	1	1
6	Telangana & Andhra Pradesh	1	-	1
7	Andhra Pradesh & Odisha	1	-	1
8	Assam and Arunachal Pradesh	-	1	1
9	Karnataka & Kerala	2	-	2
10	Karnataka & Maharashtra	-	1	1
11	Kerala & Tamil Nadu	1	-	1
12	Manipur & Nagaland	1	-	1
13	Punjab / Haryana / Himachal Pradesh / Delhi / Uttarakhand / Uttar Pradesh / Jammu & Kashmir	1	-	1
14	Sikkim and West Bengal	1	-	1
15	Uttar Pradesh & Madhya Pradesh	1	-	1
16	Uttar Pradesh and Madhya Pradesh	1	-	1
	Total	13	4	17

Results: A total of 17 products get GI tags jointly out of which 13 are agricultural products and 4 are handicraft products.

6.3 Category-wise distribution of GI Tags

There are five categories of GI tags have been registered. These are Agricultural goods, Food Stuff, Handicraft products, Manufactured goods and Natural goods.

Table No.3: Statement showing category of goods for GI Tags

S.N.	Category of Goods	Total GI Tags	%
1	Agricultural	197	32.56
2	Food Stuff	45	7.44
3	Handicraft	342	56.53

S.N.	Category of Goods	Total GI Tags	%
4	Manufactured	18	2.98
5	Natural goods	3	0.50
	Total	605	100.00

Chart 2: Category wise distribution of GI tags

- Handicrafts (56.53%): The largest share of registered GIs comes from handicrafts - iconic items like Kanchipuram saris, Tanjore paintings, and Chola bronzes belong here.
- Agricultural goods (32.56%): A significant part encompasses produce such as mangoes, spices, and rice varieties.
- Food Stuff (7.44%): Notable foodstuffs with GI tags are Rasgulla (West Bengal & Odisha – both have separate GI tags), Mysore Pak (Karnataka), Bikaneri Bhujia (Rajasthan), Tirunelveli Halwa (Tamil Nadu), Srivilliputtur Palkova (Tamil Nadu) etc.
- Manufactured items including textiles (2.987%): Smaller shares. Textiles and manufactured goods (like perfumes, metal crafts) count for a smaller proportion.
- Natural goods (0.50%): this category occupies an even smaller percentage of GI registrations. Some notable items are Makrana Marble (Rajasthan), Mizo Chilli (Bird's Eye Chilli) Mizoram, Kashmir Saffron (Jammu & Kashmir), Marble Stone of Bhedaghat (Madhya Pradesh), Blue Pottery Clay (Rajasthan) Aluva Clay (Kerala) and so on.

6.3.1 Handicrafts

Handicrafts form the largest category among products with Geographical Indication (GI) tags in India. These are manually crafted traditional products that reflect the culture, skill, and heritage of a specific region. Their uniqueness is rooted in the local materials, artisanal techniques, and historical or cultural significance tied to a particular geography (Development Commissioner (Handicrafts), 2017).

Table 4: States/UTs wise distribution of Handicraft products

Sl. No.	States/UTs	No. of GI Tags
1	Jharkhand	1
2	Nagaland	1
3	Ladakh (UT)	2
4	Meghalaya	2
5	Pondicherry	2
6	Tripura	2
7	Manipur	3
8	Chhattisgarh	5
9	Mizoram	5
10	Himachal Pradesh	7
11	Bihar	9
12	Uttarakhand	9
13	Jammu & Kashmir	10
14	Arunachal Pradesh	11
15	Maharashtra	12
16	Madhya Pradesh	14
17	Andhra Pradesh	15
18	Kerala	15
19	Telangana	15
20	West Bengal	15
21	Odisha	16
22	Rajasthan	17
23	Karnataka	19
24	Assam	20
25	Gujarat	23
26	Tamil Nadu	35
27	Uttar Pradesh	53
	Grand Total	338

Chart 2: State wise distribution of GI tags for handicraft products

Results: A total of 338 handicraft products have been registered for GI tags out of 605 products during this study period. The above table shows that large number of GI tags found in Uttar Pradesh (53), Tamil Nadu (35), Gujrat (23) Assam (20) and so on. Almost same numbers (14 to 17) are found in case of Madhya Pradesh, Andhra Pradesh, Kerala, Telangana, West Bengal, Odisha and Rajasthan. Only one or few numbers are found in Jharkhand, Nagaland, Ladakh (UT), Meghalaya, Pondicherry and in Tripura.

6.3.2 Agricultural Goods

Geographical Indication (GI) tags have been applied to a wide range of agricultural goods in India because of their distinctive characteristics related to geography, climate, soil, and traditional farming practices. These GI tags support local farmers and communities by preserving the identity, highlighting the distinctiveness, and raising the market value of the products.

Table 5: States/UTs wise distribution of Agricultural Goods

Sl. No.	States/UTs	No. of GI Tags by each State	Total
1	(i) Andhra Pradesh (ii) Rajasthan (iii) Sikkim (iv) Telangana (v) Tripura	1	5
2	(i) Chhattisgarh (ii) Himachal Pradesh (iii) Ladakh (UT) (iv) Mizoram	2	8
3	(i) Gujarat (ii) Manipur (iii) Meghalaya (iv) Nagaland	3	12
4	(i) Arunachal Pradesh (ii) Jammu & Kashmir (iii) Madhya Pradesh (iv) Odisha	4	16
5	Bihar	6	6
6	(i) Goa (ii) West Bengal	7	14
7	Assam	10	10
8	Uttar Pradesh	11	11
9	Tamil Nadu	14	14
10	Uttarakhand	15	15
11	Kerala	18	18
12	Karnataka	21	21
13	Maharashtra	34	34
Total			184

Results: A total of 184 GI tags are found for agricultural products in India. Highest number (34) of GI tags are found in Maharashtra, then Karnataka (21), Kerala (18). West Bengal and Goa have 7 GI tags separately on agricultural products. Only one or two GI tags are found in Andhra Pradesh, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Telangana, Tripura, Chhattisgarh, Himachal Pradesh, Ladakh (UT) and in Mizoram.

6.3.3 Food Stuff

India has a wide variety of traditional food products that have received Geographical Indication (GI) tags, reflecting the rich culinary heritage of the country. GI tags for foodstuff help protect the identity and uniqueness of these regional products while supporting local economies and traditional farming or preparation methods.

Table 5: States/UTs wise distribution of Food Stuff

Sl.No.	States/UTs	No. of GI Tags
1	Arunachal Pradesh	1
2	Bihar	1
3	Karnataka	1
4	Rajasthan	1
5	Telangana	1
6	Tripura	1
7	Uttarakhand	1
8	Goa	2
9	Jammu & Kashmir	2
10	Kerala	2
11	Maharashtra	2
12	Andhra Pradesh	3
13	Madhya Pradesh	3
14	Odisha	5
15	West Bengal	5
16	Uttar Pradesh	6
17	Tamil Nadu	8
Grand Total		45

Results: A total of 45 GI tags are found for Food Stuff in different States/UTs in India. Tamil Nadu holds 8 tags which includes Srivilliputtur Palkova, Kovilpatti Kadalai Mittai, Palani Panchamirtham, Manapparai Murukku, Ooty Varkey, Udangudi Panangkarupatti, Salem Sago (Javvarisi) and Marthandam Honey. There are 6 tags in Uttar Pradesh. These are Hathras Hing, Muzaffarnagar Gur (Jaggery), Banaras Lal Peda, Jaunpur Imarti, Banaras Thandai, Banaras and Tirangi Barfi. West Bengal (for Bardhaman Sitabhog, Bardhaman Mihidana, Banglar Rasogolla, Sundarban Honey and Joynagar Moa) and Odisha (for Odisha Rasagola, Kendrapara Rasabali, Odisha Khajuri Guda, Dhenkanal Magji and Similipal Kai Chutney of Odisha) have 5 each GI tags.

6.3.4 Manufactured Goods

GI tags for manufactured goods help protect diverse artistic and cultural heritage of India. They ensure that authentic, traditional skills remain economically viable and globally recognized.

Table 6: States/UTs wise distribution of Manufactured Goods

Sl.No.	States/UTs	Manufactured
1	Assam	1
2	Goa	1

Sl.No.	States/UTs	Manufactured
3	Himachal Pradesh	1
4	Maharashtra	1
5	Meghalaya	1
6	Odisha	1
7	Uttarakhand	1
8	Tamil Nadu	2
9	Arunachal Pradesh	3
10	Karnataka	3
11	Uttar Pradesh	3
Total		18

Results: A total of 18 GI tags are found for manufactured goods in India. Some of these items are Kannauj Perfume (Logo), Meerut Scissors, Agra Leather Footwear for Uttar Pradesh; Mysore Agarbathi, Mysore Sandalwood Oil, Mysore Sandal Soap for Karnataka; Arunachal Pradesh Adi Apong, Arunachal Pradesh Dao (Sword), "Arunachal Pradesh Marua Apo (Marua Millet Beverage)" for Arunachal Pradesh; Coimbatore Wet Grinder, East India Leather for Tamil Nadu; Nainital Mombatti (Candle) for Uttarakhand; Ganjam Kewda Rooh for Odisha and so on.

6.3.5 Natural Goods

According to Geographical Indications of commodities (Registration and Protection) Act, 1999 in India, natural commodities are one of the four main categories that qualify for Geographical Indications (GI). Without much human involvement, these are items that naturally exist in a particular geographic location and have special characteristics brought about by the local environment, climate, or ecology.

There are three natural goods have been found in this study period for GI tags. These are Gujarat (for Ambaji White Marble), Rajasthan (Makrana Marble) and Uttar Pradesh (Chunar Balua Patthar).

7. Discussions

Due to a confluence of awareness, administrative, legal, and financial obstacles, the registration rate for Geographical Indications (GI) tags is comparatively low in India. Below is a summary of the main causes:

- Lack of Awareness: Limited Knowledge, No institutional support etc.
- Cumbersome registration process: Complex procedures, high costs, time-consuming process etc.
- Lack of legal and technical expertise: Preparing the application, defining the uniqueness of the product, drafting the statement of case
- Limited perceived benefits: Even after getting a GI tag, many products see little commercial gain because of poor marketing and branding, lack of access to national and international markets and no clear mechanism to enforce rights or prevent misuse.
- Other issues like weak post-registration support, fragmented producer communities, regional imbalance so on.

8. Conclusion

While providing local populations with economic opportunities, Geographical Indications (GIs) are essential to preserving rich cultural, agricultural, and artisanal legacy of India. By elevating and valuing regionally specific items, they act as a tool to preserve traditional knowledge and advance rural development. For GI tags to have a greater impact in India, there needs to be more grassroots education and awareness, streamlined processes, reasonably priced legal aid, proactive government support for branding, marketing, enforcement, and an emphasis on capacity-building of producer communities in India.

References:

- About us. (n.d.). Retrieved May 23, 2025 from <https://ipindia.gov.in/about-us-gi.htm>
- Barham, E. (2003). Translating terroir: The global challenge of French AOC labeling. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 19(1), 127–138. Doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0743-0167\(02\)00052-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0743-0167(02)00052-9)
- Belletti, G., & Marescotti, A. (2011). Origin products, GI special protection schemes and rural development. In E. Barham & B. Sylvander (Eds.), *Labels of origin for food: Local development, global recognition* (pp. 75–91). Cambridge, MA: CABI International.
- Bowen, S. (2010). Embedding local places in global spaces: Geographical indications as a territorial development strategy. *Rural Sociology*, 75(2), 209–243. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1549-0831.2009.00007.x>
- Bramley, C., Biénabe, E., & Kirsten, J. F. (2009). The economics of geographical indications: Towards a conceptual framework for geographical indication research in developing countries. WIPO.
- Chaudhary, R. C., Yadav, S. K., & Kumar, S. (2017). Geographical Indications in Indian Agriculture on the anvil. *Journal of Bio Innovation*, 6(5), 790-816.
- Chavan, S. (2022). Geographic Indicator Foods of India. *Journal of Food and Nutrition*, 1(1), 2836-2276.
- Das, K. (2006). Protection of India's Geographical Indications': An Overview of the Indian Legislation and the TRIPS Scenario. *Indian Journal of International Law*, 46(1), 39.
- Development Commissioner (Handicrafts). (2017). A Compendium of Indian Handicrafts & Handlooms covered under Geographical Indications (GI). Retrieved July 22, 2025 from https://handicrafts.nic.in/CmsUpload/12222017102212GI%20BOOK%20FINAL%202-5-17_resized.pdf
- Gangjee, D. S. (2007). Quibbling siblings: Conflicts between trademarks and geographical indications. *Chicago-Kent Law Review*, 82(3), 1253–1291.
- Geographical Indications. (n.d.). Retrieved June 25, 2025 from <https://ariyalur.nic.in/geographical-indications/>
- Giovannucci, D., Josling, T., Kerr, W. A., O'Connor, B., & Yeung, M. T. (2009). Guide to geographical indications: Linking products and their origins. International Trade Centre.

- InsightsIAS (October 23, 2023). GI Tags: How does it help? Retrieved May 12, 2025 from <https://www.insightsonindia.com/2023/10/30/gi-tags-how-does-it-help/>
- Kishore, K. (2019). Geographical Indications in Horticulture: An Indian perspective. *Journal of Intellectual Property Rights*, 23, 159-166.
- Marie-Vivien, D. (2016). The protection of traditional local foods through geographical indications in India. In *Eating Traditional Food* (pp. 81-99). Routledge.
- Maurya, B. R. (2022). History and Evolution of Geographical Indications in India. *Intellectual Property Rights*, 130. Retrieved August 24, 2024 from <https://alexispress.us/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Introduction-to-Intellectual-Property-Rights.pdf#page=137>
- Mishra, A. (2022). Geographical indications-challenges and opportunities in post-covid India. *Journal of Intellectual Property Rights (JIPR)*, 26(2), 57-68.
- Overview: the TRIPS Agreement. (n.d.). Retrieved May 11, 2025 from https://www.wto.org/english/tratop_e/trips_e/intel2_e.htm
- Rangnekar, D. (2004). The Socio-Economics of Geographical Indications: A Review of Empirical Evidence.
- Rangnekar, D. (2004). The socio-economics of geographical indications: A review of empirical evidence from Europe. UNCTAD-ICTSD Project on IPRs and Sustainable Development, Issue Paper No. 8. United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD). Retrieved May 22, 2025 from <https://docslib.org/doc/7893692/the-socio-economics-of-geographical-indications-a-review-of-empirical-evidence-from-europe>
- Rudrajyoti, M. (n.d.). State Wise Registered GI of India 26-07-2024. Retrieved May 22, 2025 from <https://www.scribd.com/document/765285704/State-Wise-Registered-GI-of-India-26-07-2024>
- Seal, P. P., & Piramanayagam, S. (2018, June). Branding geographical indication (GI) of food and its implications on gastronomic tourism: An Indian perspective. In 8th advances in hospitality and tourism marketing and management (AHTMM) conference (p. 125).
- Srivastava, S. C. (2003). Geographical indications and legal framework in India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 4022-4033.
- Sylvander, B. (2004). Development of origin-labelled products: Humanity, innovation and sustainability. Dolphins WP7 Report, European Commission, Brussels.
- Vats, N. K. (2016). Geographical indication-the factors of rural development and strengthening economy.
- World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). (2020). Geographical Indications: An Introduction. Geneva: WIPO. Retrieved May 23, 2025 from <https://www.wipo.int/publications/en/details.jsp?id=4524>
- World Trade Organization (WTO). (1994). Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS), Article 22.1. Retrieved May 12, 2025 from https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/27-trips_03_e.htm

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Abstract: YouTube has become a vital part of modern life, extending its role beyond entertainment to academic and research purposes. It provides access to a wide range of information and supports scholars across various disciplines. This study investigates the use of YouTube by social science research scholars at Jadavpur University. Data were collected through a survey, using a structured questionnaire administered to a systematically selected sample from eight social science departments. The findings reveal that although YouTube is appreciated for its accessibility and engaging content, researchers primarily use it as a supplementary resource rather than a primary academic tool, due to concerns about the reliability and credibility of its content. Additionally, the platform presents several challenges, such as disruptive advertisements, questionable content quality, algorithm-driven distractions, and information overload.

Keywords: YouTube, Social Media, Academic Research, Information Source, Social Science Scholars, Jadavpur University, YouTube in Education, Research Tools, Digital Learning, Content Credibility

1 Introduction

In the Web 2.0 era, YouTube has become a key platform for research and education in the social sciences. It offers free access to lectures, tutorials, and conference videos, enabling researchers to learn at their own pace. Interactive features promote global collaboration, while academic channels extend research beyond traditional journals. Its visual content simplifies complex ideas and ensures equitable access, fostering innovation and professional growth.

Social sciences provide critical insights into human behavior, social structures, and cultural dynamics. Using qualitative and quantitative methods, fields like sociology, psychology, and political science address issues such as inequality, governance, and public health. They inform policymaking and

sustainable development by analyzing individual and institutional interactions.

YouTube supports social science research by democratizing academic content and facilitating methodological learning through videos and discussions. Researchers benefit from peer engagement and diverse perspectives, though challenges like misinformation and distractions remain. This study examines YouTube's usage, purpose, satisfaction, and impact among social science scholars at Jadavpur University.

2 Objective

This study has made an endeavour to assess the extent, purpose, satisfaction, and influence of YouTube usage among social science researchers in accessing social science-related information.

3 Methodology

To achieve the objective of the study, the survey method was employed to collect the necessary data. As the study population is large and heterogeneous—comprising research scholars from multiple social science departments at the university—a systematic sampling technique was used. A sample was drawn from eight departments: Economics, Education, Film Studies, History, International Relations, Library & Information Science, Physical Education, and Sociology. The selected sample included forty research scholars, consisting of the five senior-most researchers from each department.

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire specifically designed for this purpose. The collected data were then analyzed based on the respondents' inputs and presented through charts and tables, in alignment with the study's objectives.

4 Findings

The analysis of the collected data reveals the following findings.

4.1 Gender-wise Division of the Respondents

The following figure shows the gender-wise division of the respondents.

Figure 1: Gender-wise Division of the Respondents

Figure 1 illustrates the gender-wise distribution of the respondents. Out of a total of 40 respondents, 17 are male and 23 are female. This corresponds to 42.5% male and 57.5% female participants.

4.2 Use of YouTube for Educational Purpose

The following figure shows the usage of YouTube for educational purposes.

Figure 2: Use of YouTube for Educational Purpose (%)

Figure 2 illustrates the use of YouTube for educational purposes among the respondents. Among the total participants, 30% strongly agreed that they use YouTube for educational purposes, while 47.5% agreed with the same. However, 15% of the respondents remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. This chart clearly indicates that the majority of respondents utilize YouTube as an educational tool.

4.3 Frequency of Use of YouTube

The following chart shows the frequency of use of YouTube by the researchers.

Figure 3: Frequency of Use of YouTube (%)

Figure 3 represents the frequency of YouTube usage among the researchers. According to the data, 27.5% of respondents use YouTube very often, while 52.5% use it often. The remaining 20% remained neutral regarding their frequency of use. Notably, none of the participants reported using YouTube rarely or never, indicating that YouTube has become an important and widely adopted tool among the respondents.

4.4 Duration of YouTube Usage

The following chart represents time duration of usage of YouTube everyday by the respondents.

Figure 4: Time Duration of Usage of YouTube (%)

Figure 4 provides an overview of the duration of YouTube usage among the respondents. The chart reveals that every participant uses YouTube regularly. Specifically, 5% of respondents spend between 30 minutes to 1 hour per day on the platform, while 27.5% use it for 1 to 2 hours. Around 35% of respondents spend 2 to 3 hours, and 22.5% use it for 3 to 4 hours daily. Additionally, 7.5% spend 4 to 5 hours on YouTube, and only 2.5% use it for more than 5 hours each day. Notably, no respondent reported spending less than 30 minutes on the platform, indicating the widespread popularity and strong acceptance of YouTube among the participants.

4.5 Purpose of Use of YouTube

This chart shows the different purposes of usage of YouTube.

Figure 5: Purpose of Use of YouTube (%)

Figure 5 illustrates the various purposes for which respondents use YouTube, presenting five main categories along with the percentage of responses for each. The purposes identified include, general information, research, writing research papers, teaching/lecture, and entertainment.

For general information, 47.5% of respondents strongly agreed that they use YouTube for this purpose, 32.5% agreed, and 20% remained neutral. Notably, none of the participants disagreed or strongly disagreed with this statement.

Regarding research purposes, 37.5% of respondents strongly agreed, 30% agreed, 22.5% remained neutral, while 7.5% disagreed and 2.5% strongly disagreed.

For writing research papers, 22.5% agreed, 32.5% remained neutral, 30% disagreed, and 15% strongly disagreed. Interestingly, none of the respondents strongly agreed with this use.

In terms of teaching or lecture purposes, 17.5% strongly agreed, 32.5% agreed, 37.5% were neutral, 10% disagreed, and 2.5% strongly disagreed.

For entertainment, the responses were overwhelmingly positive: 60% strongly agreed, 20% agreed, and 20% remained neutral. No respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed with using YouTube for entertainment.

This chart clearly demonstrates that the majority of respondents use YouTube primarily for entertainment purposes, followed by general information, research, and then teaching or lecture purposes.

4.6. Advantages and disadvantages of Using YouTube

Table 1 shows the various advantages of using YouTube, while Table 2 presents the disadvantages of using YouTube.

Table 1: Advantages of Using YouTube

Sl. No.	Advantages	Strongly Agree (%)		Agree (%)		Neutral (%)		Disagree (%)		Strongly Disagree (%)	
		No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)
a.	Resources related to social sciences are easily accessible 24*7	12	30	16	40	7	17.5	5	12.5	0	0
b.	Doesn't require anybody's permission to watch those videos on you tube	14	35	17	42.5	5	12.5	4	10	0	0
c.	These videos help researchers to learn complex social concepts easily through graphics	10	25	18	45	8	20	4	10	0	0
d.	Helps to improve listening skill	11	27.5	17	42.5	9	22.5	3	7.5	0	0
e.	You tube videos provide in-depth knowledge on a topic related to social sc. In a short period of time	4	10	9	22.5	22	55	4	10	1	2.5
f.	Researchers can concentrate better while watching videos rather than reading text in the books and periodicals	19	47.5	13	32.5	6	15	1	2.5	1	2.5

Sl. No.	Advantages	Strongly Agree (%)	Agree (%)	Neutral (%)	Disagree (%)	Strongly Disagree (%)
g.	You Tube always provide updated information on any topic	6	7	14	10	3
h.	Every video related to social sciences Is very reliable	0	2	7	16	15
i.	You tube can easily replace the need of books and periodicals	0	0	6	16	18
j.	Anybody can find related topics on social sciences after few searches because of you tube's algorithm	6	13	18	3	0
k.	Availability of internet access cannot be a barrier for using you tube	0	2	6	11	21
			5	15	27.5	52.5

Table 1 illustrates the various advantages of YouTube as perceived by the respondents, showing the percentage of agreement or disagreement with each listed statement. The responses are categorized into five levels: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. A detailed analysis of the responses is given below.

Accessibility of Resources: For the first advantage—“Resources related to social science are easily accessible 24×7”—30% of respondents strongly agreed and 40% agreed. 17.5% remained neutral, while 12.5% disagreed. Notably, no respondent strongly disagreed.

Permission-Free Access: Regarding the second statement—“YouTube videos do not require permission to watch”—35% strongly agreed, 42.5% agreed, 12.5% were neutral, and 10% disagreed. Again, no one strongly disagreed.

Understanding Complex Concepts: For the third advantage—“These videos help researchers learn complex social concepts easily through graphics”—25% strongly agreed and 45% agreed. 20% stayed neutral, while 10% disagreed. No respondents strongly disagreed.

Improving Listening Skills: In response to the statement—“YouTube helps improve listening skills”—27.5% strongly agreed and 42.5% agreed. 22.5% remained neutral and 7.5% disagreed, with no strong disagreement reported.

In-Depth Knowledge in Short Time: For the fifth advantage—“YouTube videos provide in-depth knowledge on social science topics in a short time”—only 10% strongly agreed and 22.5% agreed. A significant 55% remained neutral, 10% disagreed, and 2.5% strongly disagreed.

Better Concentration with Videos: The sixth advantage—“Researchers concentrate better while watching videos than reading texts”—received 47.5% strongly agree and 32.5% agree responses. 15% were neutral, while 2.5% disagreed and another 2.5% strongly disagreed.

Updated Information: On the seventh point—“YouTube always provides updated information on any topic”—15% strongly agreed and 17.5% agreed. However, 35% were neutral, 25% disagreed, and 7.5% strongly disagreed, indicating some skepticism regarding content currency.

Reliability of Content: For the eighth statement—“Every video related to social sciences is very reliable”—none strongly agreed. Only 5% agreed and 17.5% remained neutral, whereas 40% disagreed and 37.5% strongly disagreed. This clearly shows that while YouTube is a useful tool, researchers question the reliability of its content.

Replacing Books and Periodicals: The ninth advantage—“YouTube can replace the need for books and periodicals”—received no agreement. Instead, 40% strongly disagreed and 45% disagreed, while 15% remained neutral. This underscores the continued importance of traditional academic resources.

Search Efficiency: Regarding the statement—“Related topics in social sciences can be found easily due to YouTube’s algorithm”—15% strongly agreed, 32.5% agreed, 45% remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. No strong disagreement was recorded.

Internet Access as a Barrier: The final advantage—“Internet access is not a barrier to using YouTube”—was met with skepticism. Only 5% agreed, 15% were neutral, while 27.5% disagreed and 52.5% strongly disagreed. This suggests that internet availability remains a significant limitation for some researchers.

This data suggests YouTube is valued for convenience and engagement but is not seen as a standalone academic resource due to credibility and access issues.

Table: 2 shows various disadvantages of using YouTube.

Table 2: Disadvantages of Using YouTube

Sl. No.	Disadvantages	Strongly Agree (%)		Agree (%)		Neutral (%)		Disagree (%)		Strongly Disagree (%)	
		No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)	No. of Respondent	(%)
a.	In case of YouTube videos, there is a very little space to fill up with your imagination.	0	0	26	65	11	27.5	3	7.5	0	0
b.	Watching YouTube videos related to social sciences. Is not that satisfactory regarding learning new concepts	0	0	0	0	9	22.5	31	77.5	0	0
c.	YouTube shows so many advertisements at the time of learning something important or in the middle of some complex concepts and this always breaks the concentration of researchers.	14	35	19	47.5	7	17.5	0	0	0	0
d.	Every video on YouTube related to social Sc. Doesn't come from a reliable sources	12	30	21	52.5	7	17.5	0	0	0	0
e.	It's tough to concentrate on a single topic due to it's algorithm because related topics tend to appear continuously.	2	5	13	32.5	23	57.5	2	5	0	0
f.	It could be a medium of exposure to inappropriate content for researchers.	9	22.5	28	70	3	7.5	0	0	0	0
g.	Finding relevant information on YouTube is difficult	0	0	6	15	11	27.5	20	50	3	7.5
h.	Information overload	3	7.5	27	67.5	10	25	0	0	0	0
i.	Difficulty in searching	0	0	3	7.5	14	35	23	57.5	0	0
j.	Information can be lost easily	2	5	16	40	18	45	4	10	0	0
k.	YouTube can never replace Printed books and periodicals.	31	77.5	9	22.5	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2 illustrates the various advantages of YouTube as perceived by the respondents, showing the percentage of agreement or disagreement with each listed statement. The responses are categorized into five levels: Strongly Agree, Agree, Neutral, Disagree, and Strongly Disagree. A detailed analysis of the responses is given below.

Limited Imaginative Engagement: Regarding the statement “YouTube videos offer very little room for imagination,” 65% of respondents agreed, while 27.5% remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. No respondents strongly agreed or strongly disagreed.

Learning Satisfaction: For the statement “Watching YouTube videos related to social sciences is not satisfactory for learning new concepts,” 77.5% disagreed, and 22.5% were neutral. No respondents expressed agreement or strong disagreement, suggesting that most find YouTube satisfactory for conceptual learning despite its limitations.

Advertisement Interruptions: A significant concern was highlighted in response to the statement “YouTube shows too many advertisements during important learning moments, disrupting concentration.” Here, 35% strongly agreed and 47.5% agreed, while 17.5% remained neutral. No disagreement was reported.

Reliability of Content: On the issue of credibility—“Not every YouTube video on social science comes from a reliable source”—30% strongly agreed and 52.5% agreed, with 17.5% remaining neutral. Again, no disagreement was observed.

Distractions from Algorithm: In response to the statement “It is difficult to concentrate on a single topic due to YouTube’s algorithm suggesting continuous related videos,” 5% strongly agreed and 32.5% agreed. A majority (57.5%) remained neutral, while 5% disagreed. No strong disagreement was recorded.

Limited Imaginative Engagement: Regarding the statement “YouTube videos offer very little room for imagination,” 65% of respondents agreed, while 27.5% remained neutral, and 7.5% disagreed. No respondents strongly agreed or strongly disagreed.

Learning Satisfaction: For the statement “Watching YouTube videos related to social sciences is not satisfactory for learning new concepts,” 77.5% disagreed, and 22.5% were neutral. No respondents expressed agreement or strong disagreement, suggesting that most find YouTube satisfactory for conceptual learning despite its limitations.

Advertisement Interruptions: A significant concern was highlighted in response to the statement “YouTube shows too many advertisements during important learning moments, disrupting concentration.” Here, 35% strongly agreed and 47.5% agreed, while 17.5% remained neutral. No disagreement was reported.

Reliability of Content: On the issue of credibility—“Not every YouTube video on social science comes from a reliable source”—30% strongly agreed and 52.5% agreed, with 17.5% remaining neutral. Again, no disagreement was observed.

Distractions from Algorithm: In response to the statement “It is difficult to concentrate on a single topic due to YouTube’s algorithm suggesting continuous related videos,” 5% strongly agreed and 32.5% agreed. A majority (57.5%) remained neutral, while 5% disagreed. No strong disagreement was recorded.

Exposure to Inappropriate Content: A significant 92.5% (22.5% strongly agreed, 70% agreed) felt that YouTube could expose researchers to inappropriate content. Only 7.5% remained neutral; none disagreed.

Difficulty in Finding Relevant Content: On the statement “Finding relevant information on YouTube is difficult,” 15% agreed, 27.5% were neutral, 50% disagreed, and 7.5% strongly disagreed. This mixed response suggests inconsistent user experiences.

Information Overload: Concerning the statement “Information overload,” 7.5% strongly agreed and 67.5% agreed, while 25% were neutral. No respondents disagreed or strongly disagreed, highlighting the overwhelming nature of content on the platform.

Search Difficulties: In response to “Difficulty in searching,” 7.5% agreed, 35% remained neutral, and 57.5% disagreed. No strong agreement or strong disagreement was recorded.

Loss of Information: For the statement “Information can be lost easily,” 5% strongly agreed, 40% agreed, 45% remained neutral, and 10% disagreed. No one strongly disagreed, suggesting moderate concern over content permanence.

Cannot Replace Traditional Resources: A unanimous response was recorded for the statement “YouTube can never replace printed books and periodicals.” Here, 77.5% strongly agreed and 22.5% agreed, while no respondent disagreed, strongly disagreed, or remained neutral. This result clearly reaffirms the continued importance of traditional academic materials.

YouTube’s disadvantages—**unreliable content, ad intrusions, algorithmic distractions, and information overload**—position it as a supplemental, not primary, research tool. While valued for accessibility and engagement, its flaws necessitate cautious use alongside peer-reviewed and printed materials. The unanimous preference for books underscores YouTube’s role as a **convenient but non-authoritative** resource in academia.

4.6 Technique of Searching

The following chart represents different searching techniques used by the social science researchers.

Figure 6: Technique of Searching

Figure 6 illustrates the various techniques employed by respondents to search for information on YouTube. The chart presents four distinct search approaches along with the percentage distribution of usage for each. The techniques include: Keyword Search, Phrase Search, Browsing Recommended Videos While Watching Related Content, and Accessing Content from YouTube Channels Dedicated to Social Sciences.

The data analysis reveals that a majority—67.5%—of researchers most frequently use the keyword search method to find their required information, while 27.5% use it frequently, and 5% use it occasionally. Notably, none of the respondents reported using this method rarely or never.

Similarly, 62.5% of researchers most frequently use the phrase search method, with 30% using it frequently and 7.5% using it occasionally. Again, no respondents reported using this method rarely or never.

In contrast, only 17.5% of researchers most frequently rely on the third method—recommendations while watching related videos. 22.5% use this method frequently, 40% use it occasionally, 17.5% use it rarely, and 2.5% never use it.

The fourth method—searching through YouTube channels focused on social sciences—is most frequently used by just 15% of respondents. 20% use it frequently, 42.5% occasionally, 12.5% rarely, and 10% never use this approach.

These findings clearly indicate that the majority of researchers rely heavily on keyword search (67.5%) and phrase search (62.5%) as their primary methods for finding information on YouTube. In contrast, passive methods like recommended videos and dedicated channels are used less frequently, with higher occasional/rare usage.

This suggests that active, direct search strategies dominate over algorithmic recommendations or curated content for academic purposes.

4.7 Level of Satisfaction

This chart shows the level of satisfaction of the respondents.

Figure 7: Level of Satisfaction (%)

Majority Satisfaction: Over half of the respondents (57.5%) find YouTube effective for their information needs.

Partial Satisfaction: A significant portion (32.5%) feels YouTube meets their needs only partially, suggesting room for improvement in content relevance or depth.

Dissatisfaction: A small but notable group (10%) reports dissatisfaction, indicating that YouTube may not always fulfil specialized academic or research-based queries.

5 Conclusion

The findings of the study reveal that YouTube serves as a useful resource for social science researchers. While it is appreciated for its accessibility and interactive content—and most researchers use it as a supplementary aid—it is not considered a primary academic source due to concerns about reliability and accessibility. Despite its advantages, the platform has several limitations, including intrusive advertisements, questionable content accuracy, algorithm-driven distractions, and information overload.

Researchers continue to prioritize traditional academic materials, viewing YouTube as a complementary tool rather than a replacement. Although most users find it helpful, a small portion express partial or complete dissatisfaction, suggesting that alternative platforms or improved search methods may be needed to meet specific research needs. YouTube remains a valuable, though imperfect, resource that requires critical evaluation for academic use.

References:

- Breuer, J., Kohne, J., & Mohseni, M. R. (2023). Using YouTube data for social science research. In *Research Handbook on Digital Sociology* (pp. 258-277). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Giglietto, F., Rossi, L., & Bennato, D. (2012). The open laboratory: Limits and possibilities of using Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube as a research data source. *Journal of technology in human services*, 30(3-4), 145-159.
- Jang, S. (2011). YouTube as an innovative resource for social science research.
- Moon, K., & Blackman, D. (2014). A guide to understanding social science research for natural scientists. *Conservation biology*, 28(5), 1167-1177.
- Rockwell, R. C. (1994). An integrated network interface between the researcher and social science data resources: In search of a practical vision. *Social Science Computer Review*, 12(2), 202-214.
- Snelson, C. (2011). YouTube across the disciplines: A review of the literature. *MERLOT Journal of Online learning and teaching*.
- Walter, M. (2006). The nature of social science research. *Social research methods: An Australian perspective*, 1(2).

The Moral Limits of Transparency: Privacy, Censorship, and Access to Information

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Abstract: *Many people agree that transparency is essential to social responsibility, ethical business practices, and democratic governance. Its moral worth is not unqualified, nevertheless. Overzealous openness can undermine valid privacy rights, open doors for harm, and defend repressive tactics under the guise of safety. The ethical limits of transparency are examined in this essay, with particular attention to how they interact with information access and privacy rights. Through philosophical analysis and case studies, the research investigates when transparency serves the public good and when it becomes ethically problematic. Along with current discussions on corporate disclosure, state secrecy, and censorship in the digital age, the discussion takes into account theories like deontological ethics, utilitarianism, and virtue ethics*

Keywords: Web Accessibility, Persons with Disabilities (PWD), Recruitment Websites, Digital Inclusivity, West Bengal.

1 Introduction

The mantra “sunlight is the best disinfectant,” attributed to Justice Louis Brandeis, captures the moral appeal of transparency. By enabling scrutiny, transparency fosters accountability, deters corruption, and strengthens trust. Yet, transparency without ethical limits can expose sensitive information, endanger individuals, and erode fundamental freedoms. Rethinking the concept of privacy in the digital age inevitably entangles the descriptive and the normative dimensions of this concept. In an age

defined by the rapid flow of information, the value of transparency has become a central tenet of democratic societies, corporate accountability, and digital governance. However, the pursuit of full transparency raises difficult ethical questions about its limits. When does openness infringe on individual privacy? Can censorship ever be morally justified in protecting vulnerable populations or maintaining social stability? And who gets to decide what information is accessible, and to whom? This topic explores the complex moral terrain where transparency intersects with privacy rights, government and corporate control, and the public's right to know. It challenges us to consider not just how much information should be shared, but under what conditions, by whom, and for what purpose.

2 Literature Review

Becker (2019) said that paper took as a starting point a recent development in privacy-debates: the emphasis on social and institutional environments in the definition and the defenses of privacy. Recognizing the merits of this approach supplement it in two respects. First, an analysis of the relation between privacy and autonomy teaches that in the digital age more than ever individual autonomy is threatened. Secondly, he elucidated the background of the social approach. Its importance is not exclusively related to the digital age.

Rascão (2020) reflected in this article on freedom of expression, privacy, ethical and social responsibility, in the context of social networks, in the context of the experience of democracy in cyberspace. It asked questions about ensuring the protection of privacy, freedom, and autonomy of internet users in the internet environment. The article discussed the concepts that guide this theme and that are directly involved with related domains. It was an alert to the need for ethical and legal protection of the digital data of internet users, aiming at the autonomous safeguarding of their digital identities.

Al-Harhi., Al-Raisi, & Al-Humairi (2023) tried to shed some light on the current understanding of privacy, the challenges of privacy in SMN and the laws and regulation that aims to secure this privacy for the people in their paper.

Deep, A. (2023) the paper discussed the role of legal education in preparing future generations of attorneys to navigate the ethical complexities introduced by technology. It explored the integration of technology-focused ethical training into legal curricula and the development of guidelines to assist legal professionals in upholding ethical standards in the digital age. This article provided a comprehensive overview of the ethical dimensions surrounding the integration of technology into the legal profession. By examining the challenges and opportunities presented by digital advancements, it sought to contribute to the ongoing discourse on how legal practitioners can navigate the ethical landscape in a rapidly evolving technological environment.

Ijaiya (2024) has explored the intersection of data privacy and technological advancements, highlighting the ethical challenges that arise in areas such as data collection, storage, and usage. It examined how technologies like artificial intelligence and blockchain are reshaping privacy norms, often outpacing regulatory frameworks. Key ethical concerns, including informed consent, data ownership, algorithmic bias, and the risk of discrimination, are discussed in detail. The study also presented policy solutions aimed at mitigating these challenges, such as the implementation of privacy-by-design principles, the adoption of global data protection regulations like the GDPR, and the development of transparent, accountable AI systems. The role of public-private partnerships and interdisciplinary collaborations in addressing these issues is emphasized, along with the importance of

fostering digital literacy and public awareness. By bridging ethical considerations with practical policy recommendations, this article provided a roadmap for navigating the complex interplay between data privacy and technological progress, ultimately advocating for an equitable, secure, and privacy-conscious digital future.

Singh (2024) examined in his paper the ethical concerns related to data privacy in this study in order to aid in the creation of more potent plans for stopping data breaches and lessening their effects. This study also examined a range of tactics that can assist people in understanding their right to privacy and the significance of data protection, such as educational programs, transparency efforts, communication tactics, and ethical data practices.

But there is a few paper has discussed *The Moral Limits of Transparency: Privacy, Censorship, and Access to Information* in depth.

2 Statement of the problem

The statement of the problem is **The Moral Limits of Transparency: Privacy, Censorship, and Access to Information**

Research Questions:

- i. What are the ethical frameworks governing data privacy?
- ii. How effective are current data privacy laws and regulations?
- iii. What is the impact of emerging technologies on data privacy?
- iv. What strategies can be developed to enhance public awareness and trust in data privacy?

3 Objectives

- i. To comprehend the moral principles guiding data privacy.
- ii. To evaluate the efficacy of the rules and regulations currently in place regarding data privacy.
- iii. To investigate how new technologies affect data privacy.
- iv. To create plans for raising public knowledge and confidence in data privacy.

4 Scope & Limitations of the Study

The ethical theories and principles surrounding data privacy ensure that individual rights and social values are respected by guiding the appropriate and equitable use of data. These values include fairness, accountability, transparency, and informed consent. They discuss the collection, use, sharing, and protection of data in order to guard against harm and encourage moral behavior in data-driven settings. The main ethical theories—deontology, consequentialism, and virtue ethics—are examined in depth in this study in order to assess how well they apply to data privacy.

4.1 Deontology and Data Privacy

Immanuel Kant established deontology, which emphasizes the value of obligation and following the law. Deontology, with its focus on moral duties and rules, offers a strong framework for data privacy. It highlights the inalienable right to privacy and the duty to safeguard personal information regardless of the possible repercussions. This equates to a dedication to gaining informed permission, protecting

data, and giving people authority over their personal data. Deontological ethics may lack the flexibility needed to reconcile privacy with other important interests in situations where strict adherence to rules could impede the beneficial use of data, such as in scientific study or emergency medical responses.

4.2 Consequentialism and Data Privacy

Consequentialism is an ethical theory that assesses the morality of actions based on their outcomes or consequences. In the context of data privacy, consequentialism suggests that the collection and use of personal data is justifiable if it leads to a positive outcome, even if it involves some level of privacy intrusion. The major goal is to maximize positive outcomes, such as improved services and innovations, while minimizing negative effects, including privacy violations and data abuse. The idea of proportionality, which involves balancing the benefits of processing data against potential risks to individuals, can be aided by consequentialist approaches to data privacy. Techniques for data anonymization, for instance, can reduce privacy threats and enable insightful data analysis. However, the consequentialist perspective can also lead to moral dilemmas. Invasive data practices may be justified if they are believed to have a significant positive social impact, even at the expense of individual privacy rights, if judgments are solely based on results. This strategy necessitates giving considerable thought to whose interests are given priority and how to guarantee that the advantages of data utilization are shared fairly.

4.3 Virtue Ethics and Data Privacy

Virtue ethics, when applied to data privacy, emphasizes the importance of cultivating virtuous character traits in individuals and organizations handling personal data. Instead of depending only on regulations or penalties, it emphasizes the development of a moral compass that directs ethical data activities. This entails giving virtues like accountability, transparency, justice, and responsibility top priority in all actions involving data. It encourages ongoing ethical education in addition to creating best practices that show a commitment to privacy protection. The main advantage of virtue ethics is its comprehensive approach, which promotes a whole ethical community rather than merely promoting rule compliance. However, its abstract nature could occasionally be a disadvantage. Since it may be challenging to translate well-intentioned actions into exact data protection protocols in the absence of defined standards, integrating virtue ethics with other ethical theories is essential for practical implementation.

4.4 Integrating Ethical Theories in Data Privacy

Applying philosophical frameworks to direct the proper handling of personal data is a key component of integrating ethical theories into data privacy. Important ethical theories that emphasize duties, results, and character, respectively, such as deontology, consequentialism, and virtue ethics, provide different viewpoints on data privacy obligations. By putting these theories into practice, businesses may create strong data governance guidelines, maintain openness, and win over users' trust. An integrated approach can overcome each theory's weaknesses. Adopting consequentialist flexibility might reduce the rigidity of deontology and enable context-sensitive decisions that protect fundamental privacy rights. Similarly, deontological protections and virtue ethics' emphasis on moral character can counteract consequentialism's ability to defend invasions of privacy.

4.5 Enhancing Ethical Guidelines for Data Privacy

Improving ethical standards for data privacy entails putting in place values and procedures that guarantee the responsible handling of personal information while upholding the rights of persons. This entails being open and honest about how data is collected and used, getting informed consent, reducing data collection, guaranteeing data accuracy, and putting strong security measures in place. It also entails encouraging accountability, equity, and continuous observation of data processes. Examining deontology, consequentialism, and virtue ethics may yield a more nuanced understanding of the moral dilemmas pertaining to data privacy. Each theory expands on a more comprehensive ethical framework and offers unique viewpoints. Strong ethical standards that protect individual privacy, promote ethical data practices, and foster a culture of ethical responsibility may be created by combining various points of view. A comprehensive approach is required to address the many ethical concerns related to data privacy in the digital era.

5. The Effectiveness of Laws and Regulations pertaining to Data Privacy

Data privacy laws and regulations aim to protect individuals' personal information from unauthorized access, use, or disclosure. How successfully they accomplish this objective—which takes into account elements like the strength of the laws themselves, the efficiency of the enforcement systems, and the degree of compliance by people and organizations—is how effective they are judged.

Examples of Data Privacy Laws and their Impact:

- **GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) in the EU** has had a major influence on data privacy policies around the world, leading businesses to implement stricter data security procedures.
- **CCPA (California Consumer Privacy Act) in the US** has created rights for consumers about their personal data, such as the ability to see, remove, and refuse to have their data sold.

Figure 1: Overview of key regulations

(Source: <https://www.compassitc.com/blog/ccpa-vs.-gdpr-a-comprehensive-comparison>)

5.1 An overview of the CCPA and GDPR

People now have more control over their personal data thanks to historic data privacy regulations like the California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) and the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). No matter where they are located, all businesses that process the personal data of EU citizens are subject to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). In contrast, California's CCPA is a state statute that governs companies doing business there or gathering personal data from Californians. Although protecting data privacy is their shared goal, its specific standards and scope are different.

5.2 GDPR's implementation and enforcement

Since it went into force on May 25, 2018, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) has drastically changed how businesses handle personal data both inside and outside of the European Union. With an emphasis on "data protection by design and by default," implementation calls on businesses to incorporate data protection into their processing operations from the very beginning of the design process. Supervisory Authorities (SAs), who are in charge of looking into complaints, enforcing sanctions, and guaranteeing compliance, are involved in enforcement in every EU member state. The disparities in enforcement across EU member states, which result in uneven application of the law, constitute a major problem. Furthermore, smaller businesses frequently find it difficult to manage the administrative and financial costs of GDPR compliance, which emphasizes the need for assistance and direction in order to help them comply with the regulations.

5.3 CCPA Enforcement and Implementation

The California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA), now known as the California Consumer Privacy Rights Act (CPRA), is a state law focused on protecting consumer privacy rights. It was initially enacted in 2018 and became effective in 2020, with amendments under the CPRA taking effect later. This case illustrates the importance of transparency and consumer rights under the CCPA. Despite its successes, the CCPA is criticized for its complexity and flaws. The main criticisms are over the law's exceptions and loopholes, which allow certain businesses to avoid complying. Additionally, by relying on consumer actions to start enforcement, including filing complaints, the CCPA puts the burden on individuals who might lack the knowledge or means to comply. The California Privacy Rights Act (CPRA), which is set to take effect in 2023, would create a dedicated enforcement agency and tighten protections to address some of these issues.

5.4 The Regulatory Landscape's Gaps

Despite the benefits of the CCPA and GDPR, there are still a lot of regulatory gaps. One major problem is the uneven application of data privacy laws between nations, which can be perplexing and challenging for multinational firms to follow. Additionally, both legislations have drawn criticism for not sufficiently addressing the emerging privacy risks brought about by the rapid advancements in technology, including big data analytics and artificial intelligence (AI). Another gap is the lack of protection for non-digital data and the differences in how personal data is defined by different regulations. Companies could be able to circumvent stringent privacy laws by exploiting these loopholes. An examination of the enforcement and implementation of the CCPA and GDPR demonstrates the significant advancements in data privacy protections. However, problems like inconsistent enforcement, burdensome compliance requirements, and evolving technological risks highlight the need for continuous improvement. Data privacy laws may remain robust and

comprehensive while defending people's right to privacy in the digital age by addressing these gaps with harmonized regulations, enhanced business support, and firm enforcement strategies.

6 Emerging Technologies' Effect on Data Privacy

Data privacy is being profoundly impacted by emerging technologies like blockchain, AI, and IoT, which provide both benefits and concerns. They present additional dangers associated with data breaches, spying, and algorithmic bias, even though they can improve data collecting, analysis, and security. It is essential to strike a balance between the advantages of new technologies and strong privacy protections.

6.1 Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Data Privacy

Since AI systems rely significantly on data, especially sensitive personal information, for training and operation, AI and data privacy are inextricably connected. Because AI can increase the dangers connected with data collection, use, and potential misuse, this reliance poses serious issues for data privacy. The objectivity of AI systems is dependent on the quality of the training data. In the event that prejudices exist in the training data, the AI is likely to reproduce and even magnify these prejudices, producing unfair and biased results.

The data dependency of AI is that AI algorithms, particularly those used in machine learning, require vast amounts of data to learn and improve. And this data often includes personal information, such as browsing history, location data, biometric information, and even inferred insights based on seemingly innocuous data. There are many privacy risks. That are Unauthorized Data Use, Algorithmic Bias, Data Security Vulnerabilities, Lack of Transparency, Surveillance and Tracking, Inference Risks etc.

6.2 Internet of Things (IoT) and Data Privacy

Due to its capacity to gather enormous volumes of personal data, frequently without the express knowledge or consent of users, the Internet of Things (IoT) poses serious data privacy issues. Despite the convenience and advantages of IoT devices, there are significant worries about the possibility of data misuse, privacy violations, and illegal access. Constant data collecting can result in increasing monitoring by the government and business sectors, as well as a loss of privacy. Furthermore, because IoT devices are interconnected, a breach in one device has the potential to compromise the entire network, exposing a large amount of data. To protect data privacy in the Internet of Things, it is essential to use robust security protocols, apply updates and patches often, and standardize across devices. Additionally, users ought to be in charge of their data and receive clear explanations of the data collection process.

6.3 Big Data Analytics and Data Privacy

Its many benefits, such as improved healthcare outcomes and business strategies, big data analytics poses significant privacy risks. The enormous amount of data handled in big data analytics makes it difficult to provide the safety of all personal information. One of the main privacy concerns is the potential for re-identification. Even in situations where datasets have been anonymized, sophisticated data analytics technologies may be able to re-identify individuals by cross-referencing several data points. This danger is especially important to be aware of while handling sensitive data, including financial or medical records. Businesses and governments can create thorough profiles of individuals using big data, which can then be utilized for targeted advertising, credit scoring, and predictive

policing. A decline in privacy, social sorting, and discrimination are all potential consequences of these practices. To lessen these risks, strict regulations controlling data use, open data collection and processing, and robust data governance frameworks are required.

6.4 Guidelines for Emerging Technologies in Ethics

Complex ethical and governance issues are brought up by emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), gene editing, and quantum computing. Human well-being must be prioritized, justice and fairness must be promoted, accountability and transparency must be fostered, and strong governance structures must be established in order to guarantee that these technologies are developed and used responsibly.

Furthermore, ethical principles ought to support data reduction, which guarantees that only the bare minimum of data is collected and processed. User consent is a crucial element of data privacy. Individuals should have control over their data and be able to make informed choices about how to use it. This necessitates obtaining users' express consent prior to data collection and providing them with the option to opt-out or erase their data. Furthermore, ethical standards must encourage the development of privacy-preserving technologies, such as federated learning and differential privacy, that allow data analysis without endangering individual privacy.

7 Techniques for Raising Public Knowledge and Fostering Confidence in Data Privacy

Organizations should prioritize openness, proactive communication, and giving consumers control over their data in order to raise public knowledge and foster trust in data privacy. This entails making privacy policies easier to understand, providing explicit consent procedures, and informing users about data gathering methods.

7.1 Data Privacy Education Initiatives

The goal of data privacy education programs in the education sector is to protect sensitive student data by putting strong data access controls in place, protecting networks and devices, teaching staff and students about data privacy, and creating explicit policies and procedures. These programs seek to guarantee that educational establishments adhere to data protection laws and rules, such as COPPA and FERPA, which regulate the gathering, handling, and safeguarding of student information. These programs may ensure that all members of the public are aware of data privacy and capable of protecting their personal information by means of tailored educational campaigns targeted at different age groups and demographics.

7.2 Building Credibility with Ethical Data Practices

Prioritizing openness, security, and user control in the collection, use, and protection of data is essential to establishing confidence with ethical data practices. Organizations may build trust with their partners and consumers, reduce risks, and obtain a competitive edge by putting strong data governance policies into place, training staff, and carrying out frequent audits. Ethical data practices also entail a dedication to justice and non-discrimination to guarantee that data analytics and AI systems do not exacerbate stereotypes or harm disadvantaged people.

7.3 Measures for Transparency in Data Processing

Transparency in data processing means being open and clear about how data is collected, used, stored, and shared. It involves providing individuals with understandable information about data processing activities, including automated decision-making and the use of AI. Key measures include establishing clear data transparency policies, providing accessible and understandable privacy notices, and offering mechanisms for users to access, correct, and control their data. Organizations are required to tell individuals as quickly as possible when their data is compromised and to give them clear instructions on how to reduce any potential harm. Regular transparency reports that incorporate data requests from governments and other third parties may help to further build trust by showcasing a dedication to protecting user privacy.

7.4 Techniques for Communicating Privacy Awareness

To increase public awareness of data privacy, effective communication strategies are required. Businesses should use a range of media, including blogs, webinars, email newsletters, and social media, to reach different audiences. Clear and consistent messaging on data privacy policies and processes may help to reinforce the need of privacy protection. Messages that are tailored to the individual can boost interest. Customizing messaging to address particular customer concerns, like how their data is protected in a particular service or product, can help make privacy information more relevant and understandable. Using interactive resources like tutorials and quizzes can also make learning about data privacy more engaging and remembered.

7.5 Participation of the Community and Joint Initiatives

Addressing local problems and attaining sustainable development require community involvement and teamwork. To identify issues, create solutions, and carry out initiatives that benefit the community as a whole, they entail collaborating with individuals, groups, and other stakeholders. With an emphasis on empowerment, inclusivity, and shared accountability, this strategy produces more lasting and successful results.

8 Conclusion

This study highlights how important it is to approach data privacy issues in the digital age from a variety of angles. It became clear from examining consequentialism, virtue ethics, and deontology that integrating these perspectives can result in a just framework for protecting personal information. Although the analysis of existing data privacy laws, such the CCPA and GDPR, highlighted their benefits in guaranteeing data security, it also pointed out areas that need enhancement to optimize their efficacy. Emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), big data analytics, and the Internet of Things present serious privacy challenges, including data snooping, profiling, and algorithmic discrimination. Best practices and stringent ethical standards are needed to reduce the privacy implications of these technologies. Examining these dangers gave important insights into how difficult it is to protect data in a time of fast technological development. Ultimately, this comprehensive approach to data privacy highlights the need for constant improvement and adaptation. As technology advances, so too should our approaches to protecting personal information. By addressing emerging technological risks, enforcing stringent regulations, addressing ethical issues, and increasing public awareness, we can create a secure and private digital world. The results of this study lay the groundwork for further investigation and the creation of regulations meant to protect data privacy in

the digital era.

References:

- Al-Harathi, M., Al-Raisi, A., & Al-Humairi, A. (2023). Balancing Privacy and Security: Navigating the Complexities of Digital Privacy in the Modern World. *Journal of Global Research in Computer Sciences*, 14(2), 19–28. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2229-371X.14.2.0010>
- Becker, M. (2019). Privacy in the digital age: Comparing and contrasting individual versus social approaches towards privacy. *Ethics and Information Technology*, 21(4), 307–317. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10676-019-09508-z>
- Deep, A. (2023). Legal Ethics in Technology: Navigating the Ethical Landscape in the Digital Age. *EDU Journal of International Affairs and Research*, 2(4), 5–10.
- Dutta, S., Bhungia, D., & Das, S. K. (2024a). Byte Guardians: Librarians in The Digital Divide Era-- Challenges, strategies and Empowerment. *Librarian*, 27(1 & 2), 123–128.
- Ijaiya, H. (2024). Balancing Data Privacy and Technology Advancements: Navigating Ethical Challenges and Shaping Policy Solutions. *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews*, 5(11), 8118–8130. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijbsa.2020070101>
- Singh, S. (2024). Exploring the ethics of data privacy in the Digital age. *Darpan International Research Analysis*, 12(3), 216–227. <https://doi.org/10.36676/dira.v12.i3.69>
- Rascão, J. P. (2020). Freedom of expression, privacy, and ethical and social responsibility in democracy in the Digital age. *International Journal of Business Strategy and Automation*, 1(3), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijbsa.2020070101>

First-Year Students' Perspectives on Library Use: A Survey-Based Study

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Abstract: *This study examines the perspectives, habits, and expectations of first-year students regarding library usage at Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya, an undergraduate college under the West Bengal State University for the academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. The transition from school to college presents students with new academic challenges, and the library often becomes a pivotal support resource. This study gathers information about students' past experiences with school and public libraries, present library use patterns, and future expectations by surveying them during the initial library registration process. A survey based study was carried out with a structured questionnaire consisting of 15 questions to 270 students across both academic years. Analysis of the data shows that people strongly value library resources, prefer print and digital versions, and have high expectations for study spaces, computer and internet access, and support systems. The study offers actionable recommendations to improve library services and user engagement. The results emphasize how academic libraries must change to meet students' changing information needs.*

Keywords: Library Use, Undergraduate Students

1 Introduction

An essential component of higher education is the academic library, which gives students access to resources, guidance, and a supportive learning environment. This facility frequently marks a substantial change for first-year students compared to their prior experiences in public libraries or schools. Developing responsive and efficient library services requires an understanding of how new college students perceive and expect to use the library. Many of the students at Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya, a college affiliated with West Bengal State University, come from a variety of socioeconomic and educational backgrounds. The purpose of this study was to investigate first-year students' expectations and experiences with libraries as they begin their college careers. By conducting the survey during the mandatory library card registration process, the study ensures inclusivity and relevance. The research captures students' library usage habits formed during their school days, their exposure to public libraries, and their aspirations from the college library. These

insights help college librarians as well as administrators align services with student needs, promoting greater utilization and academic success.

2 Review of Literature

The results of a seven-year longitudinal survey that was carried out between 2016 and 2022 and looked at first-year undergraduate students in the information management program's adoption of e-books are presented in the study by Nahotko & Deja (2004). According to the survey, students have long considered e-books to be an essential tool for acquiring exploratory knowledge, especially in the social sciences. Bloom, Eller, Hall, Lang, and Sample's study from 2025 looks into the connection between students' academic achievement and how often they use the library. The results show that more library visits lead to better academic performance, underscoring the library's critical function as a place where students can succeed. The purpose of the study conducted by Adetayo, Asiru, and Oladokun (2024) is to look into the factors that affect university students' decision not to enroll in LIS programs. 537 students were given a survey to gauge their views on librarians, the value of university libraries, and the reasons they did not pursue library and information science studies. The findings show that people have very favorable views of librarians as informed, personable experts who get along well with others.

Liu's (2025) current scientific article's primary goal is to empirically examine how students' utilization of library resources affects their information literacy abilities. The study focuses on the processes of choosing and processing information as well as critical thinking abilities. The article by Hodge (2022) explains the usefulness of academic capital and library anxiety as theoretical frameworks to inform future research on first-generation students and first-year students, respectively, and critiques the current state of the literature on first-year first-generation students. It also identifies important areas for additional study. In their study, Bodhinayaka, Jamali, Hider, and Carroll (2025) investigated how pre-admission students in Sri Lanka acquire their prior knowledge about academic libraries based on their contacts with different information sources and personal library experiences. Through an interpretive perspective and Charmaz's constructivist grounded theory methodology, the study took a qualitative approach.

3 Scope and Coverage of the Study

This study focuses exclusively on first-year undergraduate students of Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya during the academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. It includes students from all streams, such as science, arts and commerce and departments who visited the college library to register for a library card. The scope is limited to their past experiences with libraries (school or public libraries), current usage habits, preferred resource formats, and expectations from the college library. The findings are based on the survey conducted during the months of August to December in each academic year. The study is limited to students of one college library only.

4 Objectives of the Study

- To assess first-year students' prior experience with school and public libraries.
- To analyze current library usage habits and preferences.
- To identify students' expectations from the college library.
- To offer actionable recommendations to improve academic library services.

5 Methodology

5.1 Research Design: A quantitative, descriptive research design was used for this study and data was collected through a structured questionnaire administered in person during library card registration of first year students.

5.2 Population and Sample: The population consisted of all first-year students who came to the library for new library card registration during the academic years 2023-2024 and 2024-2025. A total of 270 students participated (140 from 2023-2024 and 130 from 2024-2025) and the students were selected via convenience sampling.

5.3 Data Collection Tool: A structured questionnaire with 15 questions was developed. The questionnaire was divided into four sections: demographic information, past library experience, current usage habits, and future expectations.

5.4 Data Analysis: Data was analyzed and interpreted using basic statistical techniques and represented using tables and charts.

6 Data Analysis and Interpretation

6.1 Demographic Information

Figure 1: Demographic Information of Students

From figure 1 it is shown that a total of 134 male and 136 female students have been selected for this study during two academic sessions. Most of these students came from Arts stream. From the college admission data it is found that most of the students take their admission into Arts and Humanities stream and a very few students take admission in the other two streams.

6.2 Past library use behaviour of students

Figure 2: Past Library Use Behaviour of Students

Figure 3: Frequency of Library Use

Total number of users who have past experience with school and/or public library use is 158, that is 58% and most of them are users of the school library. Total 18 of the 270 students have experience with public libraries that is 7 percent of total population. From the figure 2 it is also found that students of science stream have more familiarities with libraries. During the verbal communication most of them respond that they do not have any knowledge about public libraries. They used the school library sometimes only for their academic needs.

Figure 3 shows that frequency of library use is also not on a regular basis. Students used the school as well as the public libraries occasionally.

6.3 Current usage habits

Table 1: Current usage habits (N=158)

Main purpose of library visits	No. of students
Reading textbooks or reference books	158
Borrowing books	137
Internet access	3
Reading newspapers, magazines, etc.	11

The table 1 shows that almost all students with prior library experience reported using it for reading textbooks and reference books. This demonstrates a strong academic orientation in their library usage habits, with a focus on syllabus-oriented materials and supplementary academic content. Only a small number of students had used internet services within their past library experiences. Similarly, reading newspapers or magazines was also not a common activity among them. This suggests a potential gap in exposure to broader learning materials and a dependence on print books over other formats.

6.4. Expectations from the College Library

Table 2: Expectations from the college library (N=270)

Facilities / Services	Yes	No	May be
Textbooks	262	6	2
Reference books	193	48	29
Journals and magazines	236	5	29
Digital resources (e-books, e-journals, online databases)	177	53	40
Career Counselling Books/Magazines	242	15	13
Computers for study/academic use	249	5	16
Internet access	214	42	14
Wi-Fi Facility	252	0	18
Orientation sessions or user training workshops	155	27	88
Group study rooms/space	171	27	72
Quiet reading areas	164	63	43
Printing and photocopying services	246	12	12
Assistance from library staff (help finding resources, research help)	188	34	48

From the above table it is revealed that the students have high demand for core academic resources. The vast majority of students expressed an obvious need for textbooks as well as reference books. They also clearly indicate that they need print journals and magazines. Students in addition mentioned their expectations about digital resources. Approximately 66% of students stated that they expected access to digital academic contents such as e-books, online journals, and databases. This highlights a growing shift toward hybrid learning preferences that combine print and digital formats. Students of today's generation are also more aware about their career. The study revealed that about 90 percent of students expect availability and access to the resources related directly to their career development. Technological infrastructure is a basic need for today's education. Majority of students anticipated the availability of computers and reliable internet or Wi-Fi services in the library.

Students also demand for purposeful study spaces. A lot of respondents emphasized the importance of group discussion rooms and quiet study areas. Students expressed a desire for flexible environments that support both collaborative and individual learning styles. A moderate number of students selected "Maybe" when asked about library orientation or training sessions, reflecting unfamiliarity with such offerings. This suggests an opportunity to meet the students and share the information about the services or facilities that a college can provide. Unfamiliarity leading to uncertainty, that's why around 20–25% of students chose "Maybe" for services like access to databases or digital tools, indicating they may not have used such resources previously. This group requires targeted awareness and training to fully engage with library services.

In spite of varying levels of awareness, the overall response indicates that first-year students recognize the library as a vital academic resource. There is a clear willingness among the majority to explore and use multiple services provided by the library.

7 Findings and Conclusion

This survey-based study examines first-year students' perceptions and finds both consistency and change in their expectations and behaviors toward library use. According to the results, the majority of students who previously used school or public libraries did so mainly to study reference materials and textbooks. A significant 90% also utilized borrowing facilities, reflecting a strong academic motivation behind library visits.

However, there was a notably low level of participation with non-academic reading materials and digital tools. Just a small percentage of students said they read newspapers, used the internet, or read general interest periodicals. This suggests a narrow focus in prior library use, likely shaped by limited infrastructure and digital access in earlier library settings.

The results of the study reveal that although school libraries are commonly available, students' usage of these facilities varies significantly, often depending on the resources and assistance offered. Many students had access to school libraries, but the inconsistency in how frequently and effectively they were used indicates a lack of structured engagement or participation. However, just a small percentage of students had previously used public libraries, indicating that they were either underutilized or had accessibility or outreach problems.

However, students expressed a noticeable excitement for using academic libraries after they started college. When they are informed about the availability of contemporary amenities like internet connectivity, digital access points, and well-organized study spaces, their optimistic attitude becomes even more obvious. There is a significant desire to investigate services that extend beyond

conventional books, indicating a readiness to move toward more dynamic and technologically assisted teaching methods.

Students' expectations from the college library are clearly high. They prioritize improved infrastructure, access to up-to-date study aids, and organized spaces helpful to focused learning. Additionally, their willingness to participate in library orientation programs highlights a proactive approach toward gaining familiarity with the library environment. This willingness shows that students not only appreciate the library as a resource but are also eager to enhance their understanding of how to navigate and utilize it effectively for academic growth.

In general, the study shows that students are going through a transitional stage during which they keep their current habits while remaining open to adopting new services and resources. Libraries need to help with this change by providing a variety of services, enhancing accessibility, and raising awareness through training sessions and orientations. By doing this, college libraries can develop into welcoming environments that accommodate a greater range of learning styles and academic requirements.

8 Recommendations

- Conduct regular orientation sessions and library tours for new students.
- Increase digital content offerings, including e-books and academic databases. Introduce training programs to familiarize students with digital resources, including e-books, academic databases, and online journals.
- Ensure reliable internet access and adequate computer terminals within the library to support digital learning.
- Encourage students to engage with newspapers, magazines, and general knowledge resources in addition to textbooks.
- Create more individual and group study spaces.
- Establish a feedback mechanism to continually assess student needs and improve services accordingly.
- Collaborate with faculty to integrate library use into curriculum assignments.

These steps will not only align the library's offerings with student expectations but also empower learners by bridging the gap between traditional and modern information access.

Bibliographical References:

Adetayo, Adebawale Jeremy, Asiru, Mufutau Ayobami & Oladokun, Bolaji David. (2024). Student perceptions of libraries and librarians: Factors in non-enrollment in LIS programs. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(5). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102935>.

Bloom, Myra, Eller, Daniel, Mark, Hall, Andrew & Sample, Angela. (2025). The impact of library visits on undergraduate student GPA: The vital role of the library as a contributor to student success. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 51(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2025.103040>.

- Bodhinayaka, Dilini, Jamali, Hamid R., Hider, Philip & Carroll, Mary. (2025). Pre-admission undergraduate students' prior understanding of academic libraries in Sri Lanka. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 51(3). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2025.103029>.
- Hodge, Megan L. (2022). First-generation students and the first-year transition: State of the literature and implications for library researchers. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 48(4). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2022.102554>.
- Liu, Man. (2025). Information Literacy Formation through the Use of Library Resources: Thinking, Selection, and Information Processing Skills of Students. *Thinking Skills and Creativity*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsc.2025.101789>.
- Nahotko, Marek & Deja, Marek. (2024). E-book acceptance by first-year undergraduate students: A longitudinal examination and implications for library researchers. *The Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 50(2). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2024.102847>.

Webometric Evaluation of Central Government Ministries' Websites in India

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Abstract: *This study intends to measure visibility, performance and link quality of central government ministries' websites in India; for this purpose, the researchers have examined the concerned ministries' websites of India. To evaluate these websites the concept of webometrics has been adopted. The required data is collected by applying web-based survey and observation methods from all union government ministries' websites of India. Collected data has subsequently been analyzed and tabulated by using different webometric tools and techniques. The present study has analyzed domain system of the websites, the number of webpages and link pages and calculate the simple web impact factor, self-link web impact factor, external link web impact factor for the existing central government ministries' websites in India and rank the websites as per the WIF.*

Keywords: *Information Architecture, Website Information Architecture, Information Architecture Analysis, Information Architectural Components, Indian Government Ministries' Websites .*

1 Introduction

With the coming of Internet and Information and Communication Technology (ICT), it has gotten basic for each administration body to have a site. By having a site, an administration body can have most extreme effect over countless individuals utilizing least efforts and time. Consequently, it is fundamental for the administration to have their very own effective site. Aside from this, a site permits an administration body to unite all its data, regardless of whether its sub-bodies are put at topographically scattered spots. Subsequently, incorporation of ICT inside government bodies can realize advancement of government itself.

On the world stage it has been a tendency to grow the transparency of government, online public services development, as well as e-participation tools for citizens and business engagement in decision making. In this regard, it is urgent to develop substantial strategies to gauge the development in this area.

Governments over the world make data accessible through various channels to residents to make a dimension of straightforwardness, to speak to responsibility and to bring to the consideration of the overall population their accomplishments. Natives utilize this data to settle on choices in regards to the dimension of certainty and achievement of governments. Also, such data enables the residents to settle on decisions notwithstanding gaining them mindful of the ground made in various zones. Government data, for example, acts, strategies and plans are critical to natives. With the improvement of World Wide Web, governments can saddle the rich capability of the web, and reach to the residents.

The term webometrics is derived from two words “web” and “metrics”. The dictionary of science defines web as a hypermedia system that allows users to view and retrieve information from documents containing links. Metrics means Systems of measurement, particularly assessment of the usability and efficiency of electronic resources. Webometrics is a quantitative investigation of web-related phenomena. The webometric study could be applied to web with commercial search engines providing the raw data. It is concerned with measuring aspects of the web: websites, web pages, parts of web pages, words in web pages, etc.

2 Review of Related Literature

Six broad key parameters for the study of Indian Government Websites have been suggested by Chand and Ramesha; these are - identifier, information, usability, security, participation and services. Identifier is the concept which confirms the authenticity of websites and certifies the credibility which is very important from the user point of view to determine the accuracy and dependability. Information or content is the second major parameter which actually defines the key information that is being disseminated (Chand & Ramesha, 2017).

Abdulbasit Abdullah Mohammed Darem performed experiments to measure the effectiveness, efficiency and user satisfaction of e-government websites. His research process included usability testing through major usability evaluation criteria, constructing a web-based usability evaluation questionnaire and using a new framework to evaluate the e-government based on four constructs: sections, elements accessibility and speed. Finally he tried to find out how the website design influenced the effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction of e-government websites.

Wang, Bretschneider & Gant stated that, despite the importance of the evaluation of Web-based e-government services, especially the performance of government Web sites in facilitating public-government interaction, little research has been generated, with most web-based service evaluation focusing on the private sector. Web diagnostic tools have become a method of evaluation for general websites and e-Government websites (Brooks & Persaud, 2015).

Bhattacharya, Debjani worked on Service Quality of Government Websites in India and has remarked that user perceived service quality in the context of e-government, can be defined as the effectiveness of the web portals of government organizations. Usefulness and usability features of government portals can help citizens to participate in various public activities making the public administration effective, efficient, and transparent.

By searching the related literature of the concerned study, it has been observed that investigators examined usability of academic and government websites through usability testing by participation of user groups; many authors have analyzed government webpages through the evaluation of web-based e-government services, especially the performance of government web sites in facilitating public-government interaction. In this study, the researchers try to evaluate the central government ministries'

websites in India through webometric tools and techniques. Findings of this study may open the door to further studies of other new areas of the concerned field.

3 Objectives of the Study

The purpose of this research are:

- To find out the number of web pages, number of link pages, number of self-link pages, and external link pages of government ministries' websites of India;
- To examine the link quality of government websites of India
- To calculate the web impact factors of the websites of government of India;
- To identify and classify the domain of central government websites in India.

4 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The present study examines the websites of all 52 central government ministries of India. But it has been found that some of the ministries' websites were not supported to the identified SEO tool (i.e. <https://smallseotools.com/website-link-analyzer-tool/>). This tool supported 36 websites which were considered for analysis.

5 Methodology of the Study

Alike the journal/article citation mechanism, Importance of web pages or websites can be judged with the help of links (especially text links) and their analysis.

The required data is collected by applying web-based survey and observation methods from all union government ministries' websites of India. Collected data has subsequently been analyzed and tabulated by using different webometric tools and techniques. The following tools were used for this study:-

Google: Google search engine was used to collect total number of webpages from each of the websites; the identified search keyword was, site:url of the website for example, site: <https://www.indiaculture.nic.in/>

Website Link Analyzer: <https://smallseotools.com/website-link-analyzer-tool/> retrieves simple links, self or internal links and external links of each government ministries' website under investigation. The required data were collected during 17th-23rd January 2022. Each ministry website was searched during 16th – 17th February, 2022 in the website <http://checkpagerank.net/index.php> for collecting Page rank and Alexa rank of the websites under study.

6 Calculation of Web Impact Factor (WIF):

Web impact factor is the method for measuring the quality of websites according to their existing links. The calculation of WIF requires number of webpages and number of links to a website. The concerned study adopts three types of WIFs, which are formulated below:-

$$\text{Simple-WIF} = \frac{\text{No of Linked Pages}}{\text{No of webpages – indexed by the search engine Google}}$$

No of Self-Linked Pages

Self Link-WIF = $\frac{\text{No of Self-Linked Pages}}{\text{No of webpages – indexed by the search engine Google}}$

No of External Linked Pages

External Link-WIF = $\frac{\text{No of External Linked Pages}}{\text{No of webpages – indexed by the search engine Google}}$

7 Central Government Ministries' Websites of India

In the Government of India directory there are listing of 52 ministries. These are the websites through which Government of India facilitates the dissemination of information to citizens with many of these websites exists since long. Studying these websites will allow people to understand how the information dissemination is being facilitated. This is a high requirement to know the web presence of central government in general and Indian Central government in particular. It is also required to quantify the web impact through various WIFs using appropriate webometric indicators in order to enhance its efficiency through optimizing web content, analysis and re-designing. Table 1 shows the list of selected central government official websites of India along with their website addresses or URLs.

Table 1: List of Selected Central Government Ministries' Websites of India

Sr. No.	Central Government Ministries	Website Address
1	Ministry of Ayush	https://main.ayush.gov.in/
2	Ministry of Civil Aviation	https://www.civilaviation.gov.in/
3	Ministry of Coal	https://coal.gov.in/
4	Ministry of Corporate Affairs	https://www.mca.gov.in/content/mca/global/en/home.html
5	Ministry of Culture	https://www.indiaculture.nic.in/
6	Ministry of Defence	https://www.mod.gov.in/
7	Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region	https://mdoner.gov.in/#
8	Ministry of Earth Sciences	https://moes.gov.in/
9	Ministry of Education	https://www.education.gov.in/en
10	Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology	http://meity.gov.in/
11	Ministry of Finance	https://www.finmin.nic.in/
12	Ministry of Food Processing Industries	https://www.mofpi.gov.in/

Sr. No.	Central Government Ministries	Website Address
13	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	https://main.mohfw.gov.in/
14	Ministry of Heavy Industries	https://heavyindustries.gov.in/
15	Ministry of Home Affairs	https://www.mha.gov.in/
16	Ministry of Labour and Employment	https://labour.gov.in/
17	Ministry of Law and Justice	https://lawmin.gov.in/
18	Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises	https://www.msme.gov.in/
19	Ministry of Mines	https://mines.gov.in/
20	Ministry of Minority Affairs	http://minorityaffairs.gov.in/
21	Ministry of New and Renewable Energy	https://mnre.gov.in/
22	Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs	https://mpa.nic.in/
23	Ministry of Personnel, Public Grievances & Pensions	https://persmin.gov.in/
24	Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas	https://mopng.gov.in/en
25	Ministry of Ports Shipping and Waterways	https://shipmin.gov.in/
26	Ministry of Power	https://powermin.gov.in/
27	Ministry of Railways	https://indianrailways.gov.in/
28	Ministry of Rural Development	https://rural.nic.in/
29	Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship	https://www.msde.gov.in/
30	Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation	https://mospi.gov.in/
31	Ministry of Steel	https://steel.gov.in/
32	Ministry of Textiles	http://ministryoftextiles.gov.in/
33	Ministry of Tourism	https://tourism.gov.in/
34	Ministry of Tribal Affairs	https://tribal.gov.in/
35	Ministry of Women & Child Development	https://wcd.nic.in/
36	Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports	https://yas.gov.in/

8 Observation and Data Analysis

8.1 Domain wise distribution of ministries' websites: a domain name contains the website name and the domain name extension.

Table 2: Domain Extensions possessed by ministries' websites

Domain Name	No. of Government Ministries	Percentage
.in	36	100

Table 2 shows the domain distribution of government ministries' websites in India. It identifies that only one type of domain extension was observed from the study. It has been observed that all the selected websites have .in extension.

8.2 Simple Web Impact Factor of Ministries' Websites:

The Simple Web Impact Factor has been shown in Table 3. It exhibits link pages of ministries websites and their rank distribution according to their simple Web Impact Factor. Dividing the number of link pages (B) by the number of web pages (A), the score of simple WIF (B/A) of each website is found.

Table 3: Simple Web Impact Factor of Ministries' Websites

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries Websites	No. of Web Pages (A)	No. of Link Pages (B)	Simple WIF (B/A)	Rank by Simple WIF
1	Ministry of Corporate Affairs	1	312	312	1
2	Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises	118	182	1.542	2
3	Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas	266	340	1.278	3
4	Ministry of Ayush	721	164	0.227	4
5	Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship	998	181	0.181	5
6	Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs	1270	171	0.134	6
7	Ministry of New and Renewable Energy	1200	141	0.117	7
8	Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region	2340	227	0.09	8
9	Ministry of Textiles	1460	142	0.097	8
10	Ministry of Food Processing Industries	3330	320	0.096	9
11	Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports	1180	113	0.095	10

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries Websites	No. of Web Pages (A)	No. of Link Pages (B)	Simple WIF (B/A)	Rank by Simple WIF
12	Ministry of Law and Justice	622	59	0.094	11
13	Ministry of Heavy Industries	1880	176	0.093	12
14	Ministry of Mines	4560	363	0.079	13
15	Ministry of Ports Shipping and Waterways	3130	149	0.047	14
16	Ministry of Tourism	3870	171	0.044	15
17	Ministry of Coal	4460	196	0.043	16
18	Ministry of Steel	4500	174	0.038	17
19	Ministry of Defence	3450	124	0.035	18
20	Ministry of Power	4600	152	0.033	19
21	Ministry of Finance	2390	79	0.033	19
22	Ministry of Civil Aviation	14700	367	0.024	20
23	Ministry of Personnel, Public Grievances & Pensions	1690	41	0.024	20
24	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	9620	224	0.023	21
25	Ministry of Culture	12300	236	0.019	22
26	Ministry of Rural Development	10200	176	0.017	23
27	Ministry of Women & Child Development	11200	152	0.013	24
28	Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology	9760	121	0.012	25
29	Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation	23100	232	0.010	26
30	Ministry of Education	35400	342	0.009	27
31	Ministry of Labour and Employment	26400	250	0.009	27

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries Websites	No. of Web Pages (A)	No. of Link Pages (B)	Simple WIF (B/A)	Rank by Simple WIF
32	Ministry of Home Affairs	22800	222	0.009	27
33	Ministry of Minority Affairs	17700	153	0.008	28
34	Ministry of Tribal Affairs	25300	174	0.006	29
35	Ministry of Earth Sciences	308000	173	0.00056	30
36	Ministry of Railways	911000	141	0.00015	31

The above Table 3 demonstrates that Ministry of Corporate Affairs stands at first position with 312 link pages, only 1 web page and 312 Simple WIF. Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises has taken second place with 182 link pages, 118 web pages and 1.542 Simple WIF. Third position has been occupied by Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas with 1.278 Simple WIF. Ministry of Ayush and Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship take fourth and fifth position with 0.227 and 0.181 Simple WIF respectively. Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region and Ministry of Textiles stand eighth position with 0.097 Simple WIF. In terms of popularity or number of links, the ministries like Ministry of Food Processing Industries, Ministry of Mines, Ministry of Civil Aviation and Ministry of Education carry more credit than other ministries though their impact factors are not very high. Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports occupies tenth rank with 0.095 Simple WIF. Ministry of Power and Ministry of Finance stand nineteenth position with 0.033 Simple WIF. Ministry of Education, Ministry of Labour and Employment and Ministry of Home Affairs occupy same rank (i.e. twenty-seventh) with 0.009 Simple WIF. The last rank (thirty-first) has been occupied by Ministry of Railways with 0.00015 Simple WIF though it has maximum number of web pages in comparison with other websites.

8.3 External link Web Impact Factor of ministries' websites:

Table 4 shows External Link WIF of ministries' websites in India. Here, A and C indicate number of web pages and number of External linked web pages respectively in the websites. Dividing the number of External linked web pages (C) by the number of web pages (A), the score of External Link WIF (C/A) of each website is found.

Table 4: External link Web Impact Factor of Ministries' Websites

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	No of web Pages (A)	No of External Linked Web Pages (C)	External Link WIF (C/A)	Rank by External Link WIF
1	Ministry of Corporate Affairs	1	79	79	1
2	Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises	118	64	0.542	2

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	No of web Pages (A)	No of External Linked Web Pages (C)	External Link WIF (C/A)	Rank by External Link WIF
3	Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas	266	47	0.176	3
4	Ministry of Ayush	721	48	0.066	4
5	Ministry of New and Renewable Energy	1200	50	0.041	5
6	Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports	1180	45	0.038	6
7	Ministry of Law and Justice	622	22	0.035	7
8	Ministry of Textiles	1460	50	0.034	8
9	Ministry of Heavy Industries	1880	61	0.032	9
10	Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship	998	30	0.030	10
11	Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs	1270	39	0.030	10
12	Ministry of Food Processing Industries	3330	79	0.023	11
13	Ministry of Finance	2390	51	0.021	12
14	Ministry of Personnel, Public Grievances & Pensions	1690	25	0.014	13
15	Ministry of Tourism	3870	52	0.013	14
16	Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region	2340	29	0.012	15
17	Ministry of Mines	4560	52	0.011	16
18	Ministry of Defence	3450	38	0.011	16
19	Ministry of Civil Aviation	14700	152	0.010	17
20	Ministry of Steel	4500	41	0.009	18

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	No of web Pages (A)	No of External Linked Web Pages (C)	External Link WIF (C/A)	Rank by External Link WIF
21	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	9620	74	0.007	19
22	Ministry of Power	4600	36	0.007	19
23	Ministry of Coal	4460	35	0.007	19
24	Ministry of Culture	12300	83	0.006	20
25	Ministry of Ports Shipping and Waterways	3130	20	0.006	20
26	Ministry of Education	35400	201	0.005	21
27	Ministry of Women & Child Development	11200	65	0.005	21
28	Ministry of Rural Development	10200	48	0.004	22
29	Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology	9760	44	0.004	22
30	Ministry of Tribal Affairs	25300	69	0.002	23
31	Ministry of Home Affairs	22800	60	0.002	23
32	Ministry of Minority Affairs	17700	46	0.002	23
33	Ministry of Labour and Employment	26400	47	0.001	24
34	Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation	23100	37	0.001	24
35	Ministry of Earth Sciences	308000	38	0.00012	25
36	Ministry of Railways	911000	78	0.000085	26

Table 4 illustrates that Ministry of Corporate Affairs occupies first position with 79 external link pages, 1 web page and 79 External Link WIF. Second position has been taken by Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises with 64 external link pages, 118 web pages and 0.542 External Link WIF. Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas and Ministry of Ayush stand third and fourth position with 0.176 and 0.066 External Link WIF respectively. Fifth rank is occupied by Ministry of New and

Renewable Energy with 0.041 External Link WIF. Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship and Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs place tenth rank with 0.030 External Link WIF. Ministry of Tourism stands fourteenth position with 0.013 External Link WIF. Ministry of Mines and Ministry of Defence occupy same rank (i.e. sixteenth) with 0.011 External Link WIF. Nineteenth position has been occupied by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Ministry of Power and Ministry of Coal. Ministry of Civil Aviation is placed seventeenth position with 152 external link pages, 14700 web pages and 0.010 External Link WIF. Ministry of Education stands twenty-first position with 0.005 External Link WIF, though it carries the highest number of external link pages (i.e. 201) and also contains a good number of webpages i.e. 35400. Ministry of Railways contain highest number of web pages but it stands at last rank with 0.000085 External Link WIF.

8.4 Self link Web Impact Factor of ministries' websites

Table 5 exhibits Self link WIF of ministries' websites in India. In this table, A specifies number of web pages and D indicates number of Self linked web pages in the websites. Dividing the number of Self linked web pages (D) by the number of web pages (A), the score of Self Link WIF (D/A) of each website is found. Websites are ranked according to their Self Link WIFs.

Table 5: Self link Web Impact Factor of Ministries' Websites

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	No. of Web Pages (A)	No. of Self linked Web Pages (D)	Self-Link WIF (D/A)	Rank by Self Link WIF
1	Ministry of Corporate Affairs	1	233	233	1
2	Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas	266	293	1.101	2
3	Ministry of Micro Small and Medium Enterprises	118	118	1	3
4	Ministry of Ayush	721	116	0.160	4
5	Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship	998	151	0.151	5
6	Ministry of Parliamentary Affairs	1270	132	0.103	6
7	Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region	2340	198	0.084	7
8	Ministry of New and Renewable Energy	1200	91	0.075	8
9	Ministry of Food Processing Industries	3330	241	0.072	9

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	No. of Web Pages (A)	No. of Self linked Web Pages (D)	Self-Link WIF (D/A)	Rank by Self Link WIF
10	Ministry of Mines	4560	311	0.068	10
11	Ministry of Textiles	1460	92	0.063	11
12	Ministry of Heavy Industries	1880	115	0.061	12
13	Ministry of Law and Justice	622	37	0.059	13
14	Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports	1180	68	0.057	14
15	Ministry of Ports Shipping and Waterways	3130	129	0.041	15
16	Ministry of Coal	4460	161	0.036	16
17	Ministry of Tourism	3870	119	0.030	17
18	Ministry of Steel	4500	133	0.029	18
19	Ministry of Power	4600	116	0.025	19
20	Ministry of Defence	3450	86	0.024	20
21	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	9620	150	0.015	21
22	Ministry of Civil Aviation	14700	215	0.014	22
23	Ministry of Culture	12300	153	0.012	23
24	Ministry of Rural Development	10200	128	0.012	23
25	Ministry of Finance	2390	28	0.011	24
26	Ministry of Personnel, Public Grievances & Pensions	1690	16	0.009	25
27	Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation	23100	195	0.008	26
28	Ministry of Labour and Employment	26400	203	0.007	27

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	No. of Web Pages (A)	No. of Self linked Web Pages (D)	Self-Link WIF (D/A)	Rank by Self Link WIF
29	Ministry of Home Affairs	22800	162	0.007	27
30	Ministry of Women & Child Development	11200	87	0.007	27
31	Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology	9760	77	0.007	27
32	Ministry of Minority Affairs	17700	107	0.006	28
33	Ministry of Tribal Affairs	25300	105	0.004	29
34	Ministry of Education	35400	141	0.003	30
35	Ministry of Earth Sciences	308000	135	0.00043	31
36	Ministry of Railways	911000	63	0.000069	32

Table 5 denotes that Ministry of Corporate Affairs has taken first position with 233 self link pages, 1 web page and 233 Self Link WIF. Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas occupies second place with 293 Self link pages, 266 web pages and 1.101 Self Link WIF. Ministry of Ayush and Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship stand fourth and fifth position with 0.160 and 0.151 Self Link WIFs respectively. Ministry of Mines rank tenth position with 311 Self link pages, 4560 web pages and 0.068 Self Link WIF. This ministry contains highest number (i.e. 311) of Self link pages in comparison with other websites. Sixteenth rank has been taken by Ministry of Coal with 0.036 Self Link WIF. Ministry of Culture and Ministry of Rural Development occupy twenty-third position with 0.012 Self Link WIF. Ministry of Labour and Employment, Ministry of Home Affairs, Ministry of Women & Child Development and Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology occupy same rank (i.e. twenty-seventh) with 0.007 Self Link WIF. Ministry of Railways again has taken last position with 0.000069 score.

8.5 Page rank and Alexa rank of ministries' websites: The algorithm Page Rank is used by Google in their search engine results to rank webpages of different websites. The importance of website pages can be measured through this algorithm.

Alexa Rank is a worldwide ranking framework that utilizes web traffic information to list the most well-known sites. It is determined by looking at the estimated average of daily unique visitors and number of site hits for a given site throughout the course of recent months. The lower Alexa rank suggests the greater popularity of the site. In this study the Page rank and Alexa rank of different ministries' websites have been retrieved from <http://checkpagerank.net/index.php> Dated: February, 16th and 17th, 2022.

Table 6: Page rank and Alexa rank of Ministries' Websites

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	Page Rank	Alexa Rank
1	Ministry of Railways	7	14041
2	Ministry of Finance	6	223962
3	Ministry of Tourism	6	150428
4	Ministry of Labour and Employment	6	40794
5	Ministry of Home Affairs	6	30320
6	Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology	6	56625
7	Ministry of Health and Family Welfare	6	7952
8	Ministry of Women and Child Development	6	74242
9	Ministry of Corporate Affairs	6	3225
10	Ministry of Defence	5	108660
11	Ministry of Culture	5	211333
12	Ministry of Ayush	5	108169
13	Ministry of Education	5	46378
14	Ministry of Power	5	211184
15	Ministry of Minority Affairs	5	153116
16	Ministry of Rural Development	5	276305
17	Ministry of Civil Aviation	5	68623
18	Ministry of New and Renewable Energy	5	166725
19	Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation	5	248946
20	Ministry of Development of North Eastern Region	5	1288089
21	Ministry of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises	5	28254
22	Ministry of Mines	4	722012
23	Ministry of Steel	4	912904
24	Ministry of Coal	4	1431435
25	Ministry of parliamentary Affairs	4	2150363
26	Ministry of Tribal Affairs	4	484639
27	Ministry of Earth Sciences	4	680710

Sr. No.	Name of Ministries' Websites	Page Rank	Alexa Rank
28	Ministry of Law and Justice	4	512645
29	Ministry of Skill Development and Entrepreneurship	4	231556
30	Ministry of Ports Shipping and Waterways	4	275809
31	Ministry of Personnel, Public Grievances & Pensions	4	320215
32	Ministry of Textiles	3	1995124
33	Ministry of Heavy Industries	3	334364
34	Ministry of Food Processing Industries	3	184128
35	Ministry of Petroleum and Natural Gas	3	410769
36	Ministry of Youth Affairs and Sports	2	3527409

Table 6 shows the ranking position of the selected ministries' websites. According to Page rank the first place has been occupied by Ministry of Railways with the score 7.0. The first position (3225) has been taken by Ministry of Corporate Affairs as per Alexa rank.

9 Findings

The major findings of the study are mentioned below:-

- ❖ It has been observed from the study that all the selected ministries' websites have only one type of domain extension (i.e. .in).
- ❖ Out of 36 ministries' websites the website of Ministry of Corporate Affairs occupy first position as per the scores of Simple WIF (312), External Link WIF (79) and Self Link WIF (233).
- ❖ The ministries like Ministry of Food Processing Industries, Ministry of Mines, Ministry of Civil Aviation and Ministry of Education have good number of simple link pages than other ministries even though their impact factors are not very high; they occupied 9th, 13th, 20th and 27th rank respectively.
- ❖ It is evident from the study that Ministry of Corporate Affairs occupies first position with 79 external link pages, 1 web page and 79 External Link WIF.
- ❖ Ministry of Education stands twenty-first position with 0.005 External Link WIF, though it carries the highest number of external link pages (i.e. 201) and also contains a good number of webpages i.e. 35400.
- ❖ The present study clears out that Ministry of Mines contains highest number (i.e. 311) of Self link pages in comparison with other websites.
- ❖ The results of the study indicate that Ministry of Railways contain highest number of web pages (i.e. 911000) but it always stands at last rank according to the scores of Simple WIF, External Link WIF and Self Link WIF.

- ❖ The study also indicates that Ministry of Railways stand at first position with Page rank 7; and Ministry of Corporate Affairs occupy first place with Alexa rank 3225.

10 Conclusion

In this study Web Impact Factor (WIF) has been broadly utilized as webometric indicator to pass judgement on the nature of sites. The WIF is a significant tool for site assessment, however it should be used cautiously. The WIF of a website is unsteady since certain website admins erase old inlinks to numerous sites consistently, while others connect to new ones. The present study ideally gives a fair thought and data about the websites of central government ministries in India; it also shows the visibility, performance and link quality of the concerned ministries of India. The findings of this study will help to diagnose the problem and lead us to find the right direction for further research in the field of webometric evaluation of websites.

References:

- Abdulbasit Abdullah Mohammed Darem (2013). Evaluation of the usability of e government websites (Doctor of Philosophy, Department of studies in Computer Science, University of Mysore, Mysore). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/62244>
- Beerappa, M., & Sheshadri, D. K. (2016). Web Link Analysis of Selected Documentation Centres in India: A Webometric Study. *International Research: Journal of Library & Information Science*, 6(2), 367-380. Retrieved from <http://irjlis.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/08/15-IR-350-62.pdf>
- Bhattacharya, Debjani (2014). Service quality of government websites in India: A select study (Doctor of Philosophy, University School of Management Studies, New Delhi). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/110081>
- Brooks, L., & Persaud, A. (2015). Comparing local e-government websites in Canada and the UK. In *International Conference on Electronic Government* (pp. 291-304). Springer, Cham. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.co.in/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Comparing+Locale-GovernmentWebsitesinCanadaand+the+UK&btnG=
- Chand, B. B. & Ramesha (2017). Indian Government Websites: A Study. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 37(5), 346-352. Retrieved from DOI: 10.14429/djlit.37.10964
- Gullikson, S., Blades, R., Bragdon, M., McKibbin, S., Sparling, M., & Toms, E. G. (1999). The impact of information architecture on academic web site usability. *The Electronic Library*.
- Hadagali, G. S., Bulla, S. D., & Shettar, I. M. (2021). Indian Institutes of Technology's Websites in India: A Webometric Analysis. *Journal of Indian Library Association*, 57 (4), 143-154.
- Jalal, S. K., Biswas, S. C., & Mukhopadhyay, P. (2009, November). Webometric analysis of Central Universities in India: A study. In *2009 International Conference for Internet Technology and Secured Transactions, (ICITST)* (pp. 1-9). IEEE.
- Jeysankar, R. Sujitha, I. Maria and Valarmathi, A. (2012). Web Pages of ICMR Institutes Websites: A Webometric Analysis. *Global Advanced Research Journal of Library, Information and Archival Studies*, 1(1), 006-018. Retrieved from <http://garj.org/garjlis/index.htm>

- Joicy, A. J., & Varghese, R. R. (2011). Websites of research and development institutions in India: A webometric study. *International Journal of Digital Library Services*, 1(2), 90-104. Retrieved from https://scholar.google.co.in/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=Webometric+analysis+of+Central+Universities+in+India%3A+A+study&btnG=
- Kannan, R., & Govindan, M. (2011). Hyperlink analysis of e-commerce websites for business intelligence: exploring websites of top retail companies of Asia Pacific and USA. *Journal of theoretical and applied electronic commerce research*, 6(3), 97-108. Retrieved from https://scielo.conicyt.cl/scielo.php?pid=S0718-18762011000300008&script=sci_arttext
- Ramanayaka, K. H., Chen, X., & Shi, B. (2018). Application of Webometrics Techniques for Measuring and Evaluating Visibility of University Library Websites in Sri Lanka. *Journal of the University Librarians Association of Sri Lanka*, 21(1). Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7015/6e68a95c8b124c410d41695b527da1cb8ab2.pdf>
- Stover, M. Zink, S.D. 1996. World Wide Web home page design: patterns and anomalies of higher education library home pages. *Reference Services Review*.
- Verma, M. K., & Brahma, K. (2017). A webometric analysis of selected non-profit organizations (NGOS) of Assam. *KIIT J. Lib. Info. Manag*, 4(1), 63-72. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/314065883>
- Wang, L., Bretschneider, S., Gant, J.: Evaluating web-based e-government services with a citizen-centric approach. In: *Proceedings of the 38th Annual Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. IEEE, (2005).

A Methodological Framework for Analyzing Thematic Evolution: Application of Text Mining Techniques in R

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Abstract: Thematic evolution analysis reveals critical insights on how research topics emerge, develop and become obsolete over the period within different scholarly domains. This paper proposes a platform-independent methodological framework for thematic evolution analysis applying text-mining techniques using R programming. A modular, transparent and customizable workflow is ensured including acquisition of bibliometric data, data cleansing, text normalization, co-word analysis, thematic mapping, topic modeling and network visualization providing a comprehensive understanding of thematic progression. R packages, such as 'bibliometrix', 'tm', 'topicmodels', 'igraph', are explored to perform time-sensitive analysis by identifying emerging areas, persistent core themes and declining topics. Although inconsistent dataset and insufficient computational resources induce challenges, the R environment facilitates cost-effectiveness, flexibility and reproducibility. Thus, the methodology is applicable across different time slices and various academic disciplines supporting evidence-based decision-making for the researchers, the institutions and the funding bodies by offering a clear view of how knowledge landscapes evolve over time.

Keywords: Thematic Evolution, R Programming, Bibliometric Analysis, Text Mining, Trend Analysis, Co-Word Networks

1 Introduction

Thematic evolution refers to how themes emerge, develop, persist, converge or disappear as time progresses. The themes of academic literature related to a particular field are traced to determine the

progression of that field. Several bibliometric tools exist to estimate thematic progression of an academic or research field. Most of them are GUI-based, often limited in scalability (handling large-scale data), flexibility (adoption of data sources and modifiable analytical techniques), transparency (allowing users to inspect the entire workflow along with the underlying processes), reproducibility (higher code-based workflow applicable across various disciplines), automation (facility of batch processing) or customization (usage of editable packages, custom functions or designing personalized plots). In contrast, R is an open source fully scriptable and customizable environment which supports full thematic analysis including data import, data preprocessing, data modeling and data visualization. Its modularity and extensibility make it suitable for cross-disciplinary applications. A robust methodological framework developed for thematic evolution analysis using widely used R packages is portrayed integrating bibliometric processing, text mining, topic modeling and network visualization into a systematic workflow. By segmenting literature into time slices and analyzing transitions between thematic clusters, the framework enables longitudinal insights into the dynamics of scholarly communication. The researchers gain comprehensive knowledge of the evolution of scientific discourse from this scalable and domain-independent approach.

2 Objective

The primary objective of this study is to design and implement a methodological framework using R programming for thematic evolution analysis within scholarly literature.

Specifically, the study intends to:

- i. Utilize R-based tools to examine the emergence, persistence and decline of research themes across defined time slices.
- ii. Provide a scalable, transparent and platform-independent approach which can be adapted across various academic disciplines.
- iii. Support decision-making by researchers, institutions, and funding agencies through systematic thematic trend analysis and the use of the evidence in research practice or policy making.

Through this framework, the study attempts to overcome the limitations of existing GUI-based tools by offering a modular and scriptable solution capable of generating longitudinal thematic pattern across diverse subject domains.

3 Scope

The scope of this study is centered on the development and application of the framework for thematic evolution analysis in academic research.

The key components of the scope are described here:

Data Sources: The procedure acquires textual data from renowned bibliographical databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science and others, which can generate multiple export formats such as BibTeX (.bib), RIS (.ris) and CSV (.csv).

Analytical Techniques: The framework integrates various text mining as well as bibliometric techniques, including data cleansing, keyword normalization, co-word analysis, thematic mapping, topic modeling and time-based network visualization.

Tools and Technologies: The framework is entirely based on the R environment. Different R packages and functions are used, e.g., ‘bibliometrix’, ‘tm’, ‘topicmodels’, ‘igraph’, including visualization tools, e.g., ‘ggraph’, ‘LDAvis’, ‘networkD3’.

Temporal Analysis: The study incorporates time-slicing methods to trace how research themes evolve across different chronological intervals enabling longitudinal development.

Applicability: The proposed framework is independent of academic domain. Thus, it can be applicable across a wide range of disciplines, which enhances the adaptability of it for researchers, academic institutions, and policy-makers who have interest in thematic mapping of specific domains.

Reproducibility and Scalability: The approach emphasizes the creation of small-scale to large-scale projects which enable a transparent, reproducible and scriptable workflow allowing customization, automation and reuse.

The study does not attempt to propose a new theoretical model of thematic evolution, rather it focuses on developing a robust data-driven methodology for thematic trend analysis using computational tools.

4 Related Work

Thematic evolution analysis has emerged as a critical approach for understanding how scientific knowledge structures shift over time. Several methodological streams have contributed to this area, particularly in the domains of bibliometrics, co-word analysis, and topic modeling. Foundationally, Callon, Courtial, Turner, and Bauin (1983) introduced co-word analysis as a technique to map the dynamics of science through the analysis of keyword co-occurrence patterns. Their work laid the theoretical groundwork for understanding how conceptual associations in scholarly literature reflect the emergence and consolidation of research themes. This method remains widely used due to its interpretability and its ability to identify the cognitive structure of a field.

Building on these foundations, more recent computational frameworks have enabled reproducible and scalable implementations of thematic analysis. Aria and Cuccurullo (2017) developed the ‘bibliometrix’ package for R, which provides a comprehensive set of tools for bibliometric analysis, including co-word network construction, thematic mapping, and citation analysis. Unlike graphical tools such as VOSviewer or CiteSpace, ‘bibliometrix’ is command-line/script-based, allowing researchers to implement fully transparent and replicable workflows.

The topic modeling techniques, particularly Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) was parallelly introduced by Blei, Ng, and Jordan (2003). They showed that the latent semantic themes can be identified in textual corpora. LDA allows the researchers to detect thematic structures, in contrast to the surface-level keyword analysis enabling document-topic and topic-word distributions. The ‘topicmodels’ package in R (Grün, Hornik, & Blei, 2011) provides an effective and efficient implementation of LDA and other related models.

Text mining capabilities in R was significantly advanced through few tools such as the ‘tm’ package (Feinerer, Hornik, & Meyer, 2008) and its associated infrastructure (Meyer, Hornik, & Feinerer, 2008), which support core preprocessing tasks including changing to lower case, stopword removal, tokenization, stemming, lemmatization and the creation of document-term matrix. These steps are essential to ensure the consistency and accuracy of downstream thematic analysis, especially when handling heterogeneous bibliographic corpora.

Network-based methods also play a prominent role in thematic evolution analysis. The ‘igraph’ package (Csárdi & Nepusz, 2006) is frequently used for the construction and visualization of co-word and citation networks. For community detection, Blondel et al. (2008) proposed the Louvain method, which is a modularity-based algorithm for detection of the clusters in large networks.

More recently, Liu and Fang (2022) brought a structured guide for conducting bibliometric analysis and systematic reviews using R, bridging the gap between bibliometric theory and applied research workflows. The work reinforces the importance of methodological rigor, transparency and reproducibility highlighting the value of R-based approaches for the researchers who aim to conduct domain-independent and scalable analyses.

Taken together, these studies point out a progression from manual to GUI-based bibliometric tools to reproducible, flexible and modular analysis implemented by R. Despite these advancements, a need is induced for an integrated end-to-end methodological framework which not only supports text mining prerequisites, such as data acquisition or cleansing, but also unifies co-word analysis, topic modeling, and network-based visualization for tracking thematic evolution over time. This paper contributes to address this gap by presenting a generalized and reproducible methodology for thematic evolution analysis through text mining using R, applicable across various disciplines.

5 The Methodological Framework

This section illustrates a structured reproducible methodological pipeline for conducting thematic evolution analysis using R. The framework integrates distinct yet interconnected subsequent modules including data acquisition, data preprocessing, temporal segmentation, co-word and thematic mapping, topic modeling and thematic evolution analysis. Visualization techniques are associated with co-word analysis, topic modeling and thematic evolution, so they are explained in a separate dedicated section.

5.1 Data Acquisition

The textual data are acquired from bibliographic databases, such as Scopus, Web of Science, Dimensions and CrossRef, which facilitates comprehensive coverage of scholarly literature across various academic disciplines. These data are exported as BibTeX (.bib), RIS (.ris) or CSV (.csv) depending on the export options of the particular databases. The exported files are imported into R and converted into a dataframe using the `convert2df()` function of the ‘bibliometrix’ package. This process facilitates the extraction of necessary metadata fields, including title of the article, abstract, keyword, publication year and other information which are crucial for downstream text mining and network analysis.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Installing the 'bibliometrix' package  
install.packages("bibliometrix")  
# Loading the 'bibliometrix' package  
library(bibliometrix)  
# Loading bibliographic data, e.g. from a Scopus-exported file scopus.bib  
data <- convert2df("scopus.bib", dbsource = "scopus", format = "bibtex")
```

5.2 Data Preprocessing

Following data acquisition, a series of preprocessing steps are performed to ensure the quality and consistency of the textual data. Duplicate entries are first identified and removed to avoid bias in frequency-based computations. Keyword normalization is then applied to unify semantically equivalent terms which may appear in varied forms across publications, e.g., “NLP” and “Natural Language Processing” are treated as a single concept. Text normalization technique is accomplished using ‘tm’ or ‘quanteda’ packages. The texts are converted to lowercase, and cleaned through removing punctuation, number and common stopwords, e.g., "and", "the", "is", which do not contribute meaningful information. Tokenization is applied to split the text into individual words, which are the fundamental units for analysis. To further reduce lexical variation, stemming or lemmatization is performed. Stemming reduces the words to their root forms by removing suffixes, e.g. "computing" to "comput". Lemmatization converts the words to their dictionary base forms, e.g. "were" to "be". This prevents the chaos caused by lexical noise.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Installing the 'tm' package
install.packages("tm")
# Loading the 'tm' package
library(tm)
# Ensuring that abstracts are present and clean from the acquired bibliometric data (using bibliometrix)
abstracts <- na.omit(data$Abstract)
# Creating a text corpus from the abstracts
corpus <- Corpus(VectorSource(abstracts))
# Converting to lowercase
corpus <- tm_map(corpus, content_transformer(tolower))
# Removing punctuation
corpus <- tm_map(corpus, removePunctuation)
# Removing numbers
corpus <- tm_map(corpus, removeNumbers)
# Removing stopwords
corpus <- tm_map(corpus, removeWords, stopwords("en"))
# Removing whitespace
corpus <- tm_map(corpus, stripWhitespace)
```

5.3 Temporal Segmentation

The datasets are segmented into chronological intervals. These are called time slices. These allow researchers to examine how thematic content changes across distinct time periods. Each time slice is treated as an independent subset which enables the identification of emerging, persisting, or declining research topics over time. The temporal segmentation is essential for tracing the developmental trajectory of research areas and understanding the historical context of thematic evolution.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Assuming 'bibliometrix' is installed and loaded
# Converting publication year to numeric (if not done)
```

```

data$Year <- as.numeric(data$PY)
# Removing the entries with missing years
data <- data[!is.na(data$Year), ]
# Creation of time-sliced data
slice1 <- subset(data, Year >= 2000 & Year <= 2014)
slice2 <- subset(data, Year >= 2015 & Year <= 2019)
slice3 <- subset(data, Year >= 2020 & Year <= 2024)
# Printing record counts in each time slice (optional)
cat("Slice 1:", nrow(slice1), "records\n")
cat("Slice 2:", nrow(slice2), "records\n")
cat("Slice 3:", nrow(slice3), "records\n")

```

5.4 Co-word and Thematic Mapping

Thematic mapping is possible through the construction of a co-word network based on keyword co-occurrence. The `biblioNetwork()` function of the ‘bibliometrix’ package employs the creation of a keyword co-occurrence matrix, which quantifies how frequently pairs of keywords appear together. This matrix forms the basis of a network graph in which nodes represent keywords and edges represent co-occurrence frequencies. Visualization of this network is performed using either the `networkPlot()` function of the ‘bibliometrix’ package or the ‘igraph’ package, allowing for the identification of densely connected keyword clusters.

➤ Sample R Code:

```

# Assuming 'bibliometrix' is installed and loaded
# Loading Scopus data (replacing actual file path)
M <- convert2df("data_file.bib", dbsource = "scopus", format = "bibtex")
# Performing bibliometric analysis
results <- biblioAnalysis(M, sep = ";")
# Creating keyword co-occurrence network
net <- biblioNetwork(data, analysis = "co-occurrences", network = "keywords", sep = ";")
# Plotting the network, where normalization is done using association strength, fruchterman is
used as layout algorithm, labelsize indicates the size of keyword labels, n (optional) refers the
number of top keywords to include
networkPlot(net, normalize = "association", type = "fruchterman", labelsize = 0.8, label.n = 50)

```

5.5 Topic Modeling

To complement the co-word analysis, Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) is applied to uncover latent thematic structures within the corpus. The ‘topicmodels’ package of R implements LDA by representing each document as a mixture of topics and each topic as the distribution of words. A document-term matrix (DTM) is created from the preprocessed texts using the `DocumentTermMatrix()` function. The number of topics is selected via optimization methods, such as coherence score evaluation or perplexity minimization, with the establishment of a balance between interpretability and model fitting. Once the model is trained, the most representative terms for each topic are extracted using the `terms()` function, allowing to interpret the semantic content of each topic. This probabilistic approach is particularly effective in identifying themes which may not be explicitly labeled by the

authors, but present in the underlying language of abstracts and titles of the scholarly literature.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Installing required package
install.packages("topicmodels")
# Loading libraries
library(topicmodels)
# corpus is already created using 'tm' package
# Creating a Document-Term Matrix (DTM)
dtm <- DocumentTermMatrix(corpus)
# Removing empty rows in DTM, it helps to prevent model fitting errors (optional)
row_totals <- apply(dtm, 1, sum)
dtm <- dtm[row_totals > 0, ]
# Fitting LDA model with 20 topics
lda_model <- LDA(dtm, k = 20, control = list(seed = 1234))
# Extracting top 25 terms per topic
topics <- terms(lda_model, 25)
# Viewing the terms
print(topics)library(topicmodels)
```

5.6 Thematic Evolution Analysis

The final phase involves analyzing how themes evolve across the predefined time slices. This is accomplished using the thematicEvolution() function from the 'bibliometrix' package, which links keyword clusters from one time slice to another time slices of subsequent periods. The function detects continuity and change by measuring overlap and semantic similarity between clusters over time, thus persist, emerge or dissolve themes are easily identified. Visualization of thematic evolution can be determined using dynamic network representations, such as Sankey diagrams or stream graphs. These visual tools illustrate how thematic clusters shift, split or merge across time intervals, facilitating an intuitive understanding of the intellectual development of the field. Sankey diagrams effectively show the flow of thematic influence highlighting both strong and weak transitions between the clusters.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Installing and loading the 'bibliometrix' package
# Importing bibliometric data
# Running thematic evolution across four time slices
evolution <- thematicEvolution(data, field = "ID", n = 180, time.slices = c(2010, 2015, 2020,
2025), minfreq = 3)
# Plotting the thematic evolution map
plot(evolution$map).
```

6 Visualization

R packages utilized for data visualization corresponding to the phases of co-word network construction, topic modeling and longitudinal theme tracking are described in this section.

The 'igraph' and 'ggraph' packages are used to construct and visualize time-based co-word networks.

These packages enable the representation of keyword relationships as graphs, where nodes correspond to keywords and edges denote the frequency of co-occurrence across documents. In the co-word and thematic mapping phase (Section 5.4), a keyword co-occurrence matrix is generated using the `biblioNetwork()` function of the `bibliometrix` package. This matrix is then visualized using force-directed layout algorithms, such as Fruchterman-Reingold, provided by ‘`igraph`’ or enhanced visualizations using ‘`ggraph`’. These visualizations help to identify the densely connected keyword clusters associated with the emerging, persistent or obsolete research themes. Separate networks can be generated against each time slice. From this, how keyword clusters evolve, merge or dissolve over time are tracked.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Assuming the accomplishment of requisites
# Creating co-word network matrix
NetMatrix <- biblioNetwork(time_slices[[slice_name], analysis = "co-occurrences", network =
"keywords", sep = ";")
# Converting to igraph object
net_graph <- graph_from_adjacency_matrix(NetMatrix, mode = "undirected", weighted = TRUE,
diag = FALSE)
# Filtering small nodes for clarity (optional)
net_graph <- delete_vertices(net_graph, degree(net_graph) < 2)
# Converting to tidygraph for 'ggraph'
tidy_net <- as_tbl_graph(net_graph)
# Visualization using 'ggraph' with Fruchterman-Reingold layout
ggraph(tidy_net, layout = "fr") + geom_edge_link(aes(width = weight), alpha = 0.4) +
geom_node_point(color = "blue", size = 3) + geom_node_text(aes(label = name), repel = TRUE,
size = 3) + ggtitle(paste("Co-word Network:", slice_name)) + theme_minimal()
```

The ‘`wordcloud2`’ package generates wordclouds which display the most frequent or key terms within the corpus. Following text preprocessing (Section 5.2), dominant topics are displayed in a given time slice. They serve as a visual complement to topic modeling exploring term distributions along with thematic emphasis.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Assuming the accomplishment of requisites
# Creating a term-document matrix
tdm <- TermDocumentMatrix(corpus)
m <- as.matrix(tdm)
# Getting word frequencies
word_freq <- sort(rowSums(m), decreasing = TRUE)
word_freq_df <- data.frame(word = names(word_freq), freq = word_freq)
# Generating the word cloud
wordcloud2(word_freq_df, size = 1.5, shape = "circle", color = "random-dark")
```

In R, the ‘`networkD3`’ package is used to create interactive network graphs, e.g. Sankey diagrams. Sankey diagram represents the flow of various resources between different entities and categories. The diagram is useful in the thematic evolution analysis phase (Section 5.6), where clusters of related

keywords emerge, persist, diverge or converge across subsequent time slices. Each node of a Sankey diagram is considered as a thematic cluster within a specific period and the links between nodes represent semantic continuity or divergence between those clusters over time. Sankey diagrams help to understand structural transformations of a research field by providing a longitudinal view of thematic trajectories.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Assuming the accomplishment of requisites
# Defining three thematic clusters across two time periods (simplified)
nodes <- data.frame(name = c("AI_2010-2014", "ML_2010-2014", "NLP_2010-2014", "AI_2015-2019", "ML_2015-2019", "NLP_2015-2019"))
# Defining transitions between clusters (source = row number - 1)
links <- data.frame(source = c(0, 1, 2, 1), target = c(3, 5, 4, 4), value = c(7, 5, 2, 3))
# Creating Sankey diagram
sankeyNetwork(Links = links, Nodes = nodes, Source = "source", Target = "target", Value = "value", NodeID = "name", fontSize = 14, nodeWidth = 30)
```

The ‘bibliometrix’ package generates thematic maps which plot keyword clusters in a 2D space defined by centrality and density metrics. These maps provide the structural importance as well as internal development of thematic areas. Centrality reflects the relevancy of the theme and connectivity to other clusters. Density indicates the level of internal cohesion within a theme. Based on these two said dimensions, the thematic clusters are categorized into four types. They are: motor themes (high centrality and high density), niche themes (low centrality and high density), emerging or declining themes (low centrality and low density) and basic themes (high centrality and low density). These classifications help to perceive the prominence of various research themes along with their stage of development. Thematic maps are thus utilized as a critical interpretive tool for identifying core, peripheral and developing areas.

➤ Sample R Code:

```
# Assuming the accomplishment of requisites
# Performing bibliometric analysis
results <- biblioAnalysis(M, sep = ";")
# Creating co-word network matrix (keyword co-occurrence)
NetMatrix <- conceptualStructure(M, field = "ID", method = "CA", stemming = FALSE, minDegree = 4, clust = 5, k.max = 5, documents = 500, graph = FALSE)
# Plotting thematic map (based on clustering)
thematicMap(M, field = "ID", n = 250, minfreq = 5, stemming = FALSE, size = 0.5, repel = TRUE)
```

Despite these, few R packages extend the methodological framework by providing alternative preprocessing tools, more expressive modeling techniques and enriched visual outputs. The ‘tidytext’ package supports text mining using the tidy data framework enabling seamless integration with ‘dplyr’, ‘ggplot2’ and other tidyverse tools for reproducible word-level analysis and custom visualizations. ‘widyr’ adds functionality for pairwise term correlation providing a statistical alternative to raw co-occurrence. ‘LDAvis’ offers interactive web-based visualization of topic models helping users to explore topic-term relationships and semantic overlaps. For constructing similarity-based term networks, ‘textplot’ and ‘textplotnetwork’ use embeddings or distance metrics like cosine similarity.

Dimensionality reduction for thematic mapping is supported by ‘FactoMineR’ and ‘factoextra’, which enable Correspondence Analysis (CA), Principal Component Analysis (PCA) or Multi-dimensional Scaling (MDS). ‘ggalluvial’ produces high-quality alluvial (Sankey-style) diagrams for visualizing thematic transitions across time slices. Finally, biblioshiny, a GUI for bibliometrix, allows interactive bibliometric analysis for users with minimal coding experience.

The integration of the said packages in R ensures reproducibility, scalability and adaptability across domains, further strengthening the utility of the proposed approach to thematic evolution analysis.

7 Strength and Limitation

7.1 Strength

- i. The entire workflow is script-based of R. It allows others to reproduce the results and transparency in the process.
- ii. The methodology is applicable across various academic disciplines due to its modular and data-driven approach.
- iii. The framework integrates multiple analytical techniques such as text normalization, co-word analysis, thematic mapping, topic modeling and network visualization into a unified pipeline.
- iv. The approach is capable enough to handle large datasets and complex queries without depending on GUI-based tools having limitations.
 - v. Time-Sensitive Analysis is incorporated to identify trends over specific intervals.
 - vi. Various R-based tools, such as ‘igraph’, ‘ggraph’, ‘LDAvis’, Sankey diagrams, are available for comprehensive and dynamic visual analysis.
- vii. The methodology enforces the open source ecosystem, as it is developed based on free and open-source R packages entirely, making it cost-effective and customizable.
- viii. A large and active user community of R contributes regular updates, new packages and documentation. This ensures continuous development with the latest techniques and best practices.

7.2 Limitation

- i. The methodology rigorously depends on the accuracy and consistency of abstract, subject or keywords, i.e. quality of the metadata from the bibliographic databases.
- ii. Thematic outcomes can be varied based on arbitrary or inconsistent time intervals which may affect the interpretation.
- iii. The procedure requires users to be comfortable with R programming, it is not ideal for the researchers without coding experience.
- iv. Topic modeling and network analysis on large datasets may require significant computational resources such as memory or processing power.
 - v. Tasks like keyword normalization or duplicate detection sometimes require manual tuning or domain-specific inputs.
- vi. Topic modeling applying LDA can produce abstract topics which are difficult to interpret without domain expertise Nile.

8 Conclusion

The paper presents a flexible and modular approach for thematic evolution analysis using R, applicable across various research fields. Blending bibliometric techniques with text mining and topic modeling, the methodological framework is developed for examining how research themes change over time. The methodology comprises sequential procedural steps starting from data collection to topic modeling incorporating data visualization. Utilizing open-source R packages for data preprocessing, co-word analysis, temporal thematic development and dynamic visualizations, a transparent, reproducible and scalable workflow is affirmed. Although some challenges related to metadata quality, computational demands and others exist, the framework enables a thorough exploration of scientific discourses. As the advancement of R packages undergoes continuous development by the large and vibrant community of R, the adoption of best practices remains as an ongoing process. This can accelerate the future developments which may include citation trajectory analysis or the incorporation of machine learning techniques to enhance predictive capabilities and thematic forecasting.

References:

- Aria, M., & Cuccurullo, C. (2017). bibliometrix: An R-tool for comprehensive science mapping analysis. *Journal of Informetrics*, 11(4), 959–975. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joi.2017.08.007>
- Benoit, K., Watanabe, K., Wang, H., Nulty, P., Obeng, A., Müller, S., & Matsuo, A. (2018). quanteda: An R package for the quantitative analysis of textual data. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 3(30), 774. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00774>
- Blei, D. M., Ng, A. Y., & Jordan, M. I. (2003). Latent Dirichlet Allocation. *Journal of Machine Learning Research*, 3, 993–1022. Retrieved from <http://jmlr.org/papers/volume3/blei03a/blei03a.pdf>
- Blondel, V. D., Guillaume, J. L., Lambiotte, R., & Lefebvre, E. (2008). Fast unfolding of communities in large networks. *Journal of Statistical Mechanics: Theory and Experiment*, 2008(10), P10008. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-5468/2008/10/P10008>
- Callon, M., Courtial, J. P., Turner, W. A., & Bauin, S. (1983). From translations to problematic networks: An introduction to co-word analysis. *Social Science Information*, 22(2), 191–235. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/053901883022002003>
- Csárdi, G., & Nepusz, T. (2006). The igraph software package for complex network research. Retrieved from <https://igraph.org/r/pdf/1.2.6/igraph.pdf>
- Grün, B., Hornik, K., & Blei, D. M. (2011). topicmodels: Statistical topic models in R [Computer software manual]. Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/topicmodels/topicmodels.pdf>
- Feinerer, I., Hornik, K., & Meyer, D. (2008). Text mining infrastructure in R. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25(5), 1–54. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v025.i05>
- Kassambara, A., & Mundt, F. (2020). factoextra: Extract and visualize the results of multivariate data analyses (Version 1.0.7) [R package]. Retrieved from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=factoextra>

- Lê, S., Josse, J., & Husson, F. (2008). FactoMineR: An R package for multivariate analysis. *Journal of Statistical Software*, 25(1), 1–18. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.18637/jss.v025.i01>
- Pedersen, T. L. (2020). ggalluvial: Alluvial plots in ggplot2 (Version 0.12.3) [R package]. Retrieved from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=ggalluvial>
- Sievert, C. (2020). Interactive web-based data visualization with R, plotly, and shiny. CRC Press. Retrieved from <https://plotly-r.com/>
- Sievert, C., & Shirley, K. E. (2015). LDAvis: Interactive visualization of topic models, In Proceedings of the 2015 IEEE Visualization Conference (VIS). Retrieved from <https://github.com/cpsievert/LDAvis>
- Silge, J., & Robinson, D. (2016). tidytext: Text mining and analysis using tidy data principles in R. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 1(3). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.00037>
- Thorp, J. (2022). widyr: Widen and process tidy data frames (Version 0.1.4) [R package]. Retrieved from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=widyr>
- Wickham, H., Averick, M., Bryan, J., Chang, W., D’Agostino McGowan, L., François, R., ... & Yutani, H. (2019). Welcome to the tidyverse. *Journal of Open Source Software*, 4(43), 1686. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01686>
- Wickham, H., François, R., Henry, L., & Müller, K. (2023). dplyr: A grammar of data manipulation (Version 1.1.3) [R package]. Retrieved from <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=dplyr>
- Xu, W., & Wang, X. (2021). textplot: Text visualization tools (Version 0.2.1) [R package]. Retrieved from <https://cran.r-project.org/package=textplot>

Mapping Collaboration and Core Journals in Doctoral Research: A Bibliometric Study of Library and Information Science, Manipur University (1990–2018)

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Abstract: *The study examines 31 doctoral theses awarded by the Department of Library and Information Science, Manipur University, between 1990 and 2018. It uses non-source data extracted from the bibliographies or references appended at the end of each thesis. These data (bibliographic entries) are imported into Excel using KIMI and analyzed in Microsoft Excel, Jamovi (Version 2.6.26) and Bradford's Laws to meet the study's objectives. Three thousand nine hundred twenty-two (3922) bibliographic references appended to these theses were extracted and analysed. The study aims (i) to identify authorship collaborations using various indicators for measures of collaboration such as Degree of Collaboration (DC), Collaboration Index (CI), and Collaboration Coefficient (CC); (ii) to find out the prioritized medium used for exchanging research communication and (iii) to sort out the core journals of the respective studies. The findings suggest that more authors collaborating for research, intensifying collaborative networks, and enriching the university library's journal subscriptions will enhance research productivity and scholarly communication.*

Keywords: Bibliometrics, Doctoral Research, Authorship Collaboration, Core Journals, Manipur University, Bradford's Law, Research Productivity

1 Introduction

Research offered in a higher educational institution is an avenue for knowledge generation and dissemination. Scholarly communication paves the way for the progressive nature of the research.

Bibliometric methods enable the mapping of authorship and citation trends, and the identification of the types of most preferred documents used. Research collaboration amongst the authors, in particular, helps to boost research productivity, interdisciplinarity and scholarly impact. Similarly, the identification of core journals ensures that libraries subscribe to the resources and informs academic researchers about the most influential sources in their disciplines.

The present study focuses on doctoral theses from the Department of Library and Information Science, a constituent department of Manipur University established in 1986. Since the Library and Information Science has produced doctoral research in library and related social science fields, no bibliometric study has previously analysed its citation, sources and authorship trends. This paper seeks to fill that gap by examining theses produced between 1990 and 2018.

2 Literature Review

Research collaboration assessment using bibliometric indicators is not a new concept anymore. Various pioneers have studied and established mathematical formulas to highlight the shift from single-authored to multi-authored research in most disciplines. First and foremost, Subramanyam (1983) introduced the Degree of Collaboration, followed by subsequent refinements such as the Collaboration Index (Lawani, 1980), and the Collaboration Coefficient (Ajiferuke et al., 1988).

In their study, Bozeman et al. (2013) explore thoroughly how university researchers work together among themselves and with people in business or other fields. It also underlines how these partnerships can aim to widen horizons or foster prosperity through academic entrepreneurship. The authors classify the key elements that influence how collaborations happen and what impacts they have. In addition, they have shared practical aspects on how collaborative research can improve, like focusing on motives, measuring real impacts, and addressing issues like exploitation.

Bruneel et al. (2010) illuminate that previous collaborative experience fosters trust and reduces barriers to future collaborations, facilitating more successful outcomes. Similarly, having a history of alliances can engender the trust necessary for effective partnership.

Diamond (1985) elaborated from the study of Berkeley Mathematicians that citations to multi-author papers are worth more to authors in terms of their earning ability or salary than citations to single-author papers.

Katz and Martin (1997) highlighted that people collaborate at the most basic level, not institutions. Direct co-operation between two or more researchers is the fundamental unit of collaboration. Certain factors pushed the researchers to work together like – high cost involved in the scientific instrumentation; affordable cost of travel and accessibility with the introduction of fax machines and electronic mail; interactions with other scientist with the development of invisible colleges or the network; increasing need of specialization within certain scientific fields especially those where the instrumentation required is very complex; growing importance of interdisciplinary research; and healthy political relations influences greater level of collaboration among the researcher. He further mentioned that for decades, the multi-author publication, frequently referred to as a co-authored publication, has been used as a basic counting unit to measure collaboration activity.

Lee and Bozeman (2005), in their paper ‘The Impact of Research Collaboration on Scientific Productivity’ explained that modern science research has become more interdisciplinary, complex, and

costly in nature, encouraging scientists to get involved in collaborative research. Funding agencies, particularly government agencies, facilitate active research collaboration as part of their funding conditions.

Lawani (1986), in his study of cancer research, highlighted that, as the number of authors per paper increases, the proportion of high-impact papers also increases.

Nilsson et al. (2010) emphasise that a supportive infrastructure within the universities enhances researchers' confidence in engaging industry partners, while informal interactions between scientists and private sector actors can trigger more formal collaborations.

Nudelman & Landers (1972) mentioned that the scientific community has given more weight to all the authors of a jointly authored paper than to the author of a single-author paper.

Ponomariov and Boardman (2008) note that informal interactions between scientists and private sector actors can lead to more intense collaborations, and

Price and Beaver (1966) in their study found that the rate of productivity increased as the number of collaborators increased.

Rubinandhini & Gomathi (2015) conducted an authorship analysis of the journal *Annals of Library and Information Studies* and detected the values of CC and DC 0.38 and 0.67, respectively. Authorship collaboration is an intense form of research interaction that allows for effective communication as well as the sharing of competence and other resources among or between researchers or scientists (Melin & Persson, 1996).

Siamaki et al. (2014) in their study in *Library & Information Science Studies in Iran* found that the values of Degree of Collaboration (DC), Collaboration Index (CI), and Collaborative Co-Efficiency (CC) were 0.46, 1.58, and 0.23, respectively, which shows moderate collaboration among the authors.

Smith (1958) examined 4189 papers from *American Psychologist* published between 1946 and 1957 and concluded that the mean number of authors per paper increased from 1.3 to 1.7. Price (1963) mentioned that since the beginning of the 20th Century, the proportion of multiple-authored papers has accelerated at a much faster rate and predicted that if the same trend continues, by 1980, there would be no single-authored paper.

Subramanyam (1983) states that collaboration in research occurs through sharing data, advice, or an idea through correspondence or at conferences, visiting each other's research facilities, or performing parts of a project separately and then integrating the results. He further mentioned in his studies that scientists extensively used prior information to adopt a reliable framework to study scientific knowledge's generation, processing, and communication. One of the accepted norms widely followed is the established practice of giving credit to earlier records of science when the information contained in them is used in a subsequent investigation. He adopted six (6) types of collaborations: Teacher-pupil collaboration; Collaboration among colleagues; Supervisor-assistant collaboration; Research Consultant Collaboration; Collaboration between Organizations; and International Collaboration.

Several studies, such as Pandey & Sahoo (2020); Waghmode, et.al. (2020), demonstrated a very high degree of authorship collaboration.

The study includes identification of the core journals used by scholars of the library science disciplines, Manipur University. Bradford's Law of Scattering, one of the three bibliometric laws, formulated in

1934 by Samuel C. Bradford, is used to identify the core journals on a specific subject using the number of journals, articles or citations as the basic parameters. The law states that if journals are arranged in order of decreasing productivity on a given subject, they can be divided into three zones [such as First Zone (core or nucleus), Second Zone, and Third Zone] where each zone contains an equal number of articles. However, the number of journals in each zone increases geometrically. Thus, this paper aims to assess research collaboration, identify the most preferred research medium and core journals out of the cited resources used by the scholars.

3 Objectives

The study aims to:

- 3.1 Investigate authorship collaboration patterns using bibliometric indicators.
- 3.2 Distinguish the preferred media of research communication in doctoral research.
- 3.3 Confirm Bradford's Law to determine the core journals cited in doctoral theses.

4 Methodology

The study is based on 3,922 citations data extracted from 31 doctoral theses awarded at Library and Information Science from 1990 to 2018. These data are non-source bibliographical data compiled from the appendices of these theses.

4.1 Data Collection: The pdf files of the bibliographic data uploaded into google drive and extract the OCR enable text in word file. The data thus extracted are arranged and imported into Microsoft Excel using KIMI (Knowledge & Information Management Interface).

4.2 Data Analysis: Statistical analysis was carried out in Excel and Jamovi (Version 2.6.26). Indicators such as DC, CI, and CC were applied to measure research collaboration trends using MS Excel, and the most preferred document types and testing of Bradford's Law for identification of core journals, dividing the dataset into productivity zones using Jamovi Software.

5 Results and Discussion

5.1 Authorship Collaboration:

Mathematical representation for calculating different bibliometric indicators to measure research collaboration are shown below as:

5.1.(a) Degree of Collaboration (DC) formulated by Subramanyam K (1983) is used to measure the proportion of multi-authored papers out of the total published works within a given dataset.

Formula:

$$\text{Degree of Collaboration (DC)} = N_m / N_m + N_s$$

Where N_m = Number of Multi-author paper

N_s = Number of Single-author paper

Interpretations:

- If the value of DC=0, it means all publications are single-authored papers.
- If the value of DC=1, it means all publications are multi-authored papers.
- The value of DC ranges from 0 to 1, a higher value in DC implies a greater tendency toward collaboration in research.
- It does not distinguish the size of collaborative groups.

5.1. (b) Collaboration Index (CI) was formulated by Lawani M in 1980, which is used to compute the mean number of authors per paper of scholarly content focusing more on the intensity of the collaboration within a specific time period.

Formula for CI:

$$CI = [\sum_{j=1}^A (j * f_j)] / N$$

Where:

j= the number of authors on a paper.

f_j= the number of papers with 'j' authors.

N= the total number of papers published.

\sum = (sigma) indicates the summation of all papers, from the minimum number of authors to the maximum.

Interpretations:

- The value of CI is greater than equal to 1
- The value of CI gives a useful sense of the scale of collaboration (more authors per paper on average)
- The value of CI always gives a mean value rather than a proportion.

5.1. (c) Collaboration Coefficient (CC) was formulated by Ajiferuke in 1988 which is applicable to measure of the degree of collaboration in research, often applied to authorship patterns in scientific publications. In simple sense, it measures the probability of multi-authored papers in a dataset. It accounts for the different levels of multiple authorships, not just the presence or absence of collaboration, by giving more weight to papers with higher numbers of authors.

The formula for the collaboration coefficient (CC) is:

$$CC = 1 - \sum [(1/j) * (f_j)] / N$$

Where:

j= the number of authors on a paper.

f_j= the number of papers with 'j' authors.

N= the total number of papers published.

\sum = all possible values of j (number of authors), up to the maximum number of authors found in a single paper.

Interpretations:

- CC values range from 0 to 1.
- If the value of CC=0, All the papers are single-authored papers.
- If the value of CC is closer to 1, the chance of co-authored papers increases in the dataset which reflects a higher collaborative intensity within the research community.
- The CC was developed to address limitations of other measures like the Collaboration Index (CI) and the Degree of Collaboration (DC), providing a more nuanced measure of collaboration.
- The value of cc does not reach to 1 unless infinite authors.

Results obtained from the extracted compilation of 3922 citations with different bibliometric indicators values are shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1 shows multi-authorship patterns along with calculated values of DC, CI and CC

LIBRARY AND INFORMATION SCIENCE THESES (31) _MU_1990_2018 Citations for all Sources															
Sl.No.	Period	Multi-Author							Nm	Total AC(Ns+Nm)	Unknown author(s)	Grand Total	DC	CI	CC
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7							
1	Prior-1947	54	7						7	61		61	0.11	1.11	0.06
2	1948-1957	37	4						4	41		41	0.10	1.10	0.05
3	1958-1967	140	12			1			13	153		153	0.08	1.11	0.04
4	1968-1977	330	62	3		6			71	401		401	0.18	1.23	0.09
5	1978-1987	561	108	4		25			137	698	3	701	0.20	1.31	0.11
6	1988-1997	490	94	6	1	12			113	603		603	0.19	1.26	0.10
7	1998-2007	866	351	60	10	28	2	2	453	1319	1	1320	0.34	1.48	0.19
8	2008-2017	267	178	66	7	8		1	260	527		527	0.49	1.70	0.28
9	Unknown Date									115		115			
									3918	4	3922				
Average Citations per Thesis		127 Citations/Thesis													

5.1.(a) The finding of the study demonstrates that the Degree of Collaboration (DC) value is found to be (i) highest during the year 2008-2017 with 0.49, and (ii) lowest during the year 1958 to 1967 with a value of 0.08. The DC Values range from 0 to 1. From the data obtained from the present study, it can be interpreted that the lower the value of DC, the majority of the research done was single-authored and weak collaboration; on the other hand, higher DC values show multi-authored and strong collaboration. Derivatives from the present dataset reflect a transition from individualistic research to more collaborative research and the growth of a research environment where research scholars became aware of the benefits of collaborative work.

5.1.(b) The study reveals that the Collaboration Index (CI) value is found to be (i) highest during the year 2008-2017 with 1.70, and (ii) lowest during the year 1948 to 1957 with a value of 1.10. The CI values are normally greater than or equal to 1. From the data obtained from the present study, it can be interpreted that the lower the value of CI, the majority of the research was done in solo mode or minimal collaboration; on the other hand, higher CI values show shifting towards multi-authored and stronger collaborative authorship and demonstrate a new positive evolution of the collaborative research ecosystem.

5.1.(c) From the present dataset, it is found that the CC values (0.04–0.28) indicate that the research output was initially dominated by single-authored works, reflecting weak collaborative research. In the later stages, the Collaboration Coefficient increased nearly sevenfold, indicating increased collaborative research uptakes. Although research collaboration is still in the infant stage, the upward trajectory demonstrates a positive trend toward joint research activity, signalling a shift from solo research to cooperative research practices.

The present study found values of the **Degree of Collaboration (DC) ranged from 0.08 to 0.49**, the **Collaboration Index (CI) ranged from 1.10 to 1.70**, and the **Collaboration Coefficient (CC) ranged between 0.04 and 0.28**, together providing a comprehensive outline of authorship collaboration in the research output studied. Initially, the research work done by the scholar consulted works done solo or independently. The research output has gradually shown an increase in incorporating more collaborative or teamwork, seeing the benefits of collaboration in terms of progressive and collective gains. Thus, the three indicators reveal a **consistent upward trend in research collaboration**.

5.2 Medium of Communication

Various media of scholarly communication were found used in the research publications. Among them, journals are the most frequently cited source, followed by books, conference proceedings, book chapters, website resources, newspaper articles, theses and dissertations, government publication reports, etc. This study aligns with global social science research trends, where journals serve as the primary knowledge exchange medium. Details shown in Table 2

Table 2 demonstrates the most preferred document types cited by the scholars

Frequencies	
Type of Document Cited	Count
Journal Articles	1855
Book	939
Conference Publications	488
Book Chapter	224
Website	107
Newspaper Article	89
Thesis	59
Government Publications	51
Report	47
Dissertation	19
Printed Manipuri Puya	10
Unpublished Documents	8
Annual Report	7

Frequencies	
Type of Document Cited	Count
Magazine Article	5
Government Publications	4
Speech	3
Newsletter	2
Records	2
Annual Report	1
Letter To The Editor	1
Working Paper	1
	3922

Figure-1 shows the most preferred document types cited in Chart

5.3 Core Journals

The application of Bradford's Law distinguishes a consolidated set of journals constituting the 'core' of doctoral research in Library and Information Science. These journals, consistently cited across

multiple theses, represent foundational sources for management research. Their delineation provides strategic guidance for collection development within the University Library, ensuring maximised access to high-impact scholarly resources.

(a) Bradford's Law of Scattering is applied to identify the core or nucleus journals mostly cited by the research scholars of management disciplines.

Formula:

The number of the journals in each zone are given in the following ratio:

$$1: n: n^2$$

where “n” is the Bradford’s Multiplier.

Bradford Multiplier represented by ‘n’ is calculated as mean value of Zone2/Zone1:Zone3/Zone2

Application of Bradford’s Law of Scattering in the current study

The dataset consists of 1855 Journal articles out of the 3922 various resources, constituting 47.30%. The frequency of the journal citations in the dataset is extracted using Jamovi software (version 2.6.26), which also ranks journals. One thousand eight hundred fifty-five (1855) journal articles are published in 527 Journal Titles. In the process, for identification of core journals in the dataset, bibliometric measures such as Bradford's Law of Scattering and Leimkuhler Model are used to test the validity of the possibilities based on the data

Table 3 shows scattered articles cited in Journals

Bradford's Law of Scattering applied to the Cited Journals				
Zone	No. of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Citations	Bradford Multiplier (n)
1	11	615	33.15	
2	49	621	33.48	4.45
3	467	619	33.37	9.53
Total	527	1855	100	6.99

Table 3 shows zone-wise journals and distributed articles or citations. First (Core or Nucleus) Zone consists of 11 journals, Second Zone with 49 Journals, and Third Zone with 467 Journals. The mean value of Bradford's Multiplier is n=6.99

Mathematically,

Identified Zones are arranged in the geometrical series, $1: n: n^2$ - (1)

[Bradford’s Law of Scattering]

$$\% \text{ Error} = \frac{\text{Total Calculated Value of Journals} - \text{Total Given Value of Journals}}{\text{Total Given Value of Journals}} \times 100 \quad \text{-(2)}$$

In equation (1) above, Bradford’s Multiplier Value, n=6.99 is applied, [derived from Table 3 above]

Then, $1: n: n^2 :: 11: (11 \times 6.99): [11 \times (6.99)^2]$

Therefore, the total value of journals derived is = $11 + 76.89 + 537.4611$
 = 625.3511 - (3)

Putting the derived value of journals i.e. 625.3511 from (3) in equation (2),

$$\begin{aligned} \text{\% Error} &= \frac{625.3511 - 527}{527} \times 100 && [\text{Total Given Value of Journals} = 527] \\ &= 18.66\% \end{aligned}$$

Since the percentage (%) Error is quite high, the dataset does not fit into the Bradford's Law of Scattering.

(b) Leimkuhler Model & its applications:

The **Leimkuhler model**, introduced by Ferdinand F. Leimkuhler in 1967-68, is a mathematical formalization and generalization of Bradford's Law of Scattering. It provides a quantitative value for describing how articles or citations are distributed across journals or sources, often using geometric or analytic functions, especially in fields where a few sources cite maximum articles or citations while many others contribute much less.

Egghe (1990) introduced a new mathematical formula, which modifies Leimkuhler's model for calculating Bradford's multiplier 'k'. The proposed model is given below

$$k = (e_y \times Y_m)^{1/p} \quad - (4)$$

Where:

$e_y = 1.781$ (Euler's constant; sometimes represented as e^y in texts)

Y_m = number of articles (or citations) in the **most productive source** (i.e., the journal with the most articles in the dataset) = 114

p is the **number of Bradford zones** (groups that contain similar number of articles)

Using the value from the dataset,

$$\text{New Bradford's Multiplier 'k'} = (1.781 \times 114)^{1/3} \approx 5.88 \quad - (5)$$

Mathematically, the number of journals in the first (core or nucleus) zone of Bradford is calculated using the formula given below with new modifier:

$$\begin{aligned} r_o &= \frac{T(k-1)}{(k^p-1)} && \text{where, } T = \text{Total Number of Journals} \\ &= \frac{527(5.88-1)}{(5.88^3-1)} \\ &= \frac{2571.76}{202.297472} && \approx 12.713 \quad - (6) \end{aligned}$$

Then the value in the subsequent new zones are calculated as given below:

$$r_1 = r_0 * k = 12.713 \times 5.88 = 74.75 \quad - (7)$$

$$r_2 = r_0 * k^2 = 12.713 \times (5.88)^2 = 12.713 \times 34.57 = 439.5 \quad - (8)$$

Now, putting the values of (5) (6), (7) and (8) in Bradford New Zone of Scattering

i.e. $r_0 : r_1 : r_2$

$$12.713 : 12.713 \times 5.88 : 12.713 \times (5.88)^2$$

$$12.713 : 74.75 : 439.5$$

Therefore, the value becomes = 526.96 -(9)

Then, Percentage (%) Error = $\frac{526.96-5}{527} \times 100$

$$= \frac{-0.04}{527} \times 100 = -0.0076\%$$

Therefore, it is found that calculation the percentage error is very minimal which can be neglected.

Hence the Bradford's law of scattering fits very well in the present dataset for the New Bradford multiplier $k = 5.88$.

Newly derived Bradford's Zones are shown below:

Table 4 shows New Bradford's Zone Value Using New Modifier Value i.e. 5.88

New Bradford's Zone Using New Modifier Value for Cited Journals				
Zone	No. of Journals	No. of Citations	% of Citations	New Bradford Multiplier (k)
1	12.71	648	34.933	
2	74.75	687	37.035	5.881
3	439.50	520	28.032	5.879
Total	526.96	1855	100	5.88

(c) Based on the new zones, core journals from the dataset are shown below:

Table 5 provides the list of Core Journals preferred by the LIS, Scholars, MU

SI No	Source of Publications	No. of Articles or Citations	Cummulative Value
1	IASLIC Bulletin	114	114
2	ILA Bulletin	96	210
3	Reference Services Review	66	276
4	Library Review	49	325
5	Annals of Library Science and Documentation	46	371

SI No	Source of Publications	No. of Articles or Citations	Cummulative Value
6	Herald of Library Science	46	417
7	Journal of Documentation	45	462
8	New Library World	43	505
9	The Electronic Library	39	544
10	Indian Journal of Information, Library & Society	36	580
11	SRELS Journal of Information Management	35	615
12	Library Trends	33	648

Figure-2 shows graphical representation of 12 core journals, LIS, Manipur University

The study has identified the 12 core journals preferred by most scholars, with IASLIC Bulletin on the top followed by ILA Bulletin, Reference Services Review, Library Review, Annals of Library Science and Documentation, Herald of Library Science, Journal of Documentation, Newl Library World, The Electronic Library, Indian Journal of Information, Library and Society, SRELS Journal of Information Management and Library Trends.

6. Data Source:

The data used in analysis are accessible at URL: <http://bit.ly/4781jX4>.

7. Conclusion

The bibliometric study of awarded doctoral theses at Library and Information Science, Manipur University, demonstrates increasing trends in authorship collaboration, shown various preferred

communication medium used and the primary role of journals in scholarly communication. The identification of core journals and the key preferred choice of types of documents for scholarly communication provides insight for library collection development and enhances better academic services by aligning with the library's decision-making. The study contributes to the broader understanding of doctoral research citation practices and collaboration patterns. The study findings could be expanded to comparative analyses across departments and universities.

References:

- Bozeman, Barry, Fay, Daniel & P. Slade, Catherine (2013). Research collaboration in universities and academic entrepreneurship: the-state-of-the-art. *J Technol Transf*, 38, 1-67
- Bruneel, J., D'Este, P. & Salter, A. (2010). Investigating the factors that diminish the barriers to university–industry collaboration. *Research Policy*, 39(7), 858–868
- Diamond, A. M. (1985). The money value of citations to single-authored and multiple-authored articles. *Scientometrics*, 8(5–6), 315–320. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02016900>
- Egghe, L. & Rousseau, R. (1990). *Introduction to Informetrics: Quantitative methods in library, documentation and information science*. Elsevier Science Publishers.
- Katz, J. S., & Martin, B. R. (1997). What is research collaboration? *Research Policy*, 26(1), 1–18.
- Lawani, S. M. (1986). Some bibliometric correlates of quality in scientific research. *Scientometrics*, 9(1–2), 13–25.
- Lee, S., & Bozeman, B. (2005). The impact of research collaboration on scientific productivity. *Scientific Collaboration*, 35(5), 673–702. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/25046667>
- Melin, G., & Persson, O. (1996). Studying research collaboration using co-authorships. *Scientometrics*, 36(3), 363–377. <https://doi.org/10.1007/bf02129600>
- Nilsson, A. S., Rickne, A., & Bengtsson, L. (2010). Transfer of academic research: Uncovering the grey zone. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 35(6), 617-636
- Nudelman, A. E., & Landers, C. E. (1972). The failure of 100 divided by 3 to equal 33 1/3. *The American Sociologist*, 7(1), 9.
- Pandey, S., & Sahoo, S. (2020). Research collaboration and authorship pattern in the field of semantic digital libraries. *DESIDOC Journal of Library & Information Technology*, 40(6), 375–381. <https://doi.org/10.14429/djlit.40.06.15680>
- Ponomariov, B., & Boardman, P. C. (2008). The effect of informal industry contacts on the time university scientists allocate to collaborative research with industry. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 33(3), 301–313
- Price, D. J. de S. (1963). *Little science, big science*. Columbia University Press.
- Price, D. J. de S., & Beaver, D. de B. (1966). Collaboration in an invisible college. *American Psychologist*, 21(11), 1011–1018.

- Rubinandhini, A., & Gomathi, P. (2015). Authorship pattern on Annals of Library and Information Studies output during 2005–2014: A bibliometric study. *International Journal of Engineering Science & Management Research*, 2(9), 141–150. Retrieved from <http://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/14-libre.pdf>
- Siamaki, S., Geraei, E., & Zare-Farashbandi, F. (2014). A study on scientific collaboration and co-authorship patterns in library and information science studies in Iran between 2005 and 2009. *Journal of Education and Health Promotion*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.4103/2277-9531.139681>
- Simte, T. P., & Phuritsabam, B. (2022). Identifying authorship collaboration patterns and applying Bradford's law of scattering in the Department of Library and Information Science. In P. Babbar, P. K. Jain, B. Markscheffel, D. C. Kar, & R. Sangchantr (Eds.), *Metrics, indicators, mapping and data visualizations in webometrics, informetrics and scientometrics* (pp. 218–226). B.K. Books International.
- Smith, M. (1958). The trend toward multiple authorship in psychology. *American Psychologist*, 13(10), 596–599.
- Subramanyam, K. (1983). Bibliometric studies of research collaboration: A review. *Journal of Information Science*, 6(1), 33–38.
- Viju, W., & Ganesh, V. (2013). Application of Bradford's law of scattering to the literature of library & information science: A study of doctoral theses citations submitted to the universities of Maharashtra, India. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 1. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2569&context=libphilprac>
- Waghmode, S. S., Lathkar, R. A., & Kulkarni, J. N. (2020). Research publication trends in Indian LIS journals: A scientometric study. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. <http://eprints.rclis.org/40437/>

Websites:

- Manipur University. (2025). Manipur University. <https://www.manipuruniv.ac.in>
- INFLIBNET Centre. (2025). Shodhganga: A reservoir of Indian theses. <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in>

The Concept of Folk: Interpreting its Representation in Knowledge Structure

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Abstract: *Inclusion and representation of multidimensional concepts pose a challenge to any Knowledge Organisation System. This study aims to explore how the concept of Folk has been reflected in the twenty-third edition of Dewey Decimal Classification System (DDC). It shows how the various aspects related to folk has been classified in the scheme, as well as highlights the interpretational difficulties that a classifier might face while representing folk in the Universe of Knowledge. Not only so there are instances of similar terms being present in DDC making the classification context dependent. It also examines how some of the documents on folk and its diverse concepts are classified in the Library of Congress (LOC) and National Library of India (NLI). The findings reveal that the concept of folk is vastly diverse and requires proper understanding and interpretation.*

Keywords: Folk, Folklore, Library Classification, Dewey Decimal Classification Scheme, Library of Congress, National Library of India.

1 Introduction

Transfer of knowledge, orally or through formal institutions, across time and generation holds significant historical, social, and cultural importance. The term ‘Folk’ reflects the idea of a collective identity and shared experiences associated with ‘a way of life’ of a specific community that is passed through oral transmission or by common practices, generation after generations. It includes traditions and customs; faiths and beliefs; diverse forms of cultural expressions like dance, drama, and music; arts, crafts, and architecture; medicine; literary manifestations like lores, legends, fables, proverbs, mythologies, poetry, drama etc. Historically ‘folk’ was often associated with rural, agrarian, non-literate communities. With time the idea of folk evolved to include even urban, educated, and advanced groups of people who share some points of commonality and cohesion.

Dundes (1980) defined folk as “any group of people whatsoever who shares at least one common factor. It does not matter what the linking factor is – it could be a common occupation, language, or religion-but what is important is that a group is formed for whatever reason it calls its own”. So, a ‘folk

identity' can get created based on several factors viz.: ethnicity, occupation, region, religion, common history, etc. Such identities pave the way for the development of unique folk cultures that encompass all their tangible and intangible representations, viz. material cultures (arts and artifacts, architecture, handicrafts etc.); oral traditions (folklores, myths, legends, riddles, etc.); customs (rituals, festivals, etc.); performing arts (dance, music, songs). The purview of 'Folk' as a concept is therefore diverse and multidimensional. It cannot be considered just as a group of people with certain commonality. Rather 'Folk' represents a knowledge system whose understanding requires perspective of several disciplines such as Anthropology, History, Literature, Performing Arts, Sociology, Medicine, Architecture, etc.

Any library classification scheme represents innumerable multifaceted domains. These domains include concepts like Environment, Rural, Urban, Women, Disability, Disaster, Water and so on. But the disciplinary structure of the classification schemes inevitably results in their scattering under distinctly separate subject fields. Although initially this scattering might not pose a challenge, however, the growth of literary warrant of any of these domains and its emergence as significant research areas, certainly leads to serious issues in easily locating all related documents on the specific concept together. Moreover, after a period, there might emerge a separate discipline, further necessitating the need to bring together all related documents of the concerned subject matter. For instance, a whole new academic discipline called 'Folklore Study' has emerged "the subject matter of which comprises the sum total of traditionally derived and orally or imitatively transmitted literature, material culture, and custom of subcultures within predominantly literate and technologically advanced societies" (Folklore, n.d.). The need to bring together documents that are related to the core idea of 'Folk' and fall under the scope of the subject field becomes inevitable. For the concept of Folk, the area of concern is not just its scattering but also the challenge of interpreting the various related aspects. Similarly, the presence of a single term under two or more subjects further leads to considerable difficulties. Understanding the context and proper interpretation therefore becomes crucial in determining its rightful position in the universe of subject.

As the concept of 'Folk' is dynamic, and highly context dependent, exploring its treatment will give an insight into the representation of 'Folk' in a Library Classification Scheme.

2 Review of Literature

Exploring treatment of disciplines or subjects in library classification schemes have been attempted by many. Dong-Geun, & Ji-Suk (2001) highlighted the bias in representation of the religion 'Christianity' spread from 220-280 and discussed the scope for expansion of the Religion 200 class in Dewey Decimal classification scheme (DDC). Fields & Connell (2004) explored the dealing of the subject Home Economics, its number relocation, terminological changes and placement biases in the various editions of DDC. Saha & Hatua (2019) dealt with Humanities and its representation as a discipline in the twenty third edition of DDC. Studies have been conducted to investigate the inclusion and reflection of interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary subjects in classification schemes. Comparative study of selected fused main subjects in Colon Classification (CC), Universal Decimal Classification (UDC) and DDC were attempted by Neelameghan and Gopinath (1972); Husain (1989) evaluated the accommodation capability of Colon Classification seventh edition focusing on two subjects viz Astronomy and Astrophysics. A comparison of interdisciplinary representations in DDC, UDC and CC was made by Bhattacharya (2006) on subjects under Science and Technology. An investigation on

subject development and number relocation in classification schemes was carried out by Gopinath and Seetharama (1975) on three subjects viz: Biochemistry, Marketing and Survey Research Methodology. While these studies focused on understanding disciplinary/interdisciplinary representations, efforts have also been made to analyze multifaceted concepts that have over the year gathered considerable literary warrants. Biros (2013) carried out a study on 'environment' for which he analyzed the environmental dictionary present in British National Library and identified the different sub-categories in which these dictionaries have been classified. Balaji (2019) attempted to investigate the domain 'Urban' as reflected in three classification schemes- Library of Congress Classification Scheme, Universal Decimal Classification and Dewey Decimal Classification. The paper focused on the different vocabularies and disciplines from which the subject Urban Studies draws its subject matters from. The reflection of 'Children' in Dewey Decimal Classification was dealt with by Pal, Mondal & Bhattacharya (2019) in their study. Ghosh & Das (2019) showed a comparative study on the treatment of 'Persons with Disabilities' between DDC and UDC. The findings of the study showed that UDC provides for the in-depth subject coverage suitable for specialist library collections. Sanyal (2022) discussed the treatment of 'gender spectrum' in Dewey Decimal classification using N-Gram analysis. The literature search shows that most of the previous works concentrated on identifying the treatment or representation of the subjects or multifaceted concepts in a discipline-based classification schemes and very little work has been done in understanding the scattering of the domains and their overlapping of ideas posing a problems in understanding the correct position of classifying a document, leaving the decision to a large extent on the ability of the classifier to interpret the subject matter of the document to be classified. A study focusing on such problems becomes pertinent. This study thus attempts to identify the scattering, problems in interpreting and classifying the multifaceted concept 'Folk'.

3 Objective of the Study

The objective of the study is to identify the problems in interpreting and classifying a multidimensional concept of 'Folk'. In doing so the study attempted:

- To find the main classes under which 'Folk' is represented in DDC.
- To study the interpretational challenges in representation of the various aspects of the 'Folk'.
- To identify any existing gap in the inclusion of 'Folk'
- To study how documents on Folk and related aspects are classified in libraries.

4 Methodology

At first, a thorough document search was conducted to identify the various aspects that fall within the purview of the concept of 'Folk.' Literature search included dictionaries, encyclopedias as well as syllabuses of universities that have courses on Folklore Studies as separate disciplines. In the second stage the listed aspects were searched in the 23rd edition of the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) to identify its positions in the classification scheme. In the third stage documents (books) corresponding to the listed search terms for each of the aspects were searched and retrieved from the Online Public Access Catalogue (OPAC) to understand how these domains are classified. For this the Library of Congress OPAC and the National Library of India OPAC have been studied. Finally, analysis and interpretations of the collected data have been done to fulfil the objective of the study.

5 Scope and Limitations

The study is restricted to the reflection of the concept of 'Folk' in the twenty-third edition of Dewey Decimal Classification only. Also, due to unavailability of Dewey Decimal class numbers in all national library OPACs only the Library of Congress OPAC and National Library of India OPAC were used to retrieve documents for exploring the class number assigned. Class number assigned to 'Books' were only taken into consideration. As the number of retrieved books from both the OPACs were large, so, due to time constraints, a purposive sampling method was adopted to select the books for the fulfillment of the objective of the paper.

6 Significance of the Study

Classifying multifaceted concepts is a challenge. Any such concept has high chances of showing conceptual overlapping resulting in indistinctness in the subject matter of a document. Comprehending the context and properly interpreting the subject matter of the document to be classified becomes necessary to put it in its right place in the Universe of Subject. Moreover, the perspectives of interpretation might vary depending upon the main subject that is being dealt with. In DDC, mapping 'folk' and exploring its various treatments under different Main classes will help library professionals in understanding the interpretational significance and relevance in classifying multifaceted concepts like 'folk' more accurately.

7 Data Analysis and Interpretation

7.1 Reflection of Folk in Twenty-Third edition of DDC

Table 1: Folk & its corresponding class numbers as reflected in DDC

Main Class in DDC	Sub Class in DDC	Topic	Class No.
Social Science 300	Culture & institutions 306	Folkways	306
	Customs, etiquette, folklore 390	Folklore	398
		History, Geographic Treatment, biography of folklore	398.09
		Folk Literature	398.2
		Real phenomenon as subjects of folklore	398.3
		Para natural and legendary phenomenon as subject of folklore	398.4
		Riddles	398.6
		Jokes and Jests	398.7
		Rhymes and Rhyming Games	398.8
	Proverbs	398.9	

Main Class in DDC	Sub Class in DDC	Topic	Class No.
Technology 600	Medicine & health 610 Pharmacology and therapeutics 615 Specific therapies and kinds of therapies 615.8	Folk Remedies	615.88
Arts and recreation 700	Graphic arts & decorative arts 740 Decorative arts 745	Folk Arts	745
	Music 780 General principles & musical forms 781 Elements of music 781.2	Folk Music Modes	781.263
	Traditions of music 781.6	Folk Music	781.62
	Recreational and performing arts 790 Indoor games and amusements 793 Social, folk, national dancing 793.3	Folk Dance	793.31

Main Class in DDC	Sub Class in DDC	Topic	Class No.
Literature (Belles-lettres) and rhetoric 800	Rhetoric and collections of literary texts from more than two Literatures 808	Folk Poetry	808.81
	Collections of literary texts from more than two Literatures 808.8	Folk Drama	808.2

The above table reveals that the concepts relating to 'Folk' is scattered under four main classes viz.: 300 Social Science, 600 Technology, 700 Arts & Recreation and 800 Literature. Under 300 Social Science, Folk is classed as 'Folkways' in 306 'Culture & institutions'. It is also classed under 390 'Customs, Etiquette, folklore'. Class number 398 is specifically assigned to the concept of 'folklore' under which almost all aspects of folklore has been dealt with. This includes History, geographic and biographical treatment of folklore; Folk literature; Any real or paranormal phenomenon that feature as a subject of folklore, legends; as well as riddles, jokes, rhymes, proverbs that are part of folklore. Under 600 'Technology' Folk is reflected under 610 Medicine class. Folk remedies have been given class number 615.88 under 615 Pharmacology and therapeutics. In 700 'Arts and recreation' 745 Decorative Arts has a note 'Class Here Folk Arts'. Under 780 'Music', 'Folk Music Modes' have class number 781.263 and 'Folk Music' have class number 781.62. Similarly, under 790 'Recreational and performing arts' Folk Dance has the class number 793.31. Under Literature 800 'Folk Poetry' and 'Folk Drama' are assigned class number 808.81 and 808.82 respectively as collection of literary text from more than two literatures.

Table 2: Folk & its corresponding class numbers as reflected in Tables of DDC

Table No.	Topic	Class Number
Subdivisions for Works by or about More than One Author (Table 3B)	Folk Poetry, Prose, Poem	-1
	Folk Drama	-2
Notation to Be Added Where Instructed in Table 3B, 700.4, 791.4, 808-809 (Table 3C)	Customs, etiquette, folklore	-3559

Other than the Main Classes, Table 3B also reflects the concept of 'Folk Poetry, Prose, Poem' having the class number -1; and 'Folk Drama' -2. On the other hand, in table 3C -3559 is assigned for 'Customs, etiquette, folklore'.

Table 3: Folk & its corresponding class numbers as reflected in Index of DDC

Main Class in DDC	Topic	Index Class Number
Technology 600	Folk Medicine	610
Arts and recreation 700	Folk Song	782.42162
Biography	Folk Singers	782.421 620 092 (Index)
	Folk Musicians	781.620.092 (Index)

The term 'Folk Medicine' has been assigned class number 610 (Medicine & health) in the index only. The class number for 'Folk Song' needs to be constructed following the add instruction as given under 782.4. However, the class number for folk song has an index entry having the class number 782.421 62. For folk song of any region further 'add instructions' are given. Again, few of such regional folk songs have dedicated class number in the index viz: 782.4216213 (American Folk Song); 782.421622 (English Folk Song) 782.4216241 (French Folk Song) 782.4216231 (German Folk Song) 782.42162691 (Portuguese Folk Song) 782.421629171 (Russian Folk Song) 782.4216261 (Spanish Folk Song). Biographical treatment of folk singers or folk musicians is assigned class number as per instructions. In the index there is entry of already constructed class numbers for both.

7.2 Interpretational Challenges in representation of the various aspects of 'Folk' in DDC

Identifying the interpretational challenges in classifying folk necessitates the understanding of the basic concepts that are represented and how they might lead to a conflict in determining the class numbers. As revealed from Table 1 the most explicit location of Folk concepts is in 398 Folklore. This class number or any of its subordinate class number can be assigned to documents which have folk concepts as its core subject area. Under 398 Folklore is treated in two distinct ways: first 398.2 deals folk as literature and secondly 398.3-398.4 considers the themes of any folklore as social and cultural phenomenon. Both categories cover almost similar themes and subjects, however, have completely different implications. Class Number 398.2 includes folktales, fairy tales, fables, as well as any work of their criticism / critical appraisal. It includes provisions to represent folk literature by language in class number 398.204 having instruction to add language from Table 6, example 'Folktales of Bengali speaking areas of the world' 398.2049144; folk literature of specific continents, countries & localities in class number 398.209 having instruction to add area notation from Table 2, for example 398.20954 for 'Folk Literature of India'. However, for 'French Folktales from France' it is the place that gets precedence over language. Class number 398.20944 will be assigned to it. Other than this, there are provisions of class number for folklore on different topics and themes, for example paranatural beings of human, tales about places, time, animals, plants, ghost stories etc. On the other hand, Class number 398.3-398.4 deals with history and criticism of the themes/subjects of folklore. The works in consideration here treats the themes it terms of their social and cultural significance. It includes themes on 'real phenomenon' like time, weather, scientific themes as well as 'paranatural and legendary phenomenon' like folk beliefs, legendary plants and animals etc. Thus, as mentioned in DDC the class number for 'Folkloristic Ghost Story' will be 398.25 and 'Ghost as a subject of folklore' would be 398.47. Similarly, the theme 'Place' has three different representations: Folklore of India will be

398.20954 and Folktales on India will be 398.23254 both representing folk literature whereas 'India as a subject of folklore' will be classed as 398.32954 under Real phenomena as subjects of folklore. The class 398 also includes 'Riddles', 'Jokes', 'Rhymes'-including lullabies, tongue twisters, proverbs along with Folk aphorisms.

While folklore has a detailed representation in DDC, there are areas that creates interpretational challenges in deciding class numbers. One such area is determining whether the document in consideration is folk literature or general literature. Anonymity and oral transfer are not enough to identify a folklore. There also exists anonymous classics that have more literary value even if transferred across generation orally. The manual of DDC 23rd edition explains this with the example of 'Njals Saga' which they have classified under literature having 839.63 as the class number. Similarly having an author does not qualify a book to be a classic or literature. For example, as mentioned in the manual 'Collection of folktales by Grimm brothers' will always be classed as Folk literature as they are mere collections of already existing folktales and the authors have little contribution to it. But Hans Christian Andersen's collection of Fairy Tales is not a part of folklore but rather is classed under 800 Literature with 839.8136 as the specific class numbers. Again, anonymous classics can also be classed with subjects. This is especially evident in case of Mythologies. Mythologies having high religious, theological or ritualistic values are classed under 200 Religion. For example, Jataka Tales will have the class number 294.382325. However, "myths or mythology presented in terms of cultural entertainment or, especially, as representative of the early literary expression of a society, even if they are populated by gods and goddesses" (Dewey, 2011) must be classed under 398.2 Folklore. For non-religious mythology and legends that have social themes or heroes that are not related to religious beliefs again the class number is under 389.2 Folklore. Thus, classifying mythology especially those featuring gods and goddesses needs to be interpreted true to its context before assigning a class number. Collected works on folk literature faces another challenge when the document, in hand, have writings belonging to more than two literatures. In such cases Folk Drama or Folk Poetry are classed in Literature class under 808 dealing with literary text from more than two literature. This leads to scattering of folk literature under two distinct Main classes: Folk literature and Literature in general.

This ambiguity is present not just for literature. As music, art, dance, medicine, plants, animals etc all appears as themes in folklore understanding which folk music, art or dance to be classed as folklore and which under 700 Arts and recreation is important. Not all documents dealing with folk music and dance will be classed as folk music, song or dance. Music as a theme of folklore definitely will find its place under 398 but any modern expression of folk music will be classes under 781.62 'Folk Music'. So, the question to decide whether the item to be classified represents cultural tradition or a representation of modern artistic performance lies with the classifier. The line is often blurry and might lead to scattering materials in a library. Moreover, the provision to classify folk music originating from a specific ethnic group or national group falls under 781.62 with instruction to add notation from Table 5 i.e. the table dealing with ethnic and national groups, For example Spanish folk music 781.6261. Similar types of contradiction also exist in case of Folk Song and Folk dance. Any item of cultural traditional manifestation of folk dance must be classed under 398 whereas any modern-day expression of the folk dance will be classed under 793.31 Folk Dance under recreational and performing arts. For Folk Arts if represented as decorative item will be classed as 745 Folk Arts.

There are numerous such terms related to 'Folk' that have both traditional and modern manifestations. The modern manifestations include the original folk concepts and ideas but neither form folk literature

nor are true cultural and social expressions of folkways or folk cultures. Rather they are more like an adaption of those ideas into the modern context. Thus, they do not represent the folk culture true to its sense.

7.3 Gap in the inclusion of 'Folk' in DDC

Table 4: Selected terms related to Folk not reflected in DDC

Terms	Title of the book	Class Numbers in LOC OPAC
Folk Culture	Folk Culture	306.0954
Folk Customs	Folk customs / by Ellyn Sanna	398.097
	Welsh Folk Customs	398.09429
Folk Medicine	African American folk healing.	398.208996073
	Folk medicine / by Peter Sieling	398.353
	Folk medicine in America today / John Heinerman	615.50973
Folk Law	Folk law:essays in the theory & practice of Lex non scripta	340.5
	Burmese law tales; the legal element in Burmese folklore	398.209591
Folk Architecture	Spanish folk architecture	720.946
	Kentucky folk architecture	728
	Romanian folk architecture	720.9498

While carrying out the literature search a list of folk related concepts were made representing the various dimensions of 'Folk'. While most of the terms representing the concepts have been found either directly or through add instructions, some of the terms were found to have no direct terminological representation. The above table shows selected terms that have significant connection to the concept of 'Folk' but does not have an assigned class number given in DDC. The table also reveals class numbers assigned to some retrieved books from the Library of Congress OPAC on those concepts. 'Folk Culture' represents a way of life and the book retrieved is classified under 306 'Culture & institutions' with added number of 54 India. Similarly, a book on Folk customs is simply classified under 398 Folklore. Folk Medicine has only an index entry. Here it is observed from the table that three books were retrieved out of which two books were assigned class number under Folklore and one under 615.8 'Specific therapies and kinds of therapies' in the main class 610 Medicine. Similar is the case for 'Folk Laws'. Between the two retrieved books, one is classed in Folklore and the other under 340 Law. Another term that had no terminological representation is Folk Architecture, also sometimes referred to as vernacular architecture. Out of the three books two were placed directly under 720 'Architecture' and one under 728 'Residential and related buildings' with little representation of the concept of folk. A further conceptual study will reveal that there are many other such folk related terms that do not have distinct representation in DDC and therefore can pose serious ambiguity in classifying them. But again, a thorough and logical interpretation of the context and purpose of the theme both the book can decide where to classify it.

7.4 Reflection in OPAC of Selected Libraries

This section represents few selected folklore books along with its class numbers as reflected in the OPAC of Library of Congress and National Library of India.

Table 5: Examples of books on 'folk' retrieved from LOC and NLI

Books	Class Number in OPAC	
	LOC	NLI
Folktales of Mexico. Edited and translated by Américo Paredes	398.20972	398.210972
Aesop's Fable	398.2452	398.24 398.21
The Complete Grimm's Fairytale	-	398.210943
Panchatantra translated from Sanskrit by Franklin Edgerton	398.2	398.24 891.23
Maryland folk legends and folk songs	398.09752	-
Bhaoyaiya lok samgit cayanika	-	782.42162
Folk music in America	784.4973	-
The Adventure of Hatim Tai	-	823 398.21

The above table shows the importance of context of any book dealing with concepts of folk. While some of them have clear reflection of their folk nature but there are instances of ambiguity as reflected in the class numbers in Table 5. One such example is Panchatantra where both LOC and NLI have classed it under Folklore, NLI also have entry where it has been placed in Literature class. Similarly, the example incase of folk songs the book 'Maryland folk legends and folk songs' is classed in 398 folklores but the book 'Bhaoyaiya lok samgit cayanika' is classed in as 782.42162 Folk songs under 782 'Vocal music'.

8. Findings

- The above study shows that the concept of folk is scattered under four main classes namely 300 Social Science, 600 Technology, 700 Arts and recreation and 800 Literature.
- The study reveals that there are interpretational challenges in deciding class numbers on Folk and its related concepts.
- There are concepts that have significant connections with folk but does not have terminological representation and assigned class numbers in twenty-third edition of DDC.
- The reflections in the OPAC of LOC and NLI supports the previous findings by showing the difference in class numbers assigned to documents dealing with same concepts.

9 Conclusion

Understanding 'folk' demands more than just identifying the concept of the document in hand. It requires in depth analysis to justly contextualize the dynamic nature of folk. Also, as the concept of folk is evolving in modern period, there are numerous scopes to include newly emerging concepts such as urban legends and memes, that are now treated as a part of folk culture under Folklore Study.

References

- Balaji, B. P. (2019). Domain Analysis of 'Urban' in Library Classification Schemes. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=6299&context=libphilprac>
- Bhattacharya, U. (2006). *Emergence of interdisciplinary subjects in science and technology in 20th century and their treatment in different classification schemes*. (Doctoral dissertation, Jadavpur University, Kolkata, India). Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/352699>
- Biros, C. (2013). Mapping the environmental field with the help of library classification systems. *ASP. la revue du GERAS*, 64, 51-73.
- Dewey, M (2011). *Dewey Decimal Classification and Relative Index*. (23rd Edition). New York: OCLC
- Dong-Geun, O., & Ji-Suk, Y. (2001). Suggesting an option for DDC class religion (200) for nations in which religious diversity predominates. *Knowledge Organization*, 28(2), 75-84.
- Dundes, A. (1980). *Interpreting folklore*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Fields, A. M., & Connell, T. H. (2004). Classification and the Definition of a Discipline: The Dewey Decimal Classification and Home Economics. *Libraries & Culture*, 39(3), 245–259.
- Folklore (n.d.). In *Encyclopaedia Britannica*. Retrieved from <https://www.britannica.com/topic/folklore-academic-discipline>
- Ghosh, C., & Das, A. (2019). Classification scheme to organize the collection of a special library of persons with disabilities: A comparative study between DDC and UDC. *Librarian*, 25 (2), 68-73.
- Gopinath, M. A., & Seetharama, S. (1975). Interdisciplinary subjects and their classification. In *Ordering systems for global information networks: Proceedings of the Third International Study Conference on Classification Research* (pp. 121-135).
- Husain, S. (1989). A theoretical basis for the accommodation of new subjects in Colon Classification edition7. *Knowledge Organization*, 16(2), 82-88.
- Neelameghan, A., & Gopinath, M. A. (1972). Fused main subject. *Library Science*, 11(1), 316-335. Retrieved from <http://library.isical.ac.in:8080/xmlui/handle/10263/1527>
- Pal, A., Mondal, T. K., & Bhattacharya, U. (2019). Treatment of subject descriptors on children in twenty three DDC editions. In U. Bhattacharya and T. K. Mondal (Eds.), *National Seminar on Recent Trends in Knowledge Organization*.

- Saha, S & Hatua, S.R. (2019). Treatment of Humanities in DDC: a birds eye view. In U. Bhattacharya and T. K. Mondal (Eds.), *National Seminar on Recent Trends in Knowledge Organization*.
- Sanyal, A. (2022) An exploratory study of the Gender spectrum using N-Gram analysis to show its distribution in latest edition of DDC through literary warrant. *International Journal of Research in Library Science*, 8(3), 58-65